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Univerza v Ljubljani, Biotehniška fakulteta, Acta Biologica Slovenica,
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Matevž Likar, Slovenija / Slovenia, matevz.likar@bf.uni-lj.si

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Table of Contents

Original Research Paper

- 4 **Floristic Diversity and Halophytic Plant Communities Sahara (Algeria) / Floristična raznovrstnost in halofitske rastlinske skupnosti jezera Sif Lemnadi, severna Sahara (Alžirija)**
Belourghi Bariza, El Amine Khechekhouche, Zeid Alia, Laiz Aya, Menacer Nadia, Bachir Khezzani, Ghemam Amara Djilani
- 18 **Comparative study of heavy metal-induced oxidative stress responses in *Schizophyllum commune* Fr. and *Cyathus striatus* Willd. / Primerjalna študija odzivov na oksidativni stres, povzročen s težkimi kovinami, pri *Schizophyllum commune* Fr. in *Cyathus striatus* Willd.**
Priya Mondal, Dipak Kumar Kar, Subrata Raha
- 30 **Seasonal Variation of Orthoptera Densities in Lesser Kestrel Foraging Habitats of the Thessaly Plain / Sezonska spremenljivost gostote kobilic (Orthoptera) v habitatih prehranjevanja južne postovke na planoti Tesalije**
Christos E. Christakis, Athanassios I. Sfougaris
- 41 **Modelling and Mapping of Soil Salinity Related to Soil Characteristics and Irrigation in a Semi-Arid Context / Modeliranje in kartiranje slanosti tal v povezavi z značilnostmi tal in namakanjem v polsušnem okolju**
Yassine Al Masmoudi, Sanae Bel-Lahbib, Khalid Ibno Namr, Adil Jouamaa, Meryem Moustakim, Malika Laghrour, Badr Rerhou
- 59 **Effects of graded inclusion of *Jatropha tanjorensis* leaf meal on growth and feed utilisation in *Clarias gariepinus* / Vpliv postopnega dodajanja moke iz listov *Jatropha tanjorensis* na rast in izkoristek krme pri *Clarias gariepinus***
Emmanuel A. Essien, Aniefiokmkpong O. Okon, Enenwan P. Udoinyang, Prince-charles Omin Itu, Bernard Obagha Basse, Ndifreke Daniel Ekpo, Basse Okon Effanga
- 71 ***Pseudomonas stutzeri* AK17 Mediated Modulation of Plant Defence Responses under Drought Stress / Modulacija obrambnih odzivov rastlin pod vplivom suše, ki jo povzroča *Pseudomonas stutzeri* AK17**
Ritika Jain, Meenu Saraf, Dhaval Acharya, Rachana Shukla, Tisha Vyas, Shreya Modi, Tanvi Panchal
- 86 ***Erigeron sumatrensis* (Asteraceae): a new alien species to the flora of Kosovo / *Erigeron sumatrensis* (Asteraceae): nova tuja vrsta v flori Kosova**
Bujar Kadriaj, Naim Berisha

Review

- 94 **Pregled monitoringov biodiverzitete kmetijske krajine v Sloveniji in primerjava z izbranimi primeri iz tujine / Overview of biodiversity monitoring in agricultural landscapes of Slovenia and comparison with selected practices from abroad**
Irena Bertonec
- 104 **Plastika v kmetijstvu: uporaba in vplivi ostankov plastike na tla ter zelenjadarske pridelovalne sisteme / Plastics in agriculture: use and impact of residues on soil and vegetable production systems**
Špela Železnikar, Nina Kacjan-Maršič

Brief Note

- 117 **Fruit-Derived Biostimulants Promote *In Vitro* Regeneration in Mature Calamansi (*Citrus microcarpa* Bunge) Embryos / Uporaba izbranih pogosto zavrženih filipinskih sadežev kot naravni biostimulant za *in vitro* regeneracijo zrelih zarodkov kalamansija (*Citrus microcarpa* Bunge)**
Joseph Diaz, Rich Milton Dulay, Sofronio Kalaw, Mary Jhane Valentino

Original Research

Floristic Diversity and Halophytic Plant Communities of Lake Sif Lemnadi, Northern Sahara (Algeria)

Belourghi Bariza^{1,2}, El Amine Khechekhouche^{1,2*}, Zeid Alia^{1,3},
Laiz Aya^{1,2}, Menacer Nadia^{1,2}, Bachir Khezzani^{1,2},
Ghemam Amara Djilani^{1,2}

Abstract

This study aims to analyse the ecological and chorological characteristics of the flora of Lake Sif Lemnadi, located in the southeastern Saharan region of Algeria, to better understand this arid ecosystem's composition and floristic diversity. A biocoenotic analysis was carried out on four plots distributed according to the cardinal points of the site. In total, 14 species belonging to 9 families and 14 genera were recorded. Chamaephytes (50%) represented the dominant biological type, followed by hemicryptophytes (21.4%). For the frequency classes, the most represented categories were the very accidental and common species, each accounting for 42.9%. Perennial herbaceous plants dominated the morphological spectrum (50%). From a chorological perspective, species classified as Saharan elements were the best represented (35.7%). The vegetation cover ranged from 11.2% to 24.4%. The vegetation cover rate varied between 11.2% and 24.4%. The lakeshore vegetation was primarily dominated by halophytic species, mainly from the Amaranthaceae family. The variation in the total halophyte cover among plots was not influenced by their geographical orientation. These results highlight the ecological importance of Lake Sif Lemnadi as a refuge for Saharan halophytic communities and provide a baseline reference for the monitoring and conserving saline wetlands in Saharan contexts.

Keywords

Lake Sif Lemnadi, Sahara, Algeria, floristic diversity, biological types, halophytes.

1 Laboratory of Biology, Environment and Health, Department of Biology, Faculty of Life and Natural Sciences, University of El Oued, 39000, Algeria.

2 Department of Biology; Faculty of Life and Natural Sciences; University of El Oued, 39000, Algeria.

3 Department of Agronomy; Faculty of Life and Natural Sciences; University of El Oued, 39000, Algeria.

* Corresponding author:

E-mail address:

khechekhouche-elamine@univ-eloued.dz

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Floristična raznovrstnost in halofitske rastlinske skupnosti jezera Sif Lemnadi, severna Sahara (Alžirija)

Izvleček

Namen te študije je analizirati ekološke in korološke značilnosti flore jezera Sif Lemnadi, ki se nahaja v jugovzhodnem saharskem območju Alžirije, da bi bolje razumeli sestavo in floristično raznolikost tega sušnega ekosistema. Biocenotska analiza je bila izvedena na štirih parcelah, razporejenih glede na svetovne strani lokacije. Skupaj je bilo zabeleženih 14 vrst, ki pripadajo 9 družinam in 14 rodovom. Chamaefiti (50 %) so predstavljali prevladujoč biološki tip, sledili pa so jim hemikriptofiti (21,4 %). Glede na pogostost so bile najbolj zastopane kategorije zelo naključne in pogoste vrste, ki so predstavljale 42,9 %. Morfološko so prevladovala trajna zeliščna (50 %). S horološkega vidika so bile najbolj zastopane vrste, uvrščene med saharske elemente (35,7 %). Rastlinska pokrovnost je znašala od 11,2 % do 24,4 %. Stopnja rastlinske pokrovnosti je nihala med 11,2 % in 24,4 %. Ob jezeru je prevladovala predvsem halofitska flora, predvsem iz družine Amaranthaceae. Na razliko v skupni pokritosti s halofiti med parcelami ni vplivala njihova geografska usmerjenost. Ti rezultati poudarjajo ekološki pomen jezera Sif Lemnadi kot zatočišča za saharske halofitske skupnosti in zagotavljajo osnovno referenco za spremljanje in ohranjanje slanih mokrišč v saharskih kontekstih.

Ključne besede

Jezero Sif Lemnadi, Sahara, Alžirija, rastlinska raznovrstnost, biološki tipi, halofiti.

Introduction

Wetlands, long regarded as secondary habitats, play a fundamental role in maintaining biodiversity and regulating essential ecological cycles (Requier-Desjardins et al., 2021). In the Mediterranean region, they represent true hotspots of biological diversity, hosting plant and animal communities adapted to contrasting environmental conditions (Quézel & Santa, 1962).

Chotts and sebkhas are endorheic saline depressions typical of arid North Africa. Chotts are shallow basins that flood temporarily before drying into salt flats, while sebkhas are more permanently saline areas where groundwater and evaporation maintain moist, salty soils. Both host halophytic vegetation adapted to high salinity and water stress (Khaznadar et al., 2009).

In arid and semi-arid zones, such as the Algerian Sahara, chotts and sebkhas are of particular ecological importance as refuges for specialised flora. Chotts and sebkhas are endorheic (closed) saline depressions typical of arid North Africa. Chotts are shallow basins that can temporarily flood during rare rainfall events, forming ephemeral lakes that later dry out into salt flats. Sebkhas, in contrast, are more permanently saline areas where high groundwater tables

and intense evaporation maintain moist, salty soils throughout much of the year. These hydrosaline environments create harsh conditions with high salinity and water stress, yet they support the persistence of halophytic and succulent species highly adapted to such edaphic constraints (Khaznadar et al., 2009; Kaabeche et al., 1993; Pearce & Crivelli, 1994; Khan et al., 2006; Öztürk et al., 2011). Among the most representative plant families are the Amaranthaceae, particularly the genera *Atriplex*, *Suaeda*, *Salsola*, and *Salicornia* (Brown, 2006; Koull, 2023). These ecosystems contribute to biodiversity conservation and ecosystem resilience under both climatic variability and anthropogenic pressures (Benabadji et al., 2010; Chafic et al., 2013).

Algeria hosts more than 2,000 wetlands, of which 50 are listed under the Ramsar Convention, covering an area of nearly 3 million hectares (Balla, 2012). Most of these sites are concentrated in the eastern High Plateaus, where endorheic wetlands of high ecological value dominate. The Sahara, which covers more than 85% of the national territory, also harbours unique ecosystems such as sebkhas, chotts, and oases, where water availability strongly shapes the composition and distribution of plant communities (Marc et al., 2012; Chafic et al., 2013). Although locally rich in species, these habitats remain restricted to specific eco-

logical niches. Taxa such as *Salicornia fruticosa* and *Tamarix gallica* illustrate remarkable adaptive strategies to salinity and nutrient-poor soils (Holm et al., 1977; Marc et al., 2012).

Despite the richness and diversity of Algerian wetlands, floristic knowledge of these ecosystems remains highly uneven across regions. Most studies conducted to date have primarily focused on the ecology and vegetation of chotts and sebkhas in northern Algeria (Benabadji et al., 2010; Chenchouni, 2017; Bezzalla et al., 2018). In contrast, Saharan wetlands, although characterised by high floristic heterogeneity driven by hydrological fluctuations and saline constraints, remain largely under-documented (Chenchouni, 2012; Koull & Chehma, 2015, 2016; Khechekhouche et al., 2020). This lack of information is particularly pronounced in the endorheic depressions of the eastern Sahara, where variations in salinity and moisture directly influence the distribution, composition, and structure of plant communities (Marco et al., 2010; Štefanić et al., 2019).

Within this context, the floristic study of Lake Sif Lemnadi is of particular scientific interest. Located in the Souf region, this Saharan site remains poorly explored, despite its potential to harbour original plant assemblages shaped by distinctive edaphic constraints. The objective of the present study is therefore to characterise the floristic diversity and ecological traits of the plant communities of this lake, with the aim of filling a significant gap in knowledge of Saharan wetlands and providing essential baseline data for their monitoring and conservation.

Materials and Methods

Study area

Lake Sif Lemnadi (33°57'54" N; 6°22'3.92" E) is a saline wetland typical of Saharan regions (Figure 1). Its high salinity results primarily from soil salt leaching rather than from the composition of groundwater, a phenomenon frequently observed in Saharan wetlands (Koull, 2023).

The lake covers an area of approximately 60.45 hectares (Google Earth, 2019) and is situated at an average altitude of –23 m relative to sea level. Administratively, it is located about 100 km northwest of the capital of El Oued Province, in a region dominated by agricultural activities, particularly date palm cultivation (Voisin, 2004; Halis, 2024).

Climatically, the region is subject to a typical desert climate (BWh according to Köppen), characterised by per-

manent aridity (Côte, 2005; Côte, 2006). Meteorological data from the El Oued station (WMO code: 60559) covering 1989–2019 confirm the absence of a distinct wet season. January is the coldest month, with an average temperature of 12.4 °C, whereas July is the hottest, averaging 37.3 °C. Annual precipitation is low, irregular, and marked by strong interannual variability (Khechekhouche et al., 2020). Winds are frequent and exhibit notable seasonal variability (Voisin, 2004; Nadjah, 1971). During summer, the region is regularly affected by the Sirocco, accompanied by maximum temperatures often exceeding 40.8 °C.

Sampling and vegetation analysis

The floristic inventory of Lake Sif Lemnadi was carried out during the favourable vegetative growth period, in March and April 2019, following several preliminary field surveys. A subjective sampling approach was used to ensure that all plant species occurring at the site were recorded. Vegetation was studied using four rectangular plots measuring 100 m × 25 m (2,500 m² each), positioned at the four cardinal points of the lake (Neffar et al., 2016; Chenchouni, 2017). In each plot, a transect was established from the centre of the water body toward the outer margin in order to cross all vegetation belts associated with different hydrological conditions (Figure 1).

To obtain a detailed characterisation of the dominant halophytic vegetation, a total of 24 quadrats of 4 m² (2 × 2 m) were installed at regular intervals along the transects (6 quadrats per plot). Quadrats were placed so as to represent the main hydrological gradients of the site, including zones corresponding to minimal water level (peripheral dry belt), intermediate/average water level (periodically inundated belt), and maximal water level (proximal humid belt). For each quadrat, this allows the integration of micro-topographic variation into the vegetation analysis.

Within each quadrat, the cover of each species was visually estimated by measuring the area occupied and converting it into a percentage of the total quadrat surface (Van der Maarel, 1979; Neffar et al., 2013; Chenchouni, 2017). Recorded species were identified according to the standard floras of Algeria (Quézel & Santa, 1963; Ozenda, 1983; Halis, 2024), and life forms were classified following Raunkjær's system (Ellenberg & Mueller-Dombois, 1967). This sampling design enabled a consistent assessment of species relative abundance and the floristic composition of the plant communities across the lake's environmental gradients.

Figure 1. Location map of Sif Lemnadi lake (south-east Algeria).

Slika 1. Lokacijski zemljevid jezera Sif Lemnadi (jugovzhodna Alžirija).

Floristic analysis

Species richness (SR), defined as the total number of identified species, was used as the main indicator of plant diversity (Magurran, 2004). The relative abundance (RA) of each family was determined as the proportion of species belonging to that family relative to the total number of recorded species (SR). The frequency of occurrence (Occ) of each species was determined as the ratio between the number of plots where the species was recorded and the total number of plots studied. Species were then classified into four categories (Bigot & Bodot, 1973). To compare floristic composition among plots, Jaccard's similarity index was applied (Magurran, 2004).

This approach allows for the assessment of species diversity, community structure, and the degree of floristic similarity among the different zones of the lake.

Functional characterisation of plants

To better understand the ecological and adaptive strategies of the recorded species, plant functional traits (PFTs) were analysed based on major references (Quézel & Santa, 1962, 1963; Nègre, 1962; Ozenda, 1991) as well as databases such as Tela-Botanica. The approach was based on establishing

two types of biological spectra, expressed as percentages, allowing coherent comparisons between the different phytocological groups and the overall studied flora.

Life forms (Raunkiaer, 1934)

Life forms, defined according to the position of renewal buds and their protection against unfavourable conditions, reflect plant adaptive strategies. Four main categories were considered: i) Chamaephytes: buds located close to the ground, adapted to arid and constrained environments; ii) Hemicryptophytes: buds at ground level, allowing regeneration after climatic stress; iii) Phanerophytes: woody trees and shrubs, characterized by persistent aerial buds; iv) Therophytes: annual plants completing their life cycle within a single favorable season.

Morphological types

Species were also classified according to the persistence of their aerial parts: i) Perennial herbs: surviving for several years through underground organs; ii) Annual plants: completing their cycle in one season and persisting through seeds; iii) Woody plants: trees and shrubs with persistent structures, adapted to long-term survival.

Phytogeographical types

The biogeographical origin of taxa was determined from the main floristic references (Quézel & Santa, 1962, 1963; Ozenda, 1991). Species were assigned to several chorological groups representative of Saharan and Mediterranean flora, such as: i) Saharan endemics; ii) Mediterranean species, iii) Saharo-Arabian species; iv) Cosmopolitan species, etc.

This chorological classification provides insights into the biogeographical processes that shaped the local flora and allows the evaluation of the ecological specificity of the species found in the lake.

Statistical analyses

An agglomerative hierarchical clustering (AHC) was applied to classify the studied plots according to their floristic composition. Similarity between plots was assessed using Jaccard's index, which accounts for shared species and those specific to each plot.

The resulting similarity matrix was then subjected to AHC using the Unweighted Pair-Group Method with Arithmetic Mean (UPGMA). This method progressively groups the most similar plots to form homogeneous clusters, thereby identifying major trends in floristic structuring.

Results

Floristic composition and structure

The floristic inventory identified 14 vascular plant species, distributed across 14 genera and families (Table 1). The flora of Lake Sif Lemnadi is dominated by Amaranthaceae (28.6%), followed by Poaceae and Tamaricaceae (14.3% each). The other families represented, namely Cistaceae, Apocynaceae, Frankeniaceae, Plumbaginaceae, Juncaceae, and Zygophyllaceae, are each represented by a single species (7.1%).

This distribution highlights the predominance of halophytic families (Amaranthaceae, Tamaricaceae, Frankeniaceae, Plumbaginaceae), which are characteristic of saline habitats, while the presence of Poaceae reflects a certain degree of ecological heterogeneity. It should be noted that algae were observed in the shallow areas of Lake Sif Lemnadi in low abundance during the study period.

Ecological characteristics of the plant community

Analysis of biological types shows a dominance of chamaephytes (50%), followed by hemicryptophytes (21.4%) and geophytes (14.3%) (Figure 2). The predominance of chamaephytes, whose persistent buds are located close to the ground, reflects the adaptation of species to the arid and saline conditions of the environment. The notable proportion of hemicryptophytes also suggests the presence of species capable of withstanding seasonal drought, while geophytes indicate a survival strategy based on underground storage organs.

Regarding frequency of occurrence, very accidental species and common species predominate, each representing 42.9% of the recorded taxa, while constant species account for only 14.3% (Figure 3). This distribution highlights a relatively heterogeneous and fragmented plant community, where few species are widely distributed, and most have a restricted occurrence.

Morphological and Phytogeographical Spectra

The analysis of morphological types reveals a predominance of herbaceous plants (57.1%), the majority of which are perennial herbs (50%), followed by annual herbs (7.1%). Woody forms account for 42.9% of the recorded flora (Figure 4). This distribution reflects a plant community characterised by the resilience of perennial forms, capable of withstanding arid and saline conditions, and by the significant presence of woody species that stabilise soils and tolerate marked water stress.

From a chorological perspective, the flora of Lake Sif Lemnadi is mainly divided into three major groups (Figure 5). Saharan elements dominate (35.7%), highlighting the ecological imprint of the desert and the adaptation of species to hypersaline and xeric environments. Mediterranean species account for 28.6% of the flora, reflecting the influence of the temperate climate and floristic exchanges between arid and sub-humid zones. Mixed Mediterranean–Saharan taxa represent 14.3%, indicating an ecological transition gradient. It is worth noting that the presence of tropical or tropical–Saharan taxa (14.3%) illustrates the biogeographical diversity of the region and underscores the importance of the lake as a floristic crossroads.

Table 1. Systematic list of plant species recorded around Lake Sif Lemnadi (southeastern Algeria), with their life forms, chorological types, morphological types, frequency, and distribution scale.

Tabela 1. Sistematski seznam rastlinskih vrst, zabeleženih okoli jezera Sif Lemnadi (jugovzhodna Alžirija), z njihovimi življenjskimi oblikami, horološkimi tipi, morfološkimi tipi, pogostostjo in obsegom razširjenosti.

Familles	Scientific Name	Life Form (LF)	Chorological Type (CT)	Morphological Type	Occurrence (%)	scale
Poaceae	<i>Aeluropus littoralis</i> (Gouan) Parl.	Geophyte	Saharan	Perennial herbaceous	30	Common
	<i>Phragmites australis</i> subsp. <i>chrysanthus</i> (Mabille) Soják	Geophyte	Mediterranean	Perennial herbaceous	55	Constant
Amaranthaceae	<i>Cistanche lutea</i> (Desf.) Hoffmanns. & Link	Therophyte	Tropical-Saharan	Annual herbaceous	10	very accidental
	<i>Halochnemum strobilaceum</i> (Pall.) M. Bieb.	Chamaephyte	Saharan	Woody	60	Constant
	<i>Traganum nudatum</i> Delile	Chamaephyte	Saharan	Perennial herbaceous	5	very accidental
	<i>Sarcocornia perennis</i> subsp. <i>alpini</i> (Lag.) Castro.	Hemicryptophyte	Mediterranean-Saharan	Woody	30	Common
Cistaceae	<i>Helianthemum lippii</i> (L.) Dum.Cours.	Chamaephyte	Mediterranean	Woody	5	very accidental
Apocynaceae	<i>Cynanchum acutum</i> L.	Chamaephyte	Tropical	Perennial herbaceous	5	very accidental
Frankeniaceae	<i>Frankenia pulverulenta</i> subsp. <i>florida</i> (L. Chevall.) Maire	Chamaephyte	Mediterranean	Perennial herbaceous	10	very accidental
Plombaginaceae	<i>Limoniastrum guyonianum</i> Boiss.	Hemicryptophyte	Tropical-Saharan	Woody	20	accidentel
Tamaricaceae	<i>Tamarix gallica</i> L.	Phanerophyte	Mediterranean-Saharan	Woody	45	Common
	<i>Reaumuria vermiculata</i> L.	Chamaephyte	Saharan	Perennial herbaceous	5	very accidental
Juncaceae	<i>Juncus maritimus</i> Lam.	Hemicryptophyte	Mediterranean	Perennial herbaceous	35	Common
Zygophyllaceae	<i>Tetraena alba</i> (L.f.) Beier & Thulin	Chamaephyte	Saharan	Perennial herbaceous	45	Common

Figure 3. Proportion of occurrence frequency categories (C) of vegetation identified in Sif Lemnadi Lake.

Slika 3. Delež kategorij pogostosti pojavljanja (C) vegetacije, identificirane v jezeru Sif Lemnadi.

Figure 4. Proportion of plant morphological types identified in the vegetation of Sif Lemnadi Lake.

Slika 4. Delež morfoloških tipov rastlin, identificiranih v vegetaciji jezera Sif Lemnadi.

Species Occurrence Frequency

The analysis of species occurrence around Lake Sif Lemnadi (Figure 5) reveals a community dominated by very occasional species (42.9%), occurring sporadically and often associated with temporary or marginal microhabitats. Common species account for 35.7% of the flora, reflecting a regular but not permanent establishment across the studied plots. In contrast, occasional species are poorly represented (7.1%), whereas constant species (14.3%) indicate a stable floristic core capable of withstanding strong abiotic constraints, particularly salinity and water fluctuations.

This distribution suggests a generally unstable and heterogeneous vegetation, where few species succeed in establishing themselves durably, while the majority exhibit limited occurrence. Such a configuration is typical of saline and arid environments, where only certain specialised halophytic species form the ecological backbone of the community, while most taxa appear opportunistically or seasonally.

Floristic Diversity and Similarity

Species richness (SR) varies considerably among the studied plots (Table 2). The North plot (N) stands out with the highest floristic richness, with 11 recorded species, followed

by the West plot (W) with nine species and the East plot (E) with seven species. In contrast, the South plot (S) appears to be the least diverse, with only four species.

The analysis of Jaccard similarity indices (CJ) reveals high values between plots N and E (CJ = 0.64), indicating a substantial proportion of shared species. This floristic affinity may result from analogous ecological conditions or environmental gradients that favour the establishment of similar taxa. Intermediate similarities are also observed between N and W (CJ = 0.54) and between W and E (CJ = 0.60), suggesting an ecological continuity among these plots.

By contrast, the S plot shows much lower similarities with the others: S–W (CJ = 0.36) and S–N (CJ = 0.42). These values indicate a relative ecological isolation, probably linked to particular edaphic or hydric conditions that limit the number of shared species.

The overall analysis (Figure 6) thus highlights two contrasting groups:

- N and E form a relatively homogeneous core, characterised by a similar floristic composition and relatively high richness.
- S constitutes a distinct group, marked by reduced and specific flora, reflecting stronger ecological constraints.
- W occupies an intermediate position, showing affinities with N and E but also notable differences with S.

Table 2 reports Jaccard similarity indices (CJ, above diagonal) and the number of shared species (below diagonal). Station codes (N, S, E, W) indicate orientations around the lake, with species richness (SR) shown in the first column.

The hierarchical clustering analysis (HCA) based on these indices highlights the formation of three distinct groups (Figure 6):

1. A first group consisting of the plots located south (S) of the lake, characterised by a restricted and relatively isolated flora.
2. The East plot (E), which stands out as an autonomous group, reflects specific ecological conditions.
3. A third group comprising the North (N) and West (W) plots, reflecting greater floristic homogeneity and marked ecological affinities.

Contribution of dominant halophytes

Overall, vegetation cover at Lake Sif Lemnadi was relatively low, ranging from 11.2% to 24.9% across plots. Species were distributed in parallel bands along the salinity gradient, extending from the centre of the water body toward its margins. This gradient strongly influenced both the distribution and abundance of halophytes, with cover values also varying at the quadrat level.

Dominant species exhibited mean specific cover values between 20% and 30%, with extremes ranging from 4% to 50%. Among them, *Phragmites australis* was the most abundant, with a mean cover of $42.1 \pm 22.8\%$, highlighting its strong competitive ability and high tolerance to saline conditions. It occurred most frequently in plots located near the water body.

Along transects, this species was often interspersed with *Halocnemum strobilaceum* ($17.4 \pm 7.5\%$) and *Tamarix gallica* ($20.1 \pm 7.8\%$), both well represented in peripheral plots. In contrast, *Tetraena alba* appeared as a secondary

component, with a much lower average cover ($3.7 \pm 1.0\%$) (Figure 7).

Discussion

This study provides a detailed quantitative floristic analysis of the permanent saline lake of Sif Lemnadi, located in southern Algeria, a region characterised by extreme desert climatic conditions marked by low rainfall, frequent droughts, and high soil salinity. Worldwide, the number of halophytic species is estimated to range between 2,500 and 3,000, of which about 700 occur in the Mediterranean region (Khan & Dukes, 2001). In the framework of this study, the floristic inventory identified 14 plant species belonging to 9 families. Compared to other wetlands of the High Plateaus and northern Sahara (Chenchouni, 2012; Halis et al., 2012; Neffar et al., 2016; Chenchouni, 2017; Khechekhouche et al., 2020), the floristic richness of Lake Sif Lemnadi can be considered moderate. This level of richness appears to be proportional to the small size of the site and to the severity of its edaphic and climatic conditions.

As observed in other Saharan and steppe ecosystems, most of the species recorded belong to the Amaranthaceae, which are widely represented in saline habitats, and to the Poaceae, which are well adapted to hygrophilous environments. These results confirm that the flora of Lake Sif Lemnadi exhibits a plant assemblage typical of Mediterranean (Öztürk et al., 2011) and North African wetlands (Benabadiji et al., 2010; Ghezlaoui et al., 2011; Neffar et al., 2016).

The prevalence of halophilous and thermophilous species in the floristic composition reflects their remarkable ability to adapt to extreme and unstable environments (Neffar et al., 2016). Among them, *Phragmites australis* stands out due to its high cover and ubiquity, confirming its role as an ecosystem engineer capable of altering microhabitat conditions (soil structure, moisture, salinity) and thereby facilitating

Table 2. Proximity matrix applied to floristic similarity among the four sampled plots (by cardinal positions), considered in pairs.

Tabela 2. Matrika bližine, uporabljena za floristično podobnost med štirimi vzorčenimi parcelami (po kardinalnih položajih), obravnavana v parih.

Station	N	W	S	E
N (SR=11)		0,54	0,42	0,64
W (SR=9)	7		0,36	0,60
S (SR=4)	5	4		0,44
E (SR=7)	7	6	4	

Figure 6. Dendrogram of agglomerative hierarchical clustering (AHC) showing species richness (SR) similarity (Jaccard coefficient) among plants recorded at four stations around Lake Sif Lemnadi.

Slika 6. Dendrogram aglomerativnega hierarhičnega združevanja (AHC), ki prikazuje podobnost bogastva vrst (SR) (Jaccardov koeficient) med rastlinami, zabeleženimi na štirih postajah okoli jezera Sif Lemnadi.

Figure 7. Percentage cover of the dominant halophytic species recorded in the vegetation of Lake Sif Lemnadi (southeastern Algeria). Values indicate the relative contribution of each halophyte taxon to the overall community structure.

Slika 7. Odstotek pokritosti prevladujočih halofitnih vrst, zabeleženih v vegetaciji jezera Sif Lemnadi (jugovzhodna Alžirija). Vrednosti kažejo relativni prispevek vsakega halofitnega taksona k celotni strukturi skupnosti.

or limiting the establishment of other taxa. Alongside it, *Halocnemum strobilaceum* and *Tamarix gallica* play a key role in stabilising saline soils, while *Tetraena alba* appears as a secondary taxon, indicative of drier and more peripheral conditions. The spatial structuring of vegetation into parallel bands observed along the salinity gradient reflects a phenomenon of ecological segregation commonly found in North African chotts and sebkhas. This pattern supports the observations of Le Houérou (1992) and Neffar et al. (2018) regarding the strong influence of salinity and seasonal drought on the distribution of halophytic communities.

The site also hosts perennial species adapted to harsh climatic conditions (Khechekhouche et al., 2020). The vegetation is mainly composed of perennial herbaceous plants (50%) and shrubs (42.9%). These taxa exhibit adaptations not only to the high soil salinity but also to the long periods of summer heat. Most of them possess xero-halophytic traits that enable them to withstand such environmental constraints (Tug et al., 2012).

The spectrum of life forms is dominated by chamaephytes (50%), reflecting the typical influence of the Mediterranean semi-arid bioclimate (Medjahdi et al., 2009; Salama et al., 2014). These chamaephytes, entirely halophytic, are distinguished by their high tolerance to drought and salinity, unlike phanerophytes (Ellenberg & Mueller-Dombois, 1967; Ghezlaoui et al., 2011). Their widespread distribution around the lake is probably favoured by the absence of grazing, since livestock generally avoids saline plants (Neffar et al., 2016). Hemicryptophytes rank second, which may be related to the high organic matter content of soils (Bardgett et al., 2005).

The floristic distribution around the lake results from a complex interaction of several environmental factors, whether abiotic, biotic, or anthropogenic (Rozema et al., 1985; Alvarez-Rogel et al., 2007; Minggagud & Yang, 2013). According to Brown (2006), the mosaic structure of plant communities reflects the heterogeneity of environmental conditions, particularly soil moisture and salinity. Floristic diversity is also influenced by landscape organisation, land abandonment practices, and grazing regimes (Muñoz & Alcántara, 2013; Lomba et al., 2013).

Plots located to the north and west of Lake Sif Lemnadi exhibit relatively high floristic richness and homogeneity, whereas the southern plot remains the least diverse. This difference appears to be linked to the excess water from irrigation of the palm grove situated to the north, which carries residues of agricultural fertilisers. This additional water

input modifies the chemical and nutrient conditions of the habitat, thereby promoting the growth of certain species. However, the high soil salinity in the southern part limits vegetation development and reduces biodiversity (Bijos et al., 2023). In general, the vegetation of desert wetlands follows a concentric arrangement determined by a gradient of salinity and moisture (Koull, 2023).

Salinity is recognised as the main factor controlling the development, zonation, and density of vegetation in saline wetlands (Rozema et al., 1985; Alvarez-Rogel et al., 2007; Halis et al., 2012; Neffar et al., 2016; Chenchouni, 2017). The accumulation of salts in the soil reduces the water potential and limits water availability for plants, rendering the habitat physiologically dry (Djebaili, 1978). Variation in total vegetation cover also appears to depend on the distance and orientation of plots in relation to the water body, with halophytes colonising the saline margins (Aboura et al., 2006).

In these habitats, edaphic factors play a major role in the survival and distribution of species (Chenchouni, 2017). Salinity, moisture, and waterlogging strongly condition the floristic composition (Ji et al., 2009; Cott et al., 2013; González-Alcaraz et al., 2014). Several studies have shown that halophytic communities, whether coastal or inland, are closely dependent on such edaphic gradients. However, little research has focused on inland saline habitats in North Africa, particularly in arid and semi-arid wetlands (Chenchouni, 2012; El Ghani et al., 2014; Koull & Chehma, 2015; Neffar et al., 2016).

The results obtained at Sif Lemnadi confirm the observations made in other saline wetlands of the country. At Sabkha Djendli, vegetation follows a decreasing salinity gradient from the interior outward (Chenchouni, 2017). A similar pattern is observed in Chott El Gharbi, in western Algeria (Benabadji et al., 2010). Likewise, Khaznadar et al. (2009) and Bezzalla et al. (2019) showed that the distribution of halophytes depends on salinity, moisture, soil texture, temperature, water depth, and flooding duration. Finally, Gomaa (2012) highlighted that although electrical conductivity (EC) and specific resistance (SR) are correlated with vegetation cover, other factors may also influence community organisation.

Conclusion

This study highlights the ecological importance of Lake Sif Lemnadi as a refuge for specialised halophytic flora adapted to the extreme salinity and aridity of the northern Sahara.

This study highlights the ecological importance of Lake Sif Lemnadi as a refuge for specialised halophytic flora adapted to the extreme salinity and aridity of the northern Sahara. Overall, our findings met the objectives defined in this study by providing a comprehensive description of the floristic diversity and ecological strategies of species inhabiting Lake Sif Lemnadi. The analysis of life-form spectra and halophytic adaptations confirmed the predominance of xero-halophytic traits that structure plant communities under strong edaphic constraints. Similarly, the clear spatial zonation observed along the moisture and salinity gradients reflects a robust ecological pattern widely reported in Mediterranean and North African saline wetlands. Beyond their descriptive value, these results provide an essential baseline for the future monitoring of Saharan wetland vegetation. Given the sensitivity of these habitats to hydrological fluctuations, land use changes, and increasing salinisation, the floristic and ecological data provided here can support conservation planning and the development of sustainable management strategies aimed at preserving the unique biodiversity of desert wetlands.

Author Contributions

Conceptualization, B.B. and E.A.K.; methodology, B.B. and E.A.K.; investigation, B.B., E.A.K., Z.A., L.A., M.N., B.K., and

G.A.D.; formal analysis, B.B., Z.A. and E.A.K.; data curation, B.B. and E.A.K.; writing-original draft preparation, B.B. and E.A.K.; writing-review and editing, all authors; supervision, B.K. and G.A.D. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

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Data Availability

The datasets generated and analysed during the current study are openly available in the Zenodo repository at: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18173229>

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

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Original Research

Comparative study of heavy metal-induced oxidative stress responses in *Schizophyllum commune* Fr. and *Cyathus striatus* Willd.

Priya Mondal¹, Dipak Kumar Kar², Subrata Raha^{1*}

Abstract

Heavy metal exposure causes reactive oxygen species generation and oxidative stress in nearly all aerobic organisms. Antioxidant enzymes with free radical scavenging properties counter this oxidative stress produced by heavy metals. In this study, the effects of heavy metal-induced oxidative stress on the activities of antioxidant enzymes, including catalase, peroxidase, and superoxide dismutase, have been evaluated in two selected lignicolous fungal strains, *Schizophyllum commune* Fr. and *Cyathus striatus* Willd. The results showed that heavy metals exert toxicity in both fungal strains by affecting the oxidative metabolism, as evidenced by increased production of hydrogen peroxide. An increase in malonaldehyde concentration was observed at a concentration of 100 mg/L of metal ions, indicating that heavy metal exposure causes oxidative damage. To counter the oxidative stress, the activities of antioxidant enzymes, including catalase, peroxidase, and superoxide dismutase, were increased upon exposure to metal ion concentrations. However, a decrease in antioxidant enzyme activity was observed with a further increase in metal ion concentration, which indicates reactive oxygen species-induced oxidative stress. Furthermore, reduced glutathione also plays an important role in the detoxification of heavy metal ions at lower concentrations. Thus, this work suggests that these wood-rot fungi, *S. commune* and *C. striatus*, may have the potential to tolerate and accumulate heavy metals by the effective antioxidant defence mechanism, where catalase, peroxidase, superoxide dismutase, and glutathione may play a significant role in this resistance.

Keywords

Antioxidant responses, Intracellular accumulation, Lignicolous fungi, Metal ions, Reactive oxygen species

1 Department of Botany, Sidho-Kanho-Birsha University, Purulia, West Bengal-723104, India.

2 Vice Chancellor, Vidyasagar University, Midnapore, West Bengal-721102, India.

*** Corresponding author:**

E-mail address: subrata-raha@skbu.ac.in

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Primerjalna študija odzivov na oksidativni stres, povzročen s težkimi kovinami, pri *Schizophyllum commune* Fr. in *Cyathus striatus* Willd.

Izvleček

Izpostavljenost težkim kovinam povzroča nastajanje reaktivnih kisikovih spojin in oksidativni stres v skoraj vseh aerobnih organizmih. Antioksidativni encimi s sposobnostjo odstranjevanja prostih radikalov preprečujejo oksidativni stres, ki ga povzročajo težke kovine. V tej študiji so bili ocenjeni učinki oksidativnega stresa, ki ga povzročajo težke kovine, na aktivnosti antioksidativnih encimov, vključno s katalazo, peroksidazo in superoksid dismutazo, v dveh izbranih lignikolnih glivnih sevih, *Schizophyllum commune* Fr. in *Cyathus striatus* Willd. Rezultati so pokazali, da težke kovine povzročajo stres v obeh glivnih sevih, saj vplivajo na oksidativni metabolizem, kar dokazuje povečana proizvodnja vodikovega peroksida. Pri koncentraciji 100 mg/l kovinskih ionov je bilo opazno povečanje koncentracije malonaldehida, kar kaže, da izpostavljenost težkim kovinam povzroča oksidativno poškodbo. Da bi se zoperstavile oksidativnemu stresu, se je aktivnost antioksidativnih encimov v glivah, vključno s katalazo, peroksidazo in superoksid dismutazo, povečala. Vendar je bilo pri nadaljnjem povečanju koncentracije kovinskih ionov opazno zmanjšanje aktivnosti antioksidativnih encimov, kar kaže na oksidativni stres, ki ga povzročajo reaktivne kisikove spojine. Poleg tega ima zmanjšana koncentracija glutationa pomembno vlogo tudi pri razstrupljanju kovinskih ionov v nižjih koncentracijah. Ta raziskava torej kaže, da imata lesni glivi *S. commune* in *C. striatus*, potencial za prenašanje in kopičenje težkih kovin z učinkovitim antioksidativnim obrambnim mehanizmom, pri čemer imajo katalaza, peroksidaza, superoksid dismutaza in glutation pomembno vlogo pri tej odpornosti.

Ključne besede

Antioksidativni odzivi, Intracelularna akumulacija, Lignikolne glive, Kovinski ioni, Reaktivne kisikove spojine

Introduction

Heavy metal contamination of the aquatic ecosystem has been a global concern over the past few years. Overexposure to heavy metals from industrial smelting, mining ore, agriculture, burning fossil fuels, etc., has been a serious concern nowadays (Mishra and De, 2024). Heavy metals, including copper, cadmium, lead, strontium, nickel, and arsenic, are harmful to various organisms due to their significant bioaccumulation and potential mutagenic and carcinogenic effects (Mondal et al., 2024a). To combat this persistent issue, bioremediation offers a conventional clean-up technology due to its cost-effectiveness and comparatively low harmful impact on the environment. Remediation of heavy metals using biological entities has emerged as an attractive approach to eliminate these heavy metals, which potentially may be conducted with minimal costs and are eco-friendly. Among the various approaches, the mycoremediation technique has been gaining attention recently due to its eco-friendly, cost-effective, and highly

efficient approach (Koul et al., 2021). Both extracellular adsorption and intracellular accumulation are responsible in fungi for the elimination and uptake of metal ions from contaminated sites (Kumar and Dwivedi, 2021). To broaden the application of this technology, it is crucial to comprehend the microbial defence systems that protect against cellular toxicity caused by heavy metals.

Heavy metals can exert toxicity by multiple mechanisms. For instance, metals can cause oxidative stress by scavenging thiols, such as cysteine and glutathione, which are significant non-enzymatic antioxidants (Georgiou-Siafis and Tsiftoglou, 2023). Certain heavy metal ions integrate into the cytoplasm and induce reactive oxygen species (ROS) production, which impacts the mitochondrial microsome, metabolites, intermediates, and cell organelles. This creates a potent oxidising environment *in vivo* that can block the expression of mRNA, substitute the ligand in the active sites of the enzymes, damage DNA and membranes, cause lipid peroxidation, and ultimately result in apoptosis (Zhang et al., 2015). Additionally, metals may result in physi-

ological stress by producing chemical stressors that trigger the generation of ROS, including H_2O_2 , O_2^- , $\cdot OH$, etc. (Alam and Kataria, 2021). Understanding the antioxidant systems of an organism is crucial to determining the effects of metal exposure, as they are the potential targets of heavy metals.

Heavy metals can cause oxidative stress, which starts the production of ROS and eventually affects the cellular components. To counter this effect, the cellular antioxidant defence system plays an important role by scavenging ROS and maintaining cellular redox balance. The antioxidant system is composed of both enzymatic and non-enzymatic antioxidants. Certain antioxidant enzymes, including Catalase (CAT), Peroxidase (POD), Superoxide dismutase (SOD), and non-enzymatic antioxidants like Glutathione peroxidase (GPx), play an important role in defence against oxidation by sequentially sequestering O_2^- and H_2O_2 (Berni et al. 2019). CAT and POD mainly catalyse the conversion of H_2O_2 into water and oxygen rather than singlet oxygen. SOD dismutates the highly reactive superoxide anion (O_2^-) into H_2O_2 and O_2 (Ighodaro et al., 2018). Additionally, the reduced glutathione (GSH) is an essential component in metal scavenging due to the strong affinity of metals for its thiol (-SH) group and its role as a precursor of phytochelatins (Georgiou-Siafis and Tsiftoglou, 2023). GSH catalyses the reduction of oxidised glutathione (GSSG) back to its active form, GSH. GSH acts as a major antioxidant and is composed of glutamine, glycine, and cysteine. Furthermore, heavy metal-mediated inactivation of enzymatic antioxidants may occur through the substitution of cofactors necessary for enzyme function or through metal interaction with sulfhydryl or other functional groups. Understanding the role of these enzymes in the degradation and adsorption of heavy metals is essential to comprehend the biochemical and molecular mechanisms of the biodegradation process.

Wood-rot fungi typically have large biomass, and some strains are known to uptake and eliminate metal ions from contaminated sites and wastewater (Mondal et al., 2024a; 2024b). However, despite several reports on the ability of these fungi to remove heavy metals, the cellular response of fungi to heavy metal stress remains largely unknown. In this study, two selected wood rot fungi, *Schizophyllum commune* and *Cyathus striatus*, have been investigated for their oxidative stress response under heavy metal stress. These fungi are known for lignin degradation (Asgher et al., 2016; Sánchez-Ruiz et al., 2024) and have earlier been reported for the adsorption of certain metal ions (Mondal

et al., 2024b; 2025; Chaudhary and Shukla, 2019). The physiological impacts and oxidative stress responses of heavy metals on these fungal strains are still not reported. The present study aims to ascertain how the antioxidant enzymes function after being exposed to heavy metals. The effect of heavy metals (particularly lead, cadmium, zinc, and strontium) on the enzymatic responses (including CAT, POD, SOD, and GSH) has been investigated to determine the oxidative defence mechanisms.

Material and Methods

Fungal biomass preparation

The fungal specimens were collected from the forest area of Purulia district, West Bengal, India. The fruiting bodies were surface sterilised using 1 % Sodium hypochlorite, followed by rinsing with distilled water, and then inoculated on potato dextrose agar (PDA) petri-plates. The plates were kept at 28 ± 2 °C for 5-6 days for the growth of mycelia. Later, the mycelia were transferred to 100 ml of potato dextrose broth (PDB) medium containing different concentrations of metal ion solution, and incubated in a shaker at 100 rpm for 7 days at 28 ± 2 °C. The concentration (100-500 mg/L) of Pb(II), Cd(II), Zn(II), and Sr(II) was prepared using metal salt precursors, such as $Pb(C_2H_3O_2)_2$, $CdCO_3$, $ZnSO_4 \cdot 7H_2O$, and $Sr(NO_3)_2$. The biomass was harvested after 7 days and disrupted using an ultrasonicator for 3.5 min with an interval of 8 sec at 25 °C with an ice bath (Zhang et al., 2015). The homogenised cell-free extract tissue was obtained after centrifuging the homogenised solution at 4 °C.

Cell lysis and estimation of total protein

The cell lysis was performed using lysis buffer containing Tween 80 (1.5% v/v), Triton X-100 (0.5% v/v), Cetyltrimethylammonium Bromide (CTAB) (1% w/v), Sodium Dodecyl Sulphate (SDS) (5% w/v) in phosphate buffer (pH 7.8) (Alam and Kataria, 2021). The heavy metal accumulated biomass (0.1 g) was suspended in the detergent solution (1.0 ml) for 30 mins and lysed in an incubator shaker at 100 rpm at 28 ± 2 °C. The disrupted cell lysate was centrifuged at 10000 rpm for 15 min at 4 °C. The supernatant was collected, and protein content was estimated by Lowry's method for crude samples (Christias et al., 1975). To quantify the total protein, Bovine Serum Albumin (BSA) was used as a standard.

Estimation of malonaldehyde (MDA) content

The MDA concentration was determined using homogenised tissue extract (0.5 ml) dissolved in 0.1% (w/v) Trichloroacetic acid (TCA) solution (Zhang et al., 2016). The mixture was centrifuged for 15 min at 10000 rpm, and 0.5 ml supernatant was added to 0.5% Thiobarbituric acid (TBA) in 20% TCA. The mixture was heated at 90 °C for 30 min, and after cooling, the tubes were centrifuged at 4000 rpm for 10 min at room temperature. The absorbance was measured at 532 nm and 600 nm, and the difference in absorbance was calculated as MDA concentration.

Estimation of catalase activity

For estimating CAT activity, a total of 3 mL of reaction mixture was prepared, which consisted of 1 mL H₂O₂ (0.3 % v/v), 1.9 mL potassium phosphate buffer (50 mM, pH 7.0), and 0.1 mL of homogenised tissue extract (Alam and Kataria, 2021). A decrease in absorbance per minute at 240 nm was observed due to enzymatic decomposition of H₂O₂. The decrease in absorbance per minute per mg of protein in 1 ml of solution at 240 nm was used to define one unit of enzyme activity.

Estimation of peroxidase activity

The POD activity was determined using a 3 mL reaction mixture solution which contained 1 mL guaiacol (0.2 % v/v), 1 mL H₂O₂ (0.3 % v/v), 0.1 mL of homogenised tissue extract, and 0.9 mL phosphate buffer (50 mM, pH 7.0) (Alam and Kataria, 2021). The increase in absorbance at 470 nm per minute per mg of protein in 1 ml of solution was considered to be one unit of enzyme activity.

Estimation of superoxide dismutase activity

The SOD activity was determined by the nitro blue tetrazolium (NBT) method (Beauchamp and Fridovich, 1971). The blank contained 0.2 ml phosphate buffer, 2.5 ml methionine, 0.3 ml riboflavin; the test contained 0.1 ml NBT, 2.5 ml methionine, 0.3 ml riboflavin, 0.1 ml tissue extract; the standard contained 0.1 ml phosphate buffer, 0.1 ml NBT, 2.5 ml methionine, 0.3 ml riboflavin; the control contained 0.1 ml phosphate buffer, 2.5 ml methionine, 0.3 ml riboflavin, 0.1 ml tissue extract. The standard tube was without the enzyme (tissue extract), and the control was without the substrate

(NBT). The test tube contained substrate and enzyme, and the blank contained neither substrate nor enzyme. Each set of tubes was kept in an illumination chamber for 20 min. The substrate reacted with superoxide anions generated when riboflavin was illuminated with methionine (electron donor) and produced a blue colour complex, formazan. The SOD in the sample was directly proportional to the decrease in formazan formation. One unit of SOD was defined as a 50% reduction in formazan formation. The specific activity of the enzyme was calculated as U/mg protein.

Estimation of glutathione content

To estimate the GSH content, the mycelial extract was prepared by homogenising 0.1 g of mycelia with 1.0 ml of 5% (v/v) sulfosalicylic acid containing 0.1% (v/v) Triton X solution and 1 mM Ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid (EDTA). The mixture was centrifuged at 8000 rpm for 10 min at 4 °C. The supernatant was used for GSH estimation using the sulfhydryl reagent 5,5'-dithio-bis (2-nitrobenzoic acid) (DTNB). The supernatant (0.5 ml) was mixed with 0.5 ml of 3 mM DTNB and 2.0 ml reaction buffer and kept at room temperature for 10 min. Later, the absorbance was measured at 412 nm for the determination of GSH. The same reaction mixture was supplemented with β-NADPH (0.2 mM) and glutathione reductase (0.1 U mL⁻¹), and a yellow colour derivative, 5'-thio-2-nitrobenzoic acid (TNB), was formed (Huang et al., 2017). The absorbance was measured at 412 nm for the determination of total glutathione. The GSSG was measured from the difference between total glutathione and GSH.

Statistical analysis

All the experiments were carried out in triplicate. The experimental data were given as the mean ± Standard deviation (SD). The results were analysed by one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) using SPSS v18.0. A value of P < 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results

Tolerance of fungal biomass to metal ions

The molecular characterisation of fungal specimens was earlier performed based on ITS rRNA sequencing (Mondal et al., 2024b; 2025). The sequences were deposited in

the NCBI GenBank database (Accession no. PP947802 for *Cyathus striatus* and PP947751 for *Schizophyllum commune*). The optimum growth conditions of the fungal mycelia and fungal biomass inoculated with metal ions were found at a temperature of 28 ± 2 °C and pH 6. The fungal strains exhibited growth up to a maximum concentration of 500 mg/L for Pb(II), Sr(II), Zn(II), and Cd(II). However, the growth of fungal biomass decreased with increasing metal concentration, and no growth was observed at concentrations above 500 mg/L. The fungal biomass was harvested after 7 days of incubation with metal ions using Whatman filter paper No. 4 (20 to 25 μ m). Later, the biomass was repeatedly washed with distilled water and kept at -80 °C for further antioxidant enzyme estimations.

Protein estimation

Protein estimation was performed following Lowry's method using BSA as a standard. The total protein content of the biomass before and after accumulating metal ions is shown in Fig. 1. The total protein of untreated biomass was observed as 0.080 ± 0.004 mg/ml for *C. striatus* and 0.011 ± 0.0005 mg/ml for *S. commune*. In *C. striatus*, the protein content increased to 4-fold at an initial concentration of metal ions, and later it decreased with higher concentrations. The maximum protein content was observed as 0.350 ± 0.019 mg/ml after exposure to 100 mg/L Pb(II), and the minimum was observed as 0.037 ± 0.010 mg/ml after

exposure to 500 mg/L Sr(II) in *C. striatus*. Whereas the highest protein content was 0.219 ± 0.010 mg/ml after accumulating 200 mg/L Zn(II), and the lowest was observed as 0.011 ± 0.0008 mg/ml after accumulating 100 mg/L Pb(II) in *S. commune*. The protein content in *S. commune* after accumulating Pb(II) was comparatively lower than that of other metal ions, which indicates that Pb(II) might have little influence on total protein content.

Malonaldehyde estimation

The MDA content, as the end product of lipid peroxidation, was estimated to measure the oxidative damage after accumulation of metal ions. The MDA content of the untreated biomass of *C. striatus* and *S. commune* was 0.765 ± 0.090 and 0.782 ± 0.157 μ M/g, respectively. The MDA content was significantly increased at a metal ion concentration of 100 mg/L and later decreased at higher concentrations (Fig. 2). In *C. striatus*, the maximum MDA content was observed as 3.458 ± 0.201 μ M/g after exposure to 100 mg/L Sr(II), and the minimum was observed as 0.653 ± 0.039 μ M/g after exposure to 500 mg/L Cd(II). In case of *S. commune*, the highest MDA content was 3.483 ± 0.271 μ M/g after exposure to 100 mg/L Cd(II), and the lowest was 1.075 ± 0.208 μ M/g after exposure to 500 mg/L Cd(II). For both fungal strains, it was observed that the MDA concentration was highest at the lowest concentration of metal ions, and later it decreased at higher concentrations.

Figure 1. Effect of metal ion exposure on Protein content of *C. striatus* (a) and *S. commune* (b). Malonaldehyde estimation.

Slika 1. Vpliv izpostavljenosti kovinskim ionom na vsebnost beljakovin v *C. striatus* (a) in *S. commune* (b) ocena malonaldehida.

Catalase estimation

The significance of oxidative stress in the alteration of the antioxidant enzymes (including CAT, POD, and SOD) was assessed by analysing the impact of treatment with different concentrations (100–500 mg/l) of the heavy metals. The significance of CAT as a key antioxidant defence in both fungal strains is evidenced by the increased CAT activity in response to heavy metals. The CAT activity of untreated biomass of *C. striatus* and *S. commune* was observed as 0.005 ± 0.0009 and 0.005 ± 0.002 U/L, respectively. However, the CAT activity increased with initial exposure

of 100 mg/L metal ions in both strains and decreased with higher metal ion concentrations (Fig. 3). In *C. striatus*, the maximum CAT activity was observed as 0.065 ± 0.002 U/L with exposure to 100 mg/L Pb(II), while the minimum activity was observed as 0.008 ± 0.0008 U/L with exposure to 500 mg/L Zn(II). In *S. commune*, on exposure to 300 mg/L Cd(II), the highest CAT activity (0.025 ± 0.002 U/L) was observed, and the lowest CAT activity (0.003 ± 0.0005 U/L) was observed at 500 mg/L Zn(II). In *S. commune*, the CAT activity increased nearly 5-fold at 400 mg/L of Cd(II); however, a sharp decline was observed at 500 mg/L Cd(II), reaching 0.012 ± 0.001 U/L.

Figure 2. Effect of metal ion exposure on MDA content of *C. striatus* (a) and *S. commune* (b) Catalase estimation.

Slika 2. Vpliv izpostavljenosti kovinskim ionom na vsebnost MDA v *C. striatus* (a) in *S. commune* (b) ocena katalaze.

Figure 3. Effect of metal ion exposure on CAT activity of *C. striatus* (a) and *S. commune* (b) Peroxidase estimation.

Slika 3. Vpliv izpostavljenosti kovinskim ionom na aktivnost CAT pri *C. striatus* (a) in *S. commune* (b) ocena peroksidaze.

Peroxidase estimation

The POD activity with exposure to heavy metals is shown in Fig. 4. The POD activity of untreated *C. striatus* and *S. commune* biomass was observed as 1.906 ± 0.654 U/L and 1.646 ± 0.270 U/L, respectively. Like CAT, the POD activity also significantly increased during the initial exposure to heavy metal (100 mg/L), which suggests that it might be an ROS scavenger in the antioxidant system. On exposure to 100 mg/L Zn(II), *C. striatus* showed the highest POD activity (32.63 ± 0.811 U/L), and the lowest (2.426 ± 1.916 U/L) was observed with exposure to 500 mg/L Cd(II). The POD activity of *C. striatus* on exposure to Cd(II) was comparatively lower than exposure to other metal ions, which indicates that Cd(II) might have little influence on POD. In case of *S. commune*, the maximum POD activity (6.500 ± 0.520 U/L) was observed with exposure to 100 mg/L Pb(II), and the lowest (1.950 ± 0.260 U/L) was observed for 500 mg/L Zn(II). The results revealed that changes in POD activity of *S. commune* were comparatively lower than those of *C. striatus* on exposure to metal ions.

Superoxide dismutase estimation

The SOD activity, like CAT and POD, also increased on exposure to metal ions and decreased at higher metal concentrations. The SOD activity of untreated *C. striatus* and *S. commune* biomass was 0.009 ± 0.0009 and 0.011 ± 0.0006

U/mg, respectively. At an initial concentration of metal ions (100 mg/L), the SOD activity significantly increased in both strains. In *C. striatus*, the SOD activity reached its maximum value (0.054 ± 0.005 and 0.054 ± 0.002 U/mg) on exposure to 300 mg/L Zn(II) and 400 mg/L Pb(II), while the lowest activity (0.014 ± 0.003 U/mg) was observed at 500 mg/L Zn(II). In *S. commune*, SOD reached its maximum activity (0.062 ± 0.0007 U/mg) on exposure to 400 mg/L Sr(II), and the lowest activity (0.015 ± 0.003 U/mg) was observed after exposure to 500 mg/L Pb(II), as shown in Fig. 5.

Glutathione estimation

The GSH activity with exposure to heavy metals is shown in Fig. 6. The GSH activity of untreated *C. striatus* and *S. commune* biomass was observed as 7.896 ± 1.002 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ and 7.303 ± 0.559 $\mu\text{g/ml}$, respectively. The highest GSH concentration (69.229 ± 1.050 $\mu\text{g/ml}$) was observed on exposure to 100 mg/L Zn(II), and the lowest (17.155 ± 1.237 $\mu\text{g/ml}$) was observed on exposure to 500 mg/L Pb(II) in *C. striatus*. The GSH content increased with an increase in concentration of Sr(II) and Cd(II) in *C. striatus*. In case of *S. commune*, the highest GSH content (93.674 ± 1.667 $\mu\text{g/ml}$) was observed for 100 mg/L Cd(II), and the lowest (12.044 ± 1.175 $\mu\text{g/ml}$) was observed for 500 mg/L Pb(II). In *S. commune*, except for Sr(II), the GSH content decreased with an increase in metal ion concentration.

The detailed numerical data for all the enzymatic activity measurements are provided in Table S1.

Figure 4. Effect of metal ion exposure on POD activity of *C. striatus* (a) and *S. commune* (b). Superoxide dismutase estimation.

Slika 4. Vpliv izpostavljenosti kovinskim ionom na aktivnost POD pri *C. striatus* (a) in *S. commune* (b) ocena superoksid dismutaze.

Figure 5. Effect of metal ion exposure on SOD activity of *C. striatus* (a) and *S. commune* (b). Glutathione estimation.

Slika 5. Vpliv izpostavljenosti kovinskim ionom na aktivnost SOD pri *C. striatus* (a) in *S. commune* (b) Ocena glutationa.

Figure 6. Effect of metal ion exposure on GSH content of *C. striatus* (a) and *S. commune* (b).

Slika 6. Vpliv izpostavljenosti kovinskim ionom na vsebnost GSH v *C. striatus* (a) in *S. commune* (b)

Discussion

Mycoremediation using Basidiomycota fungi nowadays offers a promising approach for treating water contaminated with heavy metals due to their high biomass production, strong metal binding capacity, and efficient enzymatic systems (Zare et al., 2024). Cell walls of lignicolous fungi are rich in functional groups, such as amino, carboxyl, hydroxyl, and phosphate groups, which facilitate the adsorption and accumulation of metal ions (Mondal et al., 2024b; 2025). Furthermore, effective colonization

and metal immobilization in aquatic environments are facilitated by their extensive hyphal networks and ability to grow on lignocellulosic substrates. These fungi typically use two mechanisms to remove heavy metals from liquid cultures: intracellular bioaccumulation and extracellular adsorption. The biosorption processes often include surface adsorption by ion-exchange, surface precipitation, and hydrolytic adsorption, which make it easier for ions to pass through the cell wall and membrane (Mondal et al., 2024a). However, when metal ions enter the cell, they disrupt the cellular redox homeostasis, which starts the

production of ROS, and subsequently leads to oxidative stress. Excessive ROS might cause harmful effects on cells and cause functional changes in protein and lipid peroxidation (Berni et al., 2019). Nonetheless, the antioxidant system of fungi aids in scavenging excessive ROS through coordinated enzymatic and non-enzymatic defences, thereby preventing ROS accumulation and maintaining cellular redox homeostasis. In response to heavy metal stress, fungal biomass ensures a balanced antioxidative system by producing enzymatic antioxidants, like CAT, POD, SOD, and non-enzymatic antioxidants, like GSH, and protects its cellular components (Li et al., 2020).

In this study, the ability of two selected wild strains of lignicolous fungi, *Cyathus striatus* and *Schizophyllum commune*, was investigated to grow in liquid media containing different concentrations (100-500 mg/L) of metal ions. The selected strains showed tolerance to metal ions, including Pb(II), Sr(II), Zn(II), and Cd(II) up to a concentration of 500 mg/L. The metal uptake capacity of live biomass of *C. striatus* and *S. commune* was earlier reported as 65.55, 56.15, 71.33, and 65.94 mg/g and 81.5, 90.71, 70.18, 66.18 mg/g, and for Pb(II), Sr(II), Zn(II), and Cd(II), respectively (Mondal et al., 2024b; Mondal et al., 2025). In this study, the protein content of the fungal mycelium was significantly higher at lower concentrations of metal ions, which might be attributed to metal-protein interactions and initial adaptive response to metal exposure (Kalsoom et al., 2023). However, a relative decrease in protein content was observed with increased metal concentration, indicating ROS-induced oxidative stress and possible protein oxidation or degradation. Similar findings were observed for *Sclerotium rolfsii* (Rafi et al., 2017) and *Talaromyces pinophilus* (Dwivedi, 2023). Additionally, the important antioxidant enzymes, including CAT, POD, SOD, and their responses to different concentrations of metal ions, were also examined. The three antioxidant enzymes exhibit different responses to exposure to metal ions. Increased concentrations of metal ions generate more free radicals in *S. striatus* and *C. commune*, which creates strong oxidising conditions *in vivo*. We found that CAT activity suddenly increased at 100 mg/L concentration of metal ions and decreased at higher concentrations, suggesting that metal ions induce H_2O_2 accumulation and cause oxidative damage. Similar results were reported in *Phanerochaete chrysosporium* for the removal of Cd(II) and *Pleurotus ostreatus* for the tolerance of Pb(II) (Zhang et al., 2015; 2016). Similarly, the POD activity also increased with exposure to metal ions and later

decreased at higher concentrations. However, the activity of CAT was comparatively lower than POD activity under identical conditions for both fungal strains. The inhibition of CAT and POD at higher concentrations of metal ions may be due to enhanced production of H_2O_2 , which eventually suppresses the CAT and POD activity (Sidhu et al., 2016).

SOD is also one of the antioxidant enzymes that protects the cells from both internal and external ROS in all aerobic species (Ozougwu, 2016). SOD catalyses the dismutation of O_2^- , O_2 , and H_2O_2 , which is later reduced by CAT and POD. In this study, the SOD activity also increased with metal ion concentrations and further decreased at higher concentrations. Increased SOD activity could be due to the direct effect of heavy metal ions or an indirect effect mediated by an increase in superoxide radical levels and the de novo synthesis of enzyme proteins (Dhalaria et al., 2020). The upregulation of SOD during the metal ion exposure enhances the dismutation of O_2^- into less reactive species, thereby reducing the oxidative stress. Consistent with the findings, *Pleurotus ostreatus* and *Aspergillus oryzae* were reported to show similar results during oxidative stress induced by Pb(II) and Cu(II), respectively (Zhang et al., 2016; Long et al., 2017). Also, *Phanerochaete chrysosporium* showed similar results for the accumulation of Pb(II) (Huang et al., 2017).

On exposure to metal ions, the phospholipid bilayers of cell membranes are vulnerable to ROS oxidation, which results in lipid peroxidation (El-Mahdy et al., 2021). MDA, which is a major byproduct of lipid peroxidation, acts as a biomarker of oxidative stress. In this study, MDA showed the extent of ROS-induced membrane damage, which also increased drastically at the initial concentration (100 mg/L) of metal ions in both fungal strains. However, the MDA concentration gradually decreased with an increase in the concentration of metal ions up to 500 mg/L. This may be attributed to an initial increase in lipid peroxidation caused by elevated ROS generation at moderate metal exposure. At higher metal concentrations, enhanced activation of antioxidant defence mechanisms and reduced metabolic activity may limit the ROS production and membrane lipid oxidation, resulting in lower MDA levels (Luo et al., 2022). Similar results were reported under Cd and Cu stress in an ectomycorrhizal fungus, *Lepista sordida* (Dachuan and Jinyu, 2021) and in *Pleurotus ostreatus* HAU-2 for accumulation of Pb(II) (Zhang et al., 2016).

The detoxification of non-essential heavy metals often occurs by the synthesis of low molecular weight chelators, like GSH. Heavy metal exposure, oxidative stress, and lack

of sulphur or nitrogen are among the stress factors that influence this process (Huang et al., 2017). GSH accumulation is impeded by prolonged and excessive exposure to heavy metals, most likely because of the possible toxicity of heavy metals to microorganisms. GSH, a significant non-enzymatic antioxidant, was evaluated at varying concentrations of metal ions. Results showed that GSH activity increased with 100 mg/L metal ion concentration in both strains. However, in *C. striatus*, it was observed that with an increase in metal ion concentration, the GSH activity decreased when exposed to Pb(II) and Zn(II) and increased when exposed to Sr(II) and Cd(II). The decrease in GSH activity at higher concentrations of metal ions confirmed that the metal ions induce ROS production (Gulcin and Alwasel, 2022). Similarly, in *S. commune*, with an increase in metal ion concentration, the GSH activity decreased for Pb(II), Zn(II), and Cd(II) and increased in the case of Sr(II). These variations in results might be due to the excessive exposure to metal ions, which decreased the GSH level, probably due to excessive utilisation in ROS scavenging (Mansoor et al., 2023). In some cases, the GSH synthesis is upregulated with an increase in metal ion concentration via the γ -glutamyl cycle to detoxify the metal ions (Georgiou-Siafis and Tsiftoglou, 2023). Additionally, metal ions reduce the availability of sulfhydryl groups or other functional groups that are bound to proteins and can substitute for cofactors necessary for enzyme functions. This makes these enzymatic antioxidants vulnerable to metal-induced inactivation, which increases the production of ROS like H_2O_2 , hydroxyl radicals, and the superoxide species (Khullar and Sudhakara Reddy, 2019). At higher metal ion concentrations, the gradual accumulation of GSSG was observed, which suggests that GSH could react with H_2O_2 to produce GSSG, catalysed by glutathione peroxidase. Similar results were observed for the accumulation of Pb(II) in *P. ostreatus* (Zhang et al., 2016) and in *Phanerochaete chrysosporium* (Xu et al., 2014). Furthermore, heavy metals can be sequestered and detoxified by the GSH-dependent synthesis of metal-binding peptides, such as phytochelatins, which increases GSH depletion by producing persistent GSH-metal complexes intracellularly (Huang et al., 2017).

Conclusion

In the present work, *C. striatus* and *S. commune* were investigated for their tolerance and oxidative stress response

to heavy metal stress. *S. commune* and *C. striatus* both showed a high level of heavy metal tolerance and were able to endure up to 500 mg/L. Upon exposure to heavy metals, the intracellular accumulation of H_2O_2 increased, which triggered lipid peroxidation and subsequent MDA production. Heavy metal exposure significantly altered the activity of enzymatic and non-enzymatic antioxidants, reflecting an induced cellular stress response that protects the cells against ROS. An increase in protein content and activity of antioxidant enzymes, including CAT, POD, and SOD, at the initial exposure to metal ions suggests a coordinated defence response to counteract metal-induced oxidative stress. Additionally, the GSH also plays an important role in the detoxification of metal ions, indicating its involvement in maintaining intracellular redox balance. However, at higher metal concentrations, a decline in CAT, POD, SOD, and GSH activity was observed, likely due to excessive ROS generation surpassing the antioxidant defence system. Overall, the results showed that heavy metal exposure adversely affects fungal cellular physiology while simultaneously triggering robust antioxidant defence mechanisms. The negative impacts of oxidative stress are avoided by the induced enzymatic antioxidants, including SOD, POD, and CAT. Thus, the Basidiomycota fungi, *C. striatus* and *S. commune*, exhibited pronounced antioxidant defence responses under heavy metal exposure, reflecting their capacity to mitigate metal-induced oxidative stress and maintain cellular redox balance.

Author contributions

Writing-Original draft, P.M.; Data curation, P.M.; Validation, P.M.; Methodology, P.M.; Investigation, P.M.; Writing: Review and Editing, D.K.K.; Writing-Review and Editing, S.R.; Supervision, S.R.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors have no competing interests to declare that are relevant to the content of this article.

Data availability statement

Research data is available at Zenodo (10.5281/zenodo.18359581).

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Original Research

Seasonal Variation of Orthoptera Densities in Lesser Kestrel Foraging Habitats of the Thessaly Plain

Christos E. Christakis^{1*}, Athanassios I. Sfougaris¹

Abstract

This study investigates the seasonal variation of Orthoptera densities across the main crop types of the Thessaly Plain, central Greece, during the 2014–2015 breeding seasons of the Lesser Kestrel (*Falco naumanni*). A total of 1,820 line transects were conducted in 364 fields, yielding 5,300 Orthoptera individuals belonging mainly to the families Acrididae and Tettigoniidae. Mean densities were highest in fallow land and cereal fields, whereas cotton and maize exhibited consistently low or zero abundances, particularly during early breeding phases. Even though surveys recorded only numerical counts and not species identity or biomass, and thus the results cannot be directly converted to prey biomass, the study demonstrates the critical contribution of semi-natural habitats and crop heterogeneity to sustaining Orthoptera populations in intensively managed agroecosystems. The findings highlight the need for agri-environmental practices that maintain accessible prey throughout the Lesser Kestrel's breeding cycle.

Keywords

Biodiversity; Orthoptera; Line transects; Lesser Kestrel; Raptor

¹ Laboratory of Ecosystem and Biodiversity Management, Department of Agriculture, Crop Production and Rural Environment, University of Thessaly, Fytokou street, 38446, Volos, Greece

* Corresponding author:

E-mail address: cchristakis@uth.gr

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Sezonska spremenljivost gostote kobilic (Orthoptera) v habitatih prehranjevanja južne postovke na planoti Tesalije

Izvleček

Študija preučuje sezonska nihanja gostote kobilic (Orthoptera) na področjih glavnih vrst pridelkov na planoti Tesalije v osrednji Grčiji med sezonami razmnoževanja južne postovke (*Falco naumanni*) v letih 2014–2015. Na 364 poljih je bilo opravljenih skupno 1820 linijskih transektov, kjer smo zaznali 5300 osebkov kobilic, ki so v glavnem pripadali družinam Acrididae in Tettigoniidae. Povprečne gostote kobilic so bile najvišje na pustih poljih in žitnih poljih, medtem ko so bile na bombažnih in koruznih poljih gostote dosledno nizke ali nične, zlasti v zgodnjih fazah sezon razmnoževanja. V raziskavi so bili zabeleženi le številčni podatki in ne identitete vrst ali biomase, zato rezultatov ni mogoče neposredno pretvoriti v biomaso plena. Kljub temu študija kaže na ključni prispevek polnaravnih habitatov in heterogenosti pridelkov k ohranjanju populacij kobilic v intenzivno obdelanih agroekosistemih. Ugotovitve poudarjajo potrebo po kmetijsko-okoljskih praksah, ki ohranjajo dostopnost plena skozi celoten razmnoževalni cikel južne postovke.

Ključne besede

biodiverzitetata; Orthoptera; linijski transekti; južna postovka; ptica roparica

Introduction

Long-term changes of agricultural use in rural landscapes have created a mosaic of extensive open cultivation areas and smaller natural vegetation patches or corridors. These landscapes, formed primarily by agriculture, support the habitat of a significant number of species (Franco and Sutherland, 2004). At the same time, the species' well-being depends on the abundance, quality and distribution of resources needed, and thus lies on the farming practices utilised (Catry et al., 2012b). The intensification of agriculture that occurred in recent decades led to dramatic biodiversity loss in these agricultural areas, and when combined with the consequences of climate change, it greatly affected these agriculture-dependent species (Rodríguez and Wiegand, 2009). Modern agriculture poses a major threat to biodiversity, while further intensification is expected to have serious deteriorative impacts on species and habitats (Catry et al., 2012b).

These agroecosystems support many bird species currently under Unfavourable Conservation Status in Europe (European Environmental Agency 2021). Many farmland bird species of southern Europe—including *Otis tarda*, *Tetrax tetrax*, *Pterocles orientalis*, and *Falco naumanni*—have experienced severe declines, largely driven by habitat loss and degradation resulting from rapid agricultural change (Franco & Sutherland, 2004). Habitat het-

erogeneity and food availability are key drivers of farmland bird diversity in intensively farmed landscapes, showing positive relationships between landscape complexity and bird species richness (Holoskova et al., 2025). The way in which these species populations adapt to habitat quality and quantity decline is a major concern of conservation biology (Sánchez-Zapata et al., 2003). Therefore, understanding habitat-species relationships and the impact of changing landscape characteristics on the species is critical for understanding the causes behind their observed population declines (Catry et al., 2012a).

The Lesser Kestrel is a colonial migratory raptor. It is a species with familiarity to human activities, also considered a useful farmer ally in pest management (Kmetova et al., 2012). It usually nests in holes and crevices of old buildings, and its breeding habitats are the fairly flat agricultural landscapes of the Western Palearctic (Cramp et al., 1992; Parr et al., 1995; Negro, 1997; Perez et al., 2011). Breeding colonies are mostly located within cities and villages surrounded by large, agricultural landscapes (Bustamante, 1997; Franco et al., 2005; Perez et al., 2011; Gradev et al., 2023).

Its populations have declined rapidly in Western Europe, corresponding to a 46% loss every decade since 1950 (Mihoub et al., 2010). For this reason, it had been classified as "globally threatened" by the IUCN (Collar & Andrew, 1988). Since the 1990s, the European populations of the species have shown an increasing trend, and today the

species is classified as "Stable" (BirdLife International, 2021). The Greek population was considered "Vulnerable" (Legakis & Maragou, 2009) until 2013, when it was reclassified as "Least Concern" (LC) (NECCA, 2024). Its population decline is mainly attributed to the intensification of agricultural practices (Donazar et al., 1993; Parr et al., 1995; Bustamante, 1997; Tella et al., 1998; Tella & Forero, 2000; BirdLife International, 2004), as Lesser Kestrels depend on the conservation of the agricultural mosaic (Catry et al., 2012a).

The species forages in open areas with low vegetation (Cramp et al., 1992; Negro, 1997) where it preys mainly upon invertebrates (Parr et al., 1997), which constitute up to 85-94% of its diet and small mammals (Tella et al., 1996; Christakis & Sfougaris, 2025). In Thessaly, the majority of the Lesser Kestrel's diet during its pre-breeding period mainly consists of Coleoptera prey, while during breeding and post-breeding period the species feeds mainly on Orthoptera (Christakis et al., 2023). In terms of biomass, Orthoptera constitutes the most important invertebrate prey category.

Species of the Orthoptera order have traditionally been considered pests by farmers as they are mostly herbivorous, yet they constitute an important part of the diets of many species, such as farmland birds - including the Lesser Kestrel, thus controlling their populations (Belovsky & Slade, 1993). Important factors determining Orthoptera diversity and dispersal are vegetation structure and microclimate,

while temperature is the main physiological regulating factor (Willott, 1997; Marini et al., 2008). Orthoptera populations in the agroecosystem are affected by insecticides, intensive mowing, fire and grazing. Furthermore, vast areas with monocultures are undesirable as Orthoptera need grasslands or natural vegetation for egg laying and feeding during their nymphal stages, thus uncultivated field margins are favourable (Wilson et al., 1999; Badenhauer et al., 2012).

The aim of this study was to quantify Orthoptera densities across the main cultivation types of the Thessalian plain, which are the main feeding habitats for 65-70% of the total Greek Lesser Kestrel population, and assess their seasonal variation relevant to the species breeding period.

Materials and Methods

Study area

The study was conducted in the eastern Thessaly plain, central Greece, within an intensively cultivated landscape of ~150 km² surrounding the settlements of Stefanovikeio and Rizomylos—important Lesser Kestrel colonies. The area is dominated by arable crops such as cereals, legumes, cotton, maize, and fallow land (fig. 1).

Figure 1. The study area

Slika 1. Območje študije

Line transects as a method for estimating Orthoptera abundance

The Line transect method is a cheap and fast yet efficient way to count Orthoptera and is widely used to estimate the density, abundance and richness of the families Acrididae and Tettigoniidae. When carried out in open areas with low vegetation (<50cm plant height) and the density of Orthoptera is relatively low (<2 adults/m²), the method delivers accurate results (Gardiner et al., 2005).

To perform the line transects, the observer walks along a predetermined straight path within the selected area, counting individuals of the species under study. In the case of Orthoptera, all observed individuals, both stationary and moving, are counted (Isern-Vallverdu et al., 1993). The transects should be as straight as possible, parallel, and without overlapping segments. The distance between each transect should be consistent and predetermined throughout the experiment. Also, the speed of the transects should be consistent and not too slow, to reduce the probability of double-counting individuals (Greenwood & Robinson, 2006). Orthoptera movements depend on several factors, such as temperature, rain, wind, life cycle stage and height and density of vegetation, so an underestimation of Orthoptera population density is possible due to non-observation. All transects of each experiment should be performed, if possible, in similar, favourable environmental conditions (Isern-Vallverdu et al., 1993). To estimate the density of the

population under study, the following equation is used: $D = n/2La$, where D is the density of individuals per area unit (individuals/m²), n is the number of individuals counted by transects, L is the total length of each transect (m) and a is the half of the width of the strip area of active counting while performing each line transect (Krebs 2014).

Orthoptera counts

Line transects took place in three distinct periods of the seasonal presence of the Lesser Kestrel in Thessaly, in order to investigate Orthoptera abundance. The periods chosen, reflect important phases for the species breeding season: 1) Arrivals and pair formation (late March to early May), 2) Incubation of eggs and chick rearing /Breeding (mid-May to late June), 3) Nest abandonment / Pre-migratory phase (July and August).

Within the study area, 20 random sampling stations were selected using a Geographical Information System (GIS). A minimum distance of 500m between stations was set to cover the whole extent of the study area. For each station, the nearest available field of each crop type (cereal, legumes, cotton, maize, fallow land) was identified and tagged for repeated surveys. Line transects throughout the study were conducted in these fields (Fig. 2).

During two consecutive years for each study phase, five line transects, at a steady predefined walking pace, 50 meters long, 10 meters apart and 10 meters away from the

Figure 2. The 20 selected random points in the study area.

Slika 2. 20 naključno izbranih točk vzorčenja na območju študije.

field edges, were carried out in each selected field. The effective strip width was set to 1 m (0.5 m on each side of the observer), following Gardiner et al. (2005), who recommend narrow widths in low vegetation to maximise detection accuracy. The recordings concerned mostly families of Acrididae and Tettigoniidae. Vegetation height was roughly measured, and numerous testing transects were performed by the researchers to compensate for the varied detectability of Orthoptera among crops, particularly in tall vegetation. Similarly to O'Neill & Rolston (2007), who showed that grasshoppers are active and detectable only when environmental temperatures allow them to thermo-regulate effectively, and in agreement with standard scouting protocols recommending surveys at temperatures ≥ 21 °C (Rodbell et al. 2005), fieldwork was performed during hours of high Orthoptera mobility (10 am to 8 pm local time) and in any case at a temperature ≥ 20 °C (Rodriguez and Bustamante, 2008).

Because data lacked normality and homogeneity, differences among crop types and study phases were evaluated using Kruskal–Wallis tests followed by Mann–Whitney pairwise comparisons. Multiple comparison corrections were not applied due to the exploratory nature of the study. Tables, graphs and statistical analysis of the data were created and performed using Microsoft Excel 365, IBM Statistics v.25 and PAST (v.4.02).

Results

A total of 1,820 line transects were carried out during orthoptera population density estimations, in 364 fields (5 Line transects/field) during the two years of the study (2014 and 2015), and a total of 5,300 orthoptera individuals were counted (mean=2.91, S.D.=8.55 individuals per line transect). Across all crops and years, fallow land supported the highest mean Orthoptera densities (8.31 ± 0.73 individuals per transect), followed by cereals (4.07 ± 0.46). Cotton and maize consistently exhibited near-zero counts during early phases. Maize transects could not be conducted during the second and mostly the third study phases in either year because vegetation height and density prevented visibility, resulting in reduced sample sizes.

The results presented in tables 1, 2 and 3 show the recordings for every crop type and study phase of the study. Furthermore, Figure 3 presents the mean Orthoptera individuals/m² recorded for each crop type.

In the first year of the study (2014), the highest number of Orthoptera per line transect was recorded during the first study phase (5.37 ± 0.76). In contrast, in 2015, the peak number of individuals per line transect was observed during the third study phase (4.24 ± 0.60). A non-parametric Kruskal-Wallis test revealed statistically significant differences in mean Orthoptera counts across the study period ($H = 149.8$, $p < 0.05$). Furthermore, the mean number of Orthoptera individuals counted in fallow fields was the highest among all crop types (8.31 ± 0.73) during the study, followed by cereal crops (4.07 ± 0.46). Statistically significant differences were observed among the different crop types, as determined by the Kruskal-Wallis test ($H = 451.237$, $p < 0.05$).

During the first study phase in 2014, Orthoptera were not detected at all in cotton or maize fields. On the contrary, the mean number of individuals recorded per line transect was 11.35 ± 2.17 in cereal fields and 7.46 ± 1.35 in fallow land. The Kruskal-Wallis test revealed statistically significant differences among crop types during this phase ($H = 32.44$, $p < 0.05$). In the second phase of the study in 2014, Orthoptera were not detected in cotton fields, except for two instances where a single individual was observed. Conversely, a mean of 6.75 ± 1.14 Orthoptera per line transect was counted in fallow land. The Kruskal-Wallis test indicated statistically significant differences in Orthoptera counts across crop types ($H = 55.58$, $p < 0.05$). During the third study phase of 2014, the mean number of Orthoptera per line transect was 6.52 ± 1.04 in fallow land, followed by 2.69 ± 0.60 in cereal fields. The Kruskal-Wallis test confirmed statistically significant differences in Orthoptera abundance among crop types ($H = 61.15$, $p < 0.05$).

Similarly, in the first study phase of 2015, Orthoptera were not detected in cotton or maize fields, while the mean number of individuals per line transect was 1.36 ± 0.254 in cereal fields and 0.8 ± 0.19 in fallow land. Statistically significant differences were detected ($H = 13.99$, $p < 0.05$). During the second study phase of 2015, the mean number of individuals per line transect was 13.68 ± 3.01 in fallow land and 1.24 ± 0.36 in cereal fields. No Orthoptera were recorded in cotton fields in this study phase. The Kruskal-Wallis test revealed statistically significant differences in Orthoptera counts between crop types ($H = 92.03$, $p < 0.05$). In the third study phase of 2015, the mean number of Orthoptera per line transect was 6.52 ± 1.04 in fallow land and 2.69 ± 0.60 in cereal fields. The Kruskal-Wallis test confirmed statistically significant differences during this phase ($H = 125.8$, $p < 0.05$).

Table 1. The number of line transects carried out, and the mean Orthoptera individuals per line transect were recorded for all crop types of the study.

Tabela 1. Število izvedenih linijskih transektov in povprečno število posameznih osebkov redu Orthoptera na linijski transekt, zabeleženo za vse vrste pridelkov v študiji.

Crop type	2014			2015		
	No of line transects	Mean Orthoptera individuals per line transect	Standard Error	No of line transects	Mean Orthoptera individuals per line transect	Standard Error
Cereal	295	5,89	0,82	260	2,01	0,26
Cotton	235	0,43	0,07	260	0,14	0,03
Fallow	170	6,95	0,70	140	9,96	1,36
Legumes	200	1,19	0,13	185	0,44	0,09
Maize	40	0,10	0,05	35	0,11	0,07

Table 2. Number of line transects carried out and mean Orthoptera individuals per line transect recorded for all phases of the study (1. Arrivals and pair formation, 2. Incubation of eggs and chick rearing /Breeding, 3. Nest abandonment / Pre-migratory phase).

Tabela 2. Število izvedenih linijskih transektov in povprečno število posameznih osebkov redu Orthoptera na linijski transekt, zabeleženo za vse faze študije (1. Prihodi in tvorba parov, 2. Inkubacija jajc in vzreja mladičev/razmnoževanje, 3. Zapuščenje gnezd/predmigracijska faza).

Study Phase	2014			2015		
	No of line transects	Mean Orthoptera individuals per line transect	Standard Error	No of line transects	Mean Orthoptera individuals per line transect	Standard Error
1	330	3,47	0,30	310	0,60	0,09
2	310	5,37	0,76	295	2,32	0,50
3	300	2,48	0,32	275	4,24	0,60
Total	940	3,47	0,30	880	2,40	0,26

Table 3. Number of line transects and mean Orthoptera individuals per line transect recorded for all phases and crop types of the study.

Tabela 3. Število linijskih transektov in povprečno število posameznih osebkov redu Orthoptera na linijski transekt, zabeleženo za vse faze in vrste pridelkov v študiji.

Crop type/ Study Phase	2014			2015		
	No of line transects	Mean Orthoptera individuals per line transect	Standard Error	No of line transects	Mean Orthoptera individuals per line transect	Standard Error
Pair formation						
Cereal	100	11,35	2,17	90	1,36	0,25
Cotton	65	0,00	0,00	80	0,00	0,00
Fallow	65	7,46	1,35	55	0,80	0,19
Legumes	70	2,16	0,27	65	0,32	0,11
Maize	30	0,00	0,00	20	0,00	0,00
Incubation of eggs and chick rearing						
Cereal	100	3,47	0,64	90	1,24	0,36
Cotton	80	0,03	0,02	90	0,00	0,00
Fallow	55	6,75	1,14	40	13,68	3,01
Legumes	65	0,68	0,18	60	0,37	0,15
Maize	10	0,40	0,16	15	0,27	0,15
Nest abandonment / Pre-migratory						
Cereal	95	2,69	0,60	80	3,61	0,67
Cotton	90	1,09	0,16	90	0,40	0,07
Fallow	50	6,52	1,04	45	17,84	2,64
Legumes	65	0,65	0,14	60	0,65	0,21
Maize	0	0,00	0,00	0	0,00	0,00

Figure 3. Mean Orthoptera individuals/m² and sample sizes (number of line transects) for all crop types of the total duration of the study.

Slika 3. Povprečno število posameznih osebkov redju Orthoptera na m² in velikost vzorcev (število linijskih transektov) za vse vrste pridelkov v celotnem obdobju študije.

Discussion

This study investigated Orthoptera densities in the main crop fields of the study area (cereal, cotton, maize and legume crops and fallow land), which constitute the main foraging habitats of the Lesser Kestrel, during its breeding season in Thessaly. A recent study in the same area highlighted fallow land, legumes and cereals as the selected foraging habitats by the species (Christakis & Sfougaris, 2021).

Orthoptera counts via line transects showed that during the breeding season of the Lesser Kestrel, fallow/uncultivated fields and to a lesser extent cereals maintained the largest Orthoptera populations, while in legume fields (mainly alfalfa), fewer individuals were recorded, indicating greater Acrididae and Tettigoniidae families abundance in fallow/uncultivated and cereal fields. The finding that cereals in the study area were richer in Orthoptera than legumes is in agreement with Olfert et al. (1995), who suggested that the biotic potential of locusts is highest in wheat cultivation than legume crops (such as lentils and peas). Cereal crops seem to support a wide variety of large

insects, including Lepidoptera larvae and several Orthoptera (Stoate et al., 2000), while Orthoptera species, mainly of the Acrididae family, are considered cereal crop pests (Habtewold & Landin, 1992). Nevertheless, in all three phases during both years of the study, Orthoptera were recorded in these three crop types, while they were absent from cotton during the first two phases and appeared in small numbers in the third phase in both years. The minimal or no plant cover of cotton fields during the period before the breeding phase (second phase of the study) is a prohibitive factor for herbivorous insect species, such as Orthoptera, justifying their absence from these fields. The third study phase was characterised by the appearance of Orthoptera in all types of crops studied, since in all cases, plant cover was apparent.

In this study, Orthoptera densities can be characterised as relatively low, even in most of the fallow land, except for some fallow fields, where Orthoptera were counted at relatively high densities. However, the plant species heterogeneity of fallow/uncultivated fields reflects the Orthoptera densities recorded, which vary strongly among the different

fields of this type. These variations can be attributed to the different structure and composition of the vegetation in each fallow: fields with more grass and dense plant cover maintained increased numbers of Orthoptera, in contrast to fields dominated by perennials, broad-leaved or woody plants, where fewer Orthoptera were counted. Plant communities have a significant impact on the populations and density of Orthoptera, as they are related to the quantity and quality of their food (De Wysiecki et al., 2011). The higher densities of Orthoptera in semi-natural environments such as meadows, fallow lands and uncultivated margins, compared to other types of cultivated habitats, are confirmed by Rodriguez and Bustamante (2008), who also positively correlated Orthoptera density with the vegetative cover of the field and negatively with the increase in its size. The great heterogeneity that these systems exhibit, in terms of vegetation structure and density, probably makes some of them locally and temporally unsuitable foraging grounds for the Lesser Kestrel. Therefore, part of these habitats may be rich in unapproachable prey items, due to high and dense vegetation. Nevertheless, fallow/uncultivated fields continue to be important habitats around Kestrel colonies, functioning as shelters and reservoirs of potential prey for the species, from which surrounding areas/crops can be enriched.

The study results suggest that the most important type of farmland for the Lesser Kestrel in terms of Orthoptera (Acrididae and Tettigoniidae families) prey abundance is fallow land, confirming the opportunistic foraging strategy of the species, since fallow land seems to be the most preferred foraging habitat by the species in the area (Christakis & Sfougaris, 2021). Given that food availability is perhaps the most decisive controlling factor for any bird population, as prey scarcity at any stage of the breeding season can reduce the species' reproductive success, data on prey abundance and availability around colonies at each stage of the Kestrel breeding season is of imperative importance. In general, arthropod biomass and abundance seem to decrease with increasing agricultural intensification, likely limiting prey for dependent farmland birds (González del Portillo et al., 2021). Moreover, research on the diet of a declining species, such as the Lesser Kestrel, is of vital importance for its conservation and protection (Kopij, 2002). Based on such data, it is possible to manage the agroecosystem in favour of the species, avoiding a lack of food resources during its breeding season (Franco & Sutherland, 2004). Examples of Lesser Kestrel - friendly agroecosystem management and farming practices include the promotion

of crop rotation and fallowing, the promotion of low-input crops such as cereals, the conservation of traditional agricultural practices and the protection of natural vegetation patches and heterogeneous mosaics in rural landscapes.

The differences in Orthoptera counts between the two study years can be attributed to interannual temperature fluctuations, as higher spring temperatures began later during the second year of the study. Although this pattern is consistent with the findings of Geppert et al. (2021), who identified temperature as the primary driver of Orthoptera population density, this explanation remains hypothetical in the context of the present study.

It should be noted that, as vegetation structure was only roughly measured, and detectability varied among crop types, particularly in tall crops, some prey-rich fallow fields may have been undercounted due to dense vegetation. Furthermore, during the second and mainly the third study phases, plant height and density in maize cultivations were prohibitive for transecting within the fields during the sampling phases (in both years of the study), resulting in a small number of line transects conducted, only during the first phase and for both years of the study. Nevertheless, maize cultivations are not favourable Lesser Kestrel foraging habitats as accessibility to prey is the major foraging habitat selection factor (Donazar et al., 1993; Rodriguez et al., 2014). Moreover, because only numbers of individuals were recorded—not species identity or size—results cannot be used to estimate prey biomass, which is the most relevant metric for Lesser Kestrel foraging ecology. Orthoptera size can vary depending on their age class, and given that the Lesser Kestrel selects its prey, especially during the chick-rearing period, based on biomass, improving hunting efficiency (Christakis et al., 2023), to estimate the available prey at the biomass level, the sizes and species of Orthoptera should be further recorded. Future studies should incorporate biomass estimates to refine habitat management recommendations. However, this study constitutes a basis for investigating in depth the species' foraging ecology and agricultural biodiversity.

Conclusions

This study provides the first systematic assessment of Orthoptera densities across the main crop types of the Thessaly Plain during the Lesser Kestrel breeding season. Recordings were carried out using the line transect method

in the main crop fields of the study area, including cereals, cotton, legumes, maize cultivations and fallow/uncultivated land. The results showed that fallow land and cereal crops maintained the highest abundance of Orthoptera, while cotton and maize crops showed significantly lower or no densities. The heterogeneity of vegetation decisively affects the presence of Orthoptera, with the highest concentrations being found in fields with rich vegetation cover. Furthermore, the lack of herbivorous insects in cotton fields, mostly during early pair formation of the Lesser Kestrel, seems to make them unsuitable for foraging habitat for the Lesser Kestrel concerning Orthoptera prey, mostly Acrididae and Tettigoniidae families. On the contrary, uncultivated areas function as critical habitats, ensuring the availability of this prey. Although Orthoptera densities were thoroughly quantified, the absence of species- and size-level data limits biomass interpretation. Future research integrating species identity, size classes, and biomass measurements will further improve our understanding of prey availability for the Lesser Kestrel. Nevertheless, the findings of this study highlight the importance of maintaining semi-natural patches and crop diversification in maintaining populations of predators, such as the Lesser Kestrel.

Author Contributions

Conceptualization, C.C. and A.S.; methodology, C.C. and A.S.; writing—original draft preparation, C.C.; writing—review and editing, C.C. and A.S.; visualization, C.C.; supervision, A.S. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

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Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Ethical and Access Permissions

The study involved non-invasive visual surveys and required no handling of animals. Access to private fields was granted by landowners. No additional permits were required.

Data Availability

Research data of this study were deposited at Zenodo (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18337395>).

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Original Research

Modelling and Mapping of Soil Salinity Related to Soil Characteristics and Irrigation in a Semi-Arid Context

Yassine Al Masmoudi^{1*}, Sanae Bel-Lahbib¹, Khalid Ibno Namr¹, Adil Jouamaa², Meryem Moustakim³, Malika Laghrour⁴, Badr Rerhou⁵

Abstract

Soil salinity is a key challenge to maintaining agricultural operations in regions primarily defined by a semi-arid environment. Irrigation techniques are used to mitigate the impact of insufficient precipitation. However, excessive use of irrigation water creates significant problems of soil salinity. Utilising advanced methodologies, this investigation is dedicated to making models and maps of soil salinity. The approach involves the computation of the Normalised Differential Salinity Index (NDSI) while systematically examining potential correlations among the various physicochemical parameters under scrutiny: Soil Organic Matter (SOM), Electrical Conductivity (EC), pH, Texture, total limestone (CaCO₃) and Evapotranspiration (ET_o), in order to determine the parameters controlling salinity. The results showed a predominance of the sand fraction (57.5%), EC varied from 0.90 to 1.32 dS.m⁻¹, and exhibited varying salinity levels. Additionally, within the climate conditions of the region, climate analysis unveiled a noteworthy evapotranspiration rate (ET_o) ranging between 4 and 9 mm.day⁻¹. The model developed showed an adequate result in estimating soil salinity with an R²=0.90. Moreover, the map generated using NDSI showed that 36% of the total area displayed no evidence of salinity impact, 23% showed mild salinity, 24% indicated moderate soil salinity, and 17% showcased extreme levels of soil salinity. The proactive cartography of soil salinity in dry and semi-dry areas, coupled with an advanced modelling technique employing remote sensing data, stands as an integral methodology for informed decision-making processes.

Keywords

Irrigation, Soil salinity prediction, Modelling and Mapping, Electrical Conductivity, NDSI, Semi-arid conditions

1 Laboratory of Geosciences and Environmental Techniques, Department of Earth Sciences, Faculty of Sciences, Chouaib Doukkali University, BP.20, 24000 El Jadida, Morocco

2 Industrial and Seismic Engineering Research Team, Mohammed First University National School of Applied Sciences of Oujda, 60000, Morocco

3 Unit of Irrigation and Climate Change, Division of Water and Climate, National Centre for Energy, Sciences and Nuclear Techniques, Rabat, Morocco

4 International Centre for Agricultural Research in the Dry Areas, Avenue Hafiane Cherkaoui, Rabat 10112, Morocco

5 Department of Natural Resources and Environment, Hassan II Institute of Agronomy and Veterinary Medicine, PO Box 6202, Madinat Al Irfane 10101, Rabat, Morocco

* Corresponding author:

E-mail address: yassine.almasmoudi@gmail.com

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Modeliranje in kartiranje slanosti tal v povezavi z značilnostmi tal in namakanjem v polsušnem okolju

Izvleček

Slanost tal je ključni izziv za ohranjanje kmetijske dejavnosti v regijah, ki jih v glavnem zaznamuje polsušno okolje. Za ublažitev vpliva nezadostnih padavin se uporabljajo namakalne tehnike, a prekomerna uporaba namakalne vode povzroča znatne probleme s slanostjo tal. Naša raziskava je namenjena izdelavi modelov in zemljevidov slanosti tal s pomočjo naprednih tehnologij. Pristop vključuje izračun normaliziranega diferencialnega indeksa slanosti (NDSI) ob sistematičnem preučevanju potencialnih korelacij med različnimi fizikalno-kemijskimi parametri: organska snov v tleh (SOM), električna prevodnost (EC), pH, tekstura, skupni apnenec (CaCO_3) in evapotranspiracija (ET_0), da se določijo parametri, ki uravnavajo slanost. Rezultati so pokazali prevlado frakcije peska (57,5 %), EC je nihal od 0,90 do 1,32 $\text{dS}\cdot\text{m}^{-1}$ in pokazal različne ravni slanosti. Poleg tega je analiza podnebja v podnebnih razmerah regije razkrila opazno stopnjo evapotranspiracije (ET_0) med 4 in 9 $\text{mm}\cdot\text{dan}^{-1}$. Razvit model je pokazal ustrezen rezultat pri ocenjevanju slanosti tal z $R^2=0,90$. Poleg tega je zemljevid, ustvarjen z uporabo NDSI, pokazal, da 36 % celotne površine ni kazalo znakov vpliva slanosti, 23 % je kazalo blago slanost, 24 % je kazalo zmerno slanost tal, 17 % pa je kazalo ekstremne ravni slanosti tal. Proaktivna kartografija slanosti tal v suhih in polsuhih območjih, skupaj z napredno tehniko modeliranja, ki uporablja podatke daljinskega zaznavanja, predstavlja celovito metodologijo za informirane procese odločanja.

Ključne besede

Namakanje, napovedovanje slanosti tal, modeliranje in kartiranje, električna prevodnost, NDSI, polsušne razmere

Introduction

Environmental stresses, notably soil salinity, have significantly impacted the sustainability of soil and the cultivation of agricultural crops (Shrivastava and Kumar, 2015). The increase of salinity in soil and water was noted at the beginning of the 21st century (Yamaguchi and Blumwald, 2005). Regarded as one of the most destructive environmental stressors, soil salinity has precipitated critical reductions in agricultural areas (Yamaguchi and Blumwald, 2005; Shahbaz and Ashraf, 2013). Approximately 10 hectares of agricultural land are lost every minute globally, with salinisation contributing to 30% of this overall loss (FAO, 2020). In Mediterranean soils, the accumulation of salt is mostly a natural process that is made easier by the area's ecological characteristics (Aragüés and Tanji, 2003). This happens a lot in Africa, which has 63% of the world's salty soils (Kahime et al, 2018). Specifically, in semi-arid areas, intense use of water resources causes a lot of evaporation, which makes soils and groundwater salty (Khan et al, 2016; Jamaa et al, 2020). Drainage and evapotrans-

piration are important factors in fostering this process, especially in semi-arid and arid areas. Additionally, the ascent of water from shallow salty aquifers contributes to soil salinisation (FAO, 2020). Crops can absorb important nutrients from the soluble salts formed in irrigated soils. However, successive irrigations with saline water prompt the salts in the soil to expand. Consequently, a study on sugar beet crops by Rerhou et al (2023) in the Doukkala plain of Morocco demonstrates that, at high rates, this accumulation would affect root development and plant growth. This accelerates land degradation in semi-arid Mediterranean environments, especially in agricultural regions using poor-quality water for irrigation systems (Rahoui et al., 2000; El Achheb et al., 2001; Aragüés and Tanji, 2003). In essence, the expansion of salinized areas can be attributed to various factors, including soil-related elements (such as permeability, water depth, groundwater quality and topography), climatic conditions (like low rainfall and humidity), elevated surface evaporation, proximity to the sea, and management factors (involving irrigation, drainage, and cultural practices) (Ug and

Douaik, 2008; Ben-Dor et al., 2009). The mobility of water and air in the soil, the capacity of plants to hold water and root penetration are all affected by salt in the soil. In different studies (Curtis and Lauchli, 1986; Suárez and Medina, 2005; Al-Maskri et al., 2010; Amirul et al., 2014; Ors and Suarez, 2017), under salinity stress, a decrease in plant biomass, leaf area, and growth has been noted in a variety of vegetable crops. These salts can also impede the development of plants (Tang et al., 2015; Yadav et al., 2020). Salinity stress impacts various stages of plant growth, including seed germination, which is recognised as the stage that is most susceptible and crucial to abiotic stress (Patade et al., 2011). In addition to the environmental and agronomic impacts, soil salinity has socio-economic impacts (Sidike et al., 2014), mainly in arid and semi-arid zones (FAO, 2002; Farifteh et al., 2006; Allbed et al., 2014; El Harti et al., 2016). The FAO estimates that there are around 27.3 million hectares of areas affected by salt in the Mediterranean basin, including Morocco. Being an arid and semi-arid country, Morocco remains concerned about the ongoing degradation of soil due to salinisation, and the number of regions in Morocco affected by this phenomenon is increasing with a low rainfall rate (Oumara and El Youssefi, 2022). The second biggest threat to crop production is salinisation (Montanarella et al., 2016), after erosion, which is also considered a serious threat (Moustakim et al., 2019; 2022), and soil compaction (Al Masmoudi et al., 2019; 2021). This negatively affects the country, as the agriculture sector contributes significantly to Morocco's economic development (Oumara and El Youssefi, 2022). Conventionally, the evaluation of soil salinity traditionally involves collecting on-site soil samples, followed by laboratory analysis to measure electrical conductivity. However, these techniques are resource-intensive and economically challenging due to the need for extensive sampling to accurately capture the spatial variations within a given region (Nanni and Dematté, 2006; Brunner et al., 2007). Remote sensing has surpassed traditional methods in evaluating salinity, providing more comprehensive and efficient rapid evaluation techniques to manage and map the salinity in the soil in a professional manner (Allbed and Kumar, 2013). Several studies have adopted remote sensing and GIS-related approaches to effectively and efficiently study, map, and model the spatial and temporal variability of soil salinity across different environmental contexts (Rao and Kumar, 1991; Srivastava et al., 1997; Eldeiry and Garcia, 2008, 2010; Jiapaer et

al., 2011). Once it involves mapping soil salinity, remote sensing has many scientific advantages over traditional field-based methods (Ben-Dor et al., 2008; Bai et al., 2016; Bannari, 2019). Remote sensing data and methodologies are better and less costly tools for rapidly verifying and visualising soil salinity (Allbed and Kumar, 2013). Several remote sensing indices, like the salinity index (SI), the normalised difference salinity index (NDSI), the brightness index (BI), and the normalised difference vegetation index (NDVI), were used to see how well they worked at mapping soil salinity in dry areas (Douaoui et al., 2006; Jiapaer et al., 2011). Recent advances in remote sensing have significantly improved soil salinity assessment in arid and semi-arid regions. Satellite imagery allows the identification of salinity patterns over large areas and helps to better capture their spatial variability. When combined with field measurements, remote sensing provides an effective alternative to traditional field-based methods. In the Doukkala region of Morocco, agriculture stands as the primary activity for the local population. The arid climate, proximity to the sea, marine intrusion, and the declining quality of irrigation water collectively contribute to the deterioration of agricultural soils (Bel-Lahbib et al., 2022; El Bourhrami et al., 2022; Bounif et al., 2023). Despite the vital role of agriculture, there have been limited studies on the quantification, sources, and spatial variability of soil salinity in Morocco. Comprehensive data regarding soil salinity across various regions of the country are scarce. Since there hasn't been any modelling done on soil salinity in the research region, this study is crucial for managing and forecasting soil salinity; its goal is to assess the degree of salinity using both remote sensing data and on-site observation/evaluation.

This study aims to model and map soil salinity in the Doukkala region of Morocco and to support decision-making through a comprehensive strategy combining scientific and policy-oriented interventions. The originality of the work lies in its integrated approach, which combines field soil analyses, climatic data derived from the Penman–Monteith model, and satellite-based salinity indices to develop a robust framework for soil salinity mapping in semi-arid agricultural environments. Although the Doukkala region was selected as a case study, the proposed methodology is transferable to other arid and semi-arid regions facing similar salinisation issues. The main objectives are to analyse the spatial distribution of soil salinity and to support sustainable soil and irrigation management.

Materials and Methods

Study area description and climatic conditions

This study was done in the Doukkala plain, located in Central Morocco (Fig. 1). The Doukkala region forms a segment of the expansive western Moroccan Meseta. Geomorphologically, it comprises three distinct units: the coastal edge, the Sahel, and the plain (Eljebri et al., 2019). The Doukkala Abda area has semi-arid winters and hot, dry summers that are affected by the maritime environment. The temperature fluctuates between 5 and 39 °C. October through May is the rainy period, with an average yearly rainfall of roughly 317 mm (Ait Ayad et al., 2023). The National Meteorological Service of Morocco, which is in charge of data collection and quality control, gathered the climatic dataset from thirty local weather stations, and the computation of evapotranspiration employed the Penman-Monteith model. Figure 2 presents the ombrothermic diagram during the 2019 crop year.

Soil sampling and analysis

During 2019, 500 soil samples (0-30 cm) were collected from diverse locations across the study area. Soil samples were collected during the 2019 agricultural campaign, mainly between March and May, before the period of intensive irrigation and crop maturation. The analyses comprised a comprehensive assessment of soil properties, including soil organic matter (SOM) utilising the Walkley and Black method (1934), CaCO₃ measured with the Bernard calcimeter, soil texture determined through the Robinson method (Robinson et al, 1997), and the evaluation of water pH and electrical conductivity (EC). Figure 1 provides an overview of soil sampling and the distinct meteorological stations utilised for data analysis in this study.

The soil classifications in the research area, used to determine soil salinity, are based on the agronomic classification of soil salinity, as shown in Table 1. This comprehensive classification system allows for a nuanced evaluation of the diverse salt-affected zones present, providing a strong framework for studying the differences in salinity levels across different soil types within the study region.

Figure 1. Geographic location of the Doukkala irrigated perimeter, meteorological stations, and soil sampling.

Slika 1. Geografska lokacija namakalne površine Doukkala, meteoroloških postaj in vzorčenja tal.

Figure 2. Climatic conditions (Precipitation [mm] and Temperature [°C]) in the Doukkala region: 57-year average and the 2019 agricultural campaign.

Slika 2. Podnebne razmere (padavine [mm] in temperatura [°C]) v regiji Doukkala: 57-letno povprečje in kmetijska kampanja 2019.

Tabela 1. Agronomic classification of soil salinity based on EC (Brown et al, 1954).

Table 1. Agronomska klasifikacija slanosti tal na podlagi EC (Brown et al, 1954).

Classification	EC dS.m-1	Crop yield
Non-saline soils	0-2	Not affected
Slightly saline soils	2-4	Sensitive crops affected
Saline soils	4-8	Many crops affected
Strongly saline soils	8-16	Only tolerant crops are possible
Extremely saline soils	>16	Few very tolerant crops are possible

Estimation of reference evapotranspiration (ET_0) based on the FAO Penman–Monteith equation

The reference evapotranspiration (ET_0) was calculated using the FAO Penman-Monteith equation (Eq. 1), with daily meteorological information obtained from 30 meteorological stations established in the study area. Daily meteorological records required to compute ET_0 (Allen et al., 1998), including air temperature, solar radiation, humidity, wind speed and rainfall, were collected by these stations. Daily ET_0 values at each station were estimated by the FAO Penman-Monteith equation. These values were averaged

across the soil sample period to describe the mean evapotranspiration environment during the study period. Spatial distribution of the mean ET_0 in the study region.

$$ET_0 = \frac{0.408\Delta(Rn-G) + \gamma \frac{900}{(T+273)} U_2 (e_s - e_a)}{\Delta + \gamma(1+0.34U_2)} \quad (1)$$

Where Rn is the net radiation at the crop surface ($MJ\ m^{-2}\ day^{-1}$), G the soil heat flux density ($MJ\ m^{-2}\ day^{-1}$), T the air temperature at 2 m height ($^{\circ}C$), u_2 the wind speed at 2 m height ($m\ s^{-1}$), e_s the vapour pressure of the air at saturation (kPa), e_a the actual vapour pressure (kPa), D the slope of the vapour pressure curve ($kPa\ ^{\circ}C^{-1}$) and γ is the psychrometric constant ($kPa\ ^{\circ}C^{-1}$).

Mapping of soil salinity using GIS and remote sensing

Table 2 details some of the indices reported in the literature to map soil salinity in the current study. In addition, the Normalised Differential Salinity Index (NDSI) was obtained from one Landsat 8 OLI (Operational Land Imager) image acquired on July 21, 2019, and freely downloaded from the United States Geological Survey (USGS) website. The OLI sensor collected information in 11 bands. This paper used only the visible bands (2–4) and the NIR band (5) (Khan et al, 2005). A number of salinity indices, including SWIR-based indices (SI1–SI5), were calculated and assessed in addition to NDSI. However, the indices using SWIR bands did not enhance the prediction precision in comparison to NDSI; consequently, only NDSI was retained for full mapping and discussion. This period is characterised by high evapotranspiration rates and limited vegetation cover, which are favourable for detecting surface soil salinity. Vegetated and built-up areas were excluded using a supervised classification approach to focus the analysis on bare or sparsely vegetated soils. The salinity classes derived from NDSI represent spatially integrated surface conditions influenced by evaporation, irrigation practices, and salt accumulation at the soil surface, even though the majority of field EC measurements show non-saline to slightly saline conditions. The classification criteria were applied to the NDSI-derived EC estimates rather than directly to point-based field EC measurements, which explains the apparent distinction between laboratory EC statistics and mapped salinity classes. Figure 3 shows the methods used in outline form.

Tabela 2. Soil salinity indexes based on different band ratios of Landsat.

Table 2. Indeksi slanosti tal na podlagi različnih razmerij pasov Landsat.

Salinity Indexes	Spectral functions	References
Normalised Differential Salinity Index	$NDSI = \frac{R-NIR}{R+NIR}$	(Khan et al, 2005)
Brightness Index	$BI = \sqrt{R^2 + NIR^2}$	(Khan et al, 2005)
Salinity Index 1	$SI1 = \sqrt{B \times R}$	(Douaoui et al, 2006)
Salinity Index 2	$SI1 = \sqrt{G^2 + R^2 + NIR^2}$	(Douaoui et al, 2006)
Salinity Index 3	$SI3 = \frac{SWIR-1 \times SWIR-2 \times SWIR-2}{SWIR-1}$	(Bannari et al, 2008)
Salinity Index 4	$SI4 = \frac{R \times NIR}{G}$	(Abbas and Khan, 2007)
Salinity Index 5	$SI5 = \frac{G \times R}{B}$	(Bannari et al, 2008)

B, blue band; G, green band; R, red band; NIR, near-infrared band; SWIR 1 and SWIR 2, short-wave infrared 1 and 2 bands of the Landsat 8 image.

The Inverse Distance Weighting (IDW) interpolation method was used to generate continuous spatial distribution maps of soil and climatic parameters across the study area (Eq. 2). Point-based values of soil electrical conductivity (EC), soil pH, soil organic matter (SOM), clay content, calcium carbonate (CaCO₃), and reference evapotranspiration (ET₂) obtained from weather stations were interpolated using this technique. IDW makes the assumption that a sampled point's influence diminishes with increasing distance, giving nearest observations more weight for estimating values in unsampled locations (Bhunja et al., 2018). The regional variability of soil characteristics associated with soil salinity was examined using the interpolated maps that were produced. ArcGIS 10.8 was used for all spatial analysis.

$$z(x_0) = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n \frac{x_i}{h_{ij}^\beta}}{\sum_{i=1}^n \frac{1}{h_{ij}^\beta}} \quad (2)$$

Where Z (X₀) is the interpolation value; h_{ij} is the separation distance between the interpolation value and the measurement value; n is the number of sample points; x_i is the measurement value; β is the weight power (β=2).

The IDW interpolation method was chosen because it is simple to implement and suitable for large datasets with a relatively uniform distribution of sampling points. Soil parameters measured in the laboratory were interpolated to generate continuous spatial maps used in the analysis.

Statistical analysis of data

An investigation into the connections between soil salinity and other physicochemical parameters was carried out using advanced statistical methods by the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS). The minimum, maximum, and mean values for each soil parameter were among the important descriptive statistics that could be determined thanks to this analysis. Additionally, the distribution characteristics of the data were evaluated by calculating skewness and kurtosis.

Results

Data of Evapotranspiration

The spatial distribution of daily reference evapotranspiration (ET_0) measured at 30 weather stations is shown in Figure 4. ET_0 values, which are measured in millimetres per day (mm day^{-1}) and range roughly from 4 to 8.5 mm

day^{-1} , show moderate spatial variability throughout the monitoring network. Overall, the majority of stations exhibit ET_0 values between 5 and 7 mm day^{-1} , suggesting that the study area's climate is rather uniform. However, a number of stations exhibit higher evapotranspiration rates of more than 8 mm day^{-1} , which could be linked to regional differences in meteorological elements like air temperature, solar radiation, wind speed, and atmospheric vapour pressure deficit. On the other hand, lower ET_0 values (less than 5 mm day^{-1}) at a small number of stations indicate the impact of more temperate weather. In order to accurately characterise evapotranspiration dynamics at the regional scale, multi-station observations are crucial. The observed spatial patterns of ET_0 highlight the combined effects of regional climate and local microclimatic variability.

Statistical analysis

Table 3 summarises the analytical results of the soil samples utilised for salinity mapping. To determine if the soil physicochemical characteristics were normal, histograms were

created (Fig. 5). Sand concentration varied from 26.8% to 90.6%, silt content from 3% to 25.3%, and clay content from 5.70% to 54.8%. The mean value of soil organic matter (SOM) was 1.61%, with values ranging from 0.24% to 4.8%. Soil pH readings varied from 7.0 to 9.1, while electrical conductivity (EC) ranged from 0.08 to 1.3 dS m⁻¹ with an average of 0.37 dS m⁻¹. Figure 6 shows the correlations between the various soil physicochemical properties.

In order to better understand the relationships between soil physicochemical characteristics and to identify the major variables that might be influencing the distribution of soil salinity in the research region, correlation analysis was carried out. It is possible to evaluate how soil texture, chemical characteristics, and electrical conductivity interact to affect salt transportation and accumulation in semi-arid conditions. In circumstances with heavy irrigation and high evapotranspiration, this type of analysis is essential for distinguishing between the direct and indirect effects of soil properties on salinity processes. Additionally, identifying important connections facilitates the selection of relevant factors for soil salinity modelling and improves the interpretation of geographical patterns displayed in the salinity maps produced from remote sensing data. This method offers a scientific foundation for sustainable soil and irrigation management techniques and advances a more thorough understanding of soil behaviour.

Spatial distribution of soil parameters

The primary soil physicochemical characteristics, such as soil SOM, pH, CaCO₃, electrical conductivity (EC), and clay content, are shown spatially throughout the study region in Figure 7. The spatial representation of these parameters was obtained by interpolating individual soil sample values using the Inverse Distance Weighting (IDW) approach, as described in the Materials and Methods section. The regional visualisation of the spatial variability of soil parameters was made possible by the use of IDW to create continuous surfaces while preserving the influence of pertinent data. Due to the discrete nature of sampling points and local variability in soil properties, individual point symbols are still visible in some places (e.g., Fig. 7c). These symbols were intentionally preserved to highlight original measurement locations and emphasise data reliability.

The region's soil fertility patterns were revealed by the soil organic matter (SOM) content, which varied from 0.24% to 4.8%. The majority of soils have moderate (1.5–3%) to

low (0.7–1.5%) SOM levels, according to the DIAEA (2008) interpretation standards (Fig. 7a). The pH values of the soil (Fig. 7b) range from 7.0 to 9.1, indicating primarily neutral to basic conditions. The total calcium carbonate content ranges from 0% to 8.8%. According to national standards (Badraoui et al., 2000), the majority of soils are categorised as non-calcareous (<5% CaCO₃), with only a few regions exhibiting slightly calcareous soils (5–30% CaCO₃) (Fig. 7c). Electrical conductivity values frequently remain below 4 dS m⁻¹ (Fig. 7d), indicating primarily non-saline soils, according to Brown et al. (1954). Hazelton and Murphy (2016) classified the majority of the study area as having a moderate clay concentration (25–40%) in terms of soil texture (Fig. 7e). These soils, which are primarily Vertisols, are known for their high-water retention capacity due to clay swelling, which enhances their capacity to retain salts in the upper soil layers under conditions of high evapotranspiration and irrigation. All things considered, these geographic distributions provide a comprehensive understanding of the soil heterogeneity in the Doukkala region and provide a strong basis for examining soil salinity patterns and the factors that affect them.

Relationship between experimental electrical conductivity and Penman-Monteith model outputs

The output from the Penman-Monteith equation, used to estimate soil evapotranspiration, was compared with the variation in electrical conductivity to assess the degree of correlation between these two parameters. Notably, a substantial correlation ($R^2 = 0.826$) was identified, as depicted in Fig. 8, between the EC in dS m⁻¹ and the Penman model values reflecting daily evaporation trends (mm. day⁻¹) [$Y (ET_0) = \text{Intercept} + B1 * X (EC)^{1.4}$]; $R^2 = 83\%$.

This correlation can help analyse how soil evaporation/evapotranspiration, influenced by the climatic context in the study area, impacts the variation in soil salinity. Essentially, it gauges how well the model output adapts to effectively manage soil irrigation and practical application.

The modelling performance was assessed using regression analysis between measured soil electrical conductivity (EC) and EC values predicted from spectral indices. The coefficient of determination ($R^2 = 0.90$) represents the relationship between NDSI values and measured EC and was used for evaluating the performance of the different salinity indices. A final calibrated regression model

Figure 4. Evapotranspiration (ETO mm.day⁻¹) values according to the use of Penman-Monteith equations and meteorological stations in the sampling period.

Slika 4. Vrednosti evapotranspiracije (ETO mm.dan⁻¹) v skladu z uporabo Penman-Monteithovih enačb in meteoroloških postaj v obdobju vzorčenja.

Figure 5. Normality histogram of soil parameters (n = 500).

Slika 5. Histogram normalnosti parametrov tal (n = 500).

Tabela 3. Statistics descriptive of soil parameters (n=500).

Table 3. Statistični opis parametrov tal (n=500).

Parameters	Min	Max	Mean	S. D	C V	Skewness	Kurtosis
Sand %	26.8	90.6	54.41	15.24	28.02	0.545	-0.666
Silt %	3	25.3	13.83	5.04	36.41	-0.126	-0.783
Clay %	5.7	54.8	32.06	11.45	35.71	-0.364	-0.703
EC dS.m ⁻¹	0.08	1.3	0.37	0.20	52.52	1.729	3.527
pH	7	9.1	8.10	0.37	4.60	-0.607	0.216
SOM %	0.24	4.8	1.61	0.64	39.52	1.202	2.539
CaCO ₃ %	0	8.8	1.01	1.67	165.32	2.43	5.754
ETO mm.day ⁻¹	4	8.5	6.18	1.17	18.93	0.142	-0.378

Figure 6. Pearson correlation between physicochemical parameters of the Doukkala soils.

Slika 6. Pearsonova korelacija med fizikalno-kemijskimi parametri tal v Doukkali.

Figure 7. Mapping of (a) SOM, (b) pH, (c) CaCO₃, (d) EC, and (e) Clay.

Slika 7. Kartiranje (a) SOM, (b) pH, (c) CaCO₃, (d) EC in (e) glin.

Figure 8. Correlation between ET0 and soil evapotranspiration.

Slika 8. Korelacija med ET0 in evapotranspiracijo tal.

was then developed for spatial prediction of soil salinity across the study area, yielding an additional coefficient of determination ($R^2 = 0.90$). Error metrics, such as the Root Mean Square Error (RMSE), which measure the difference between measured and predicted EC values, were used to further evaluate model accuracy.

Spatial variation of soil salinity using modelling

NDSI was found to be the most dependable indicator for mapping soil salinity out of all the tested spectral indices. The remote sensing-based soil salinity modelling approach was calibrated and validated using electrical conductivity (EC) data collected from soil sampling. These ground-based measurements were used to assess how well the tested spectral indices represented soil salinity conditions throughout the study area. The Normalised Difference Salinity Index (NDSI), which is computed as $NDSI = (R - NIR) / (R + NIR)$, was used to create a map of soil salinity. R and NIR

stand for the red and near-infrared bands of the Landsat 8 OLI image, respectively (Khan et al., 2005).

In the visible and near-infrared portions of the electromagnetic spectrum, this index takes advantage of the spectral difference between salt-affected soils and non-saline surfaces. Using agronomic salinity classification thresholds proposed by Brown et al. (1954), the resulting NDSI-derived salinity map (Fig. 9) was explained, classifying soils into five salinity classes ranging from non-saline ($<2 \text{ dS m}^{-1}$) to extremely saline ($>16 \text{ dS m}^{-1}$). This classification indicates that about 36% of the study area is unaffected by salinity.

Built-up areas were identified and excluded using supervised image classification to avoid misinterpretation of non-soil surfaces. Higher salinity levels were mainly observed in the northern, western, south-western, and central parts of the study area. The NDSI model showed the strongest statistical relationship with measured soil electrical conductivity among the tested indices, confirming its robustness for predicting and mapping the spatial distribution of soil salinity using multispectral satellite data.

Figure 9. Map of soil salinity based on NDSI in the Doukkala region.
Slika 9. Zemljevid slanosti tal na podlagi NDSI v regiji Doukkala.

Discussions

The study area, renowned for its agricultural productivity, particularly owes its fertility to the prevalence of loam and clay-loam soils. These soil types possess properties and fertility that make them suitable for significant crop yields. Coastal agricultural regions, like the study area, often feature soils with minimal permeability and excellent capillary capacity, such as loam and clay-loam (Ray et al, 2014). Previous studies (Feng et al., (2015); Sun et al., (2018); Tully et al., (2019); Taylor and Krüger (2019); Arulmathi and Porkodi (2020); de la Reguera and Tully (2021) and Guo and Liu (2023)) indicate that in these soils, more than 50% of the salt that infiltrates remain concentrated in the upper 1-meter layer even a year after contact with saline water. This ability to retain salt is attributed to the robust capillary action inherent in silt-loam and clay-loam soils. Indeed, among the critical soil parameters influencing salinity, clay content assumes significance due to its water absorption and swelling capacities. The water-retention

characteristics of clay offer a protective mechanism against the deleterious effects on crops and soil. However, challenges may emerge in the face of increased evaporation, particularly driven by elevated temperatures, leading to the evaporation of freshwater and subsequent salt accumulation in the soil. In contrast, sandy-loam soils, characterised by weaker capillarity due to higher permeability, exhibit less pronounced salt trapping. This suggests that silt-loam and clay-loam soils face challenges in recovering from saltwater irrigation. Consequently, the study area is deemed vulnerable to salinity, potentially impacting crop production. Given that 30% of the soils in the area are loam and clay-loam, combined with the prevailing climate conditions characterised by elevated temperatures leading to increased evaporation/evapotranspiration, the susceptibility to salinity poses a notable concern for crop cultivation.

In this research, soil salinity maps developed using the chosen computational model for NDSI revealed extensive areas with notable index values. The spatial distribution of this salinity classification varied across the studied

regions. Specifically, the study area exhibited heightened soil salinity, particularly in its northern, western, south-western, and central regions, depicted in blue on the map (Fig. 9) due to irrigation with saline water. The use of such saltwater for crop irrigation can result in salt accumulation in the topsoil. Conversely, arid regions (depicted in shades ranging from yellow to light blue) occur when saline water reaches the ground level, and high evaporation rates leave salt deposits on the soil surface (Al-Mahawili et al, 1983). Evaporation-driven water uptake is the reason for the elevated salt content in the superficial soil layer and upward capillary flow, following the stages of soil evaporation (Al Masmoudi et al, 2023). Therefore, these results imply that the utilisation of saltwater for irrigation, coupled with salt buildup at the soil surface and a high rate of evaporation, likely contributes significantly to the spatial disparities in soil salinity across these areas. Indeed, the pattern of occurrence of saline soils within the Doukkala area (Fig. 9) shows a moderate salinity content in parts of the study area, which is eventually related to the water irrigation quality (and/or climatic conditions, such as soil evaporation intensified by higher temperatures). To reduce the effect of soil salinity on crop yield production, several economic and scientific technologies should be adopted for sustainable agricultural productivity and environmental sustainability.

Variations in soil type and structure, the topography zone, inadequate drainage, and the quality of irrigation water could all contribute to differences in salinity levels across the study area. These factors are recognised as influencing the distribution of soil salinity across landscapes (Stavi et al, 2021). While irrigation water quality can pose challenges, these can be mitigated through effective management of irrigation. Additionally, it's worth noting that instruments for measuring and monitoring soil moisture content were not employed for irrigation purposes in any of the study area plots. Furthermore, many farmers may face financial constraints that prevent them from purchasing such instruments, and there may be a lack of extension services to promote their utilisation. As a result, improper irrigation practices, including excessive water applications and poor timing, can lead to varying degrees of salt accumulation in the soil profile, which is ultimately detrimental to crop production. This study demonstrates the effectiveness of utilising regression analysis alongside high-resolution remote sensing imagery to predict and map spatial variations in soil salinity across a region. The

new perspectives generated in this study may be helpful for farmers, scientists and engineers in the management of soil salinity problems in ecosystems. Furthermore, the low cost complexity of the proposed approach, and the satisfactory accuracy achieved by the presented approach make it an alternative to the traditional methods of soil salinity prediction and mapping. Although this study seeks to investigate the mapping and modelling of soil salinity's geographical fluctuation during a certain time period, future work should also address temporal variability in soil salinity in semi-arid and arid areas to recognise the evolving patterns of soil salinity over time. Previous studies conducted in the Doukkala region mainly focused on soil quality, erosion processes, or groundwater salinity. The spatial salinity patterns identified in this study are consistent with areas previously reported as vulnerable, which supports the validity of the proposed mapping approach and highlights its added value.

Soil salinity, being a phenomenon characterised by both spatial and temporal variations, necessitates further investigation into its temporal dynamics. Early identification of the salinity, as well as prediction and mapping of its severity and extent, allows decision-makers to take necessary decisions to protect date palm crops, agricultural lands, and natural ecosystems, especially in areas with severely saline soils. Furthermore, while this work yields promising results for predicting and mapping soil salinity using NDSI computing, there is room for future expansion to include hyperspectral imaging. Investigating how hyperspectral imagery can enhance the accuracy of spatial variation modelling and mapping in similar environments is a worthwhile endeavour. Numerous studies have highlighted the promising potential of hyperspectral imagery in assessing and mapping soil salinity (Allbed and Kumar, 2013; Hamzeh et al., 2016; Sytar et al., 2017). For example, with the aid of Partial Least Squares Regression (PLSR) and Hyperion hyperspectral images, Gorji et al (2015) were able to predict and map soil salinity at a regional scale (>400,000 ha). Similarly, Goldshleger et al. (2013) and Fan et al. (2015) used the PLSR model to analyse the salt stress relationship of tomato plants, and soil spectral reflectance measured with a hyperspectral radiometer showed promise. They determined that hyperspectral radiometry is useful for measuring salinity in vegetative characterisation and estimating salt content. As a result, more research is needed to assess the capabilities of remote sensing data in mapping and predicting soil salinity under these conditions.

Conclusion

Agriculture stands as one of the primary activities for the population of the Doukkala region in Morocco. However, the progress of this activity is constrained by climatic conditions, the utilisation of saltwater in irrigation systems, and the physical degradation of agricultural soils. The climatic components impede crop development in the absence of suitable irrigation, leading to the accumulation of salts in the soil. This research revealed that electrical conductivity (EC) levels indicate varying degrees of salinity. Additionally, climate analysis within the region indicated a significant evapotranspiration rate (ET₀) ranging from 4 to 9 mm.day⁻¹. The model employed in the study demonstrated satisfactory results of the remote sensing approach in predicting soil salinity, achieving an R² value of 0.90. Furthermore, the generated map utilising NDSI illustrated that 36% of the total area showed no signs of salinity impact, 23% exhibited mild salinity, 24% indicated moderate soil salinity, and 17% displayed extreme levels of soil salinity. This strategic mapping of soil salinity in semi-arid and arid environments, combined with an advanced modelling approach utilising remote sensing data, serves as a crucial methodology for facilitating informed decision-making processes. Understanding the spatial variability of soil salinity is essential for sustainable agriculture in semi-arid regions. The approach proposed in this study provides a practical and cost-effective tool to support soil and irrigation management. Future research should focus on temporal monitoring and the integration of advanced modelling techniques to further improve soil salinity assessment.

Following the spatiotemporal dynamics of soil salinity is essential to comprehend the effects of precipitation, irrigation systems, and agricultural operations on its development. Consequently, agricultural researchers, utilising remote sensing and satellite imaging, can access essential intervention strategies to alleviate the enduring effects of soil salinisation on agricultural output. Since salt-tolerant plants can be useful for recovering saline soils in the region, it is advised that future research be done on growing halophilic plants in extremely saline areas.

Authorship contribution statement

Conceptualisation, Y.A., S.B., and A.J.; methodology, Y.A., S.B., and A.J.; validation, Y.A., S.B., and K.I.N.; formal analysis, Y.A.; investigation, Y.A. and S.B.; data curation, Y.A.; writing original draft preparation, Y.A. and S.B.; writing, review and editing, Y.A., S.B., K.I.N., A.J., M.M., M.L., and B. Rerhou; visualisation, K.I.N.; supervision, K.I.N. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

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Data Availability

The data that support the findings of this study are deposited at Zenodo (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18717167>).

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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Original Research

Effects of graded inclusion of *Jatropha tanjorensis* leaf meal on growth and feed utilisation in *Clarias gariepinus*

Emmanuel A. Essien^{1*}, Aniefiokmkpong O. Okon¹, Enenwan P. Udoinyang¹, Prince-charles Omin Itu², Bernard Obagha Bassey³, Ndifreke Daniel Ekpo¹, Bassey Okon Effanga⁴

Abstract

The Nigerian aquaculture industry, despite its 50-year existence and vast cultivable water resources, still struggles to meet domestic fish demand, largely due to high feed costs. This study investigated the growth performance and physicochemical responses of *Clarias gariepinus* fingerlings fed graded levels (0%, 5%, 10%, and 20%) of *Jatropha tanjorensis* leaf meal (JTLM). Standard methodologies were used to assess the physicochemical qualities and growth parameters such as weight, length, specific and daily growth rates, and feed conversion ratio and condition factor. The results revealed that the proximate composition of JTLM had moderate nutritional values: 25.5% crude protein, 5.0% fibre, 20.3% fat, 9.5% ash, 0.9% moisture, and 38.8% nitrogen-free extract. Water quality parameters remained within optimal ranges, with slight reductions in dissolved oxygen and increases in BOD, TSS, and conductivity at higher inclusion levels (20%). Growth performance was significantly improved in the 5% and 10% JTLM groups, which exhibited superior weight gain, daily growth rate, specific growth rate (SGR), and feed conversion ratio (FCR) compared to the control and 20% treatments. The best FCR (3.52–4.18) was also observed at these levels. Although all groups maintained healthy condition factors (>1.0), the 20% JTLM group had the lowest survival rate. Statistical analysis confirmed significant differences ($p \leq 0.05$) across treatments. The findings indicate that JTLM is a viable, cost-effective feed ingredient for African catfish when used at appropriate inclusion levels. It is recommended to limit JTLM inclusion to 5–15%, combine it with high-protein ingredients, and further explore its effects on other cultured fish species.

Keywords

physicochemical parameters, growth performance, *Clarias gariepinus*, *Jatropha tanjorensis*, plant-based protein

1 Department of Animal and Environmental Biology, Faculty of Biological Sciences, University of Uyo, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria

2 Department of Environmental Standard, University of Calabar, Calabar, Cross River State, Nigeria

3 Department of Geography and Environmental Science, University of Calabar, Calabar, Cross River State, Nigeria

4 Department of Biochemistry, University of Calabar, Cross River State, Nigeria

* Corresponding author:

E-mail address: emeritusessien49@gmail.com

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Vpliv postopnega dodajanja moke iz listov *Jatropha tanjorensis* na rast in izkoristek krme pri *Clarias gariepinus*

Izvleček

Nigerijska ribogojna industrija kljub 50-letni tradiciji in obsežnim vodnim virom, primernim za gojenje rib, še vedno težko zadovoljuje domače povpraševanje po ribah, predvsem zaradi visokih stroškov krme. V tej študiji smo preučevali rastne zmogljivosti in fizikalno-kemijske odzive mladice ribe *Clarias gariepinus*, ki so bile krmiljene z različnimi deleži (0 %, 5 %, 10 % in 20 %) listne moke *Jatropha tanjorensis* (JTLM). Za oceno fizikalno-kemijskih lastnosti in parametrov rasti, kot so teža, dolžina, specifične in dnevne stopnje rasti ter razmerje pretvorbe krme in kondicijski faktor, so bile uporabljene standardne metodologije. Rezultati so pokazali, da je imela sestava JTLM zmerne hranilne vrednosti: 25,5 % surovih beljakovin, 5,0 % vlaknin, 20,3 % maščob, 9,5 % pepela, 0,9 % vlage in 38,8 % ekstrakta brez dušika. Parametri kakovosti vode so ostali v optimalnih mejah, z rahlim zmanjšanjem raztopljenega kisika in povečanjem BOD, TSS in prevodnosti pri višjih vključitvenih ravneh (20 %). Rastna zmogljivost se je znatno izboljšala v skupinah z 5 % in 10 % JTLM, ki so pokazale boljše telesno maso, dnevno stopnjo rasti, specifično stopnjo rasti (SGR) in razmerje pretvorbe krme (FCR) v primerjavi s kontrolno skupino in obdelavami z 20 %. Najboljši FCR (3,52–4,18) je bil prav tako opazen pri teh vsebnostih. Čeprav so vse skupine ohranile zdrave kondicijske faktorje (>1,0), je imela skupina z 20 % JTLM najnižjo stopnjo preživetja. Statistična analiza je potrdila statistično značilne razlike ($p \leq 0,05$) med poskusi. Rezultati kažejo, da je JTLM uporabna in stroškovno učinkovita sestavina krme za afriškega soma, če se uporablja v ustreznih vsebnostih. Priporoča se, da se vsebnost JTLM omeji na 5–15 %, da se ga kombinira s sestavinami z visoko vsebnostjo beljakovin in da se nadalje raziskujejo njegovi učinki na druge gojene ribje vrste.

Ključne besede

fizikalno-kemijski parametri, rastni kazalniki, *Clarias gariepinus*, *Jatropha tanjorensis*, rastlinske beljakovine

Introduction

The Nigerian aquaculture industry is over five decades old (Olagunju *et al.*, 2007); however, domestic fish production has remained inadequate to meet the protein needs of the rapidly growing population. Despite this challenge, Nigeria possesses enormous aquaculture potential. Ita *et al.* (1985) reported that the country has over 13 million hectares of cultivable water bodies suitable for aquaculture development. In addition, several cultivable fish species, both exotic and indigenous, have been documented (Ngueku, 2015), indicating strong prospects for expanding fish production.

Fish is one of the most nutritious and highly demanded sources of animal protein worldwide. The increasing human population has further intensified the demand for fish and fishery products. However, the sustainability of aquaculture is largely dependent on the availability of quality and affordable feeds. CMFRI and SAARC (2013) identified fish feed as one of the major constraints to aquaculture development,

contributing significantly to the decline of the agricultural sector. The success of fish production depends heavily on feed quality and cost (Udo and Umanah, 2017).

The major ingredients used in aquafeeds include fish-meal, soybean meal, and maize. Unfortunately, these conventional feedstuffs are expensive and increasingly scarce due to competition for human food, livestock feed, and industrial uses (Rahman *et al.*, 2023). In Nigeria, the cost of fish feed has risen drastically over the years. Daily Trust (2016) reported an 80–100% increase in feed prices within eight years, forcing many fish farmers, particularly in Lagos State, out of business. Similarly, Okon *et al.* (2020) reported that a bag of Blue Crown feed sold for about ₦10,500, but the same brand now costs over ₦24,400, representing about a 138% increase (Thompson *et al.*, 2024). These rising costs reduce farmers' profit margins and threaten the sustainability of aquaculture.

To address this challenge, alternative, cost-effective, and sustainable feed resources must be explored. Plant-based proteins are considered the most suitable substi-

tutes for fishmeal in freshwater diet formulation (Naylor *et al.*, 2009). The inclusion of plant protein ingredients in fish diets has increased due to their relatively low cost and balanced amino acid profiles (Mahboob, 2014). Consequently, attention has shifted toward underutilised plant resources as potential ingredients for aquafeeds.

One such promising plant resource is the genus *Jatropha*. In Nigeria, *Jatropha tanjorensis* is commonly known as “Hospital Too Far,” “Catholic vegetable,” “Iyana-Ipaja,” or “Lapalapa” (Iwalewa *et al.*, 2005). *Jatropha* plantations can yield up to four tons of seeds per hectare annually, producing about one ton of protein-rich kernel meal (Makkar and Becker, 1997). This indicates the potential of *Jatropha* seed meal as a sustainable protein source for aquaculture feeds.

However, the utilisation of *Jatropha* seed meal has been limited by the presence of toxic and anti-nutritional factors. Its toxicity is mainly attributed to phorbol esters, along with other antinutrients such as trypsin inhibitors, lectins, phytates, saponins, tannins, and alkaloids (Makkar and Becker, 2009; Pelletier *et al.*, 2015). These compounds may restrict their use in animal feeding. Nevertheless, studies have shown that appropriate processing methods, such as heat treatment and solvent extraction, can significantly reduce phorbol esters and eliminate most antinutrients, thereby improving the safety and nutritional quality of *Jatropha* meals (Goel *et al.*, 2007).

Although research on *Jatropha* species has focused mainly on their distribution, cultivation, and nursery development, studies on *Jatropha tanjorensis* as a feed ingredient remain limited (Sudheer *et al.*, 2009). Available evidence, however, supports its potential as a protein source in aquaculture. Previous studies have demonstrated the effectiveness of *Jatropha* seed meal in the diets of common carp (*Cyprinus carpio*) (Kumar *et al.*, 2008), rainbow trout (*Oncorhynchus mykiss*) (Kumar *et al.*, 2009), Nile tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*) (Abozaid *et al.*, 2016), and African catfish (*Clarias gariepinus*) (Adeyemi *et al.*, 2016; Musa *et al.*, 2018).

In Nigeria, the most commonly cultured fish species include catfish and tilapia. Among them, the African catfish (*Clarias gariepinus*) is the most popular due to its fast growth, hardiness, tolerance to low dissolved oxygen, and ability to survive under high stocking densities (Adikwu, 2003). It is highly valued for its high protein content, palatability, and adaptability to various Nigerian culinary styles, making it an important contributor to household nutrition and food security (Ezenwa, 2006).

To meet FAO’s recommended fish consumption rate of 12.5 kg per capita annually, Nigeria requires about 1.5 million metric tonnes of fish per year (FAO, 2017). However, current production remains insufficient, and demand continues to rise. This underscores the need to explore alternative feed ingredients that are affordable, sustainable, and capable of supporting both fish growth and nutritional quality.

Therefore, this study is designed to provide nutritionists, aquafeed manufacturers, and fish farmers with a practical, economical, and sustainable alternative for feed formulation. Specifically, the study evaluates the effect of *Clarias gariepinus* growth fed graded levels of *Jatropha tanjorensis* meal. The findings also contributed to the baseline information for improving feed utilisation, reducing production costs, and enhancing profitability and sustainability within the Nigerian aquaculture industry.

Materials and Methodology

Experimental Location

The experiment was carried out in the Department of Animal and Environmental Biology, Faculty of Biological Sciences, University of Uyo. The feeding trial was conducted under semi-controlled outdoor conditions. The experiment was carried out in eight (8) black, round rubber plastic tanks with a working volume of 50 L each, placed on an open field to allow exposure to natural sunlight and ambient environmental conditions. The tanks were made of high-density plastic material and operated as static water systems with periodic water renewal. This study was conducted between April and June 2025, which corresponds to the early rainy season in southern Nigeria. During this period, ambient temperature ranged between approximately 26–32 °C, with relative humidity of 70–85% and a natural photoperiod of about 12 h light and 12 h dark. Water temperature followed ambient conditions and was monitored regularly to ensure suitability for *Clarias gariepinus* culture.

The tanks were cleaned regularly, and uneaten feed and faecal materials were siphoned to maintain water quality. Water was partially renewed every two weeks to prevent the accumulation of metabolic wastes. All husbandry practices were carried out uniformly across treatments to minimise environmental variation and ensure reliable assessment of dietary effects.

Collection and Identification

Fresh branches of *Jatropha tanjorensis* leaf were obtained from a farm in Uyo L.G.A, Akwa Ibom State. The leaves and stems of the plant were plucked and taken to the Herbarium of the Department of Botany and Ecological Studies, University of Uyo, for proper identification.

Collection, Identification and Processing of *Jatropha tanjorensis* Leaf Meal (JTLM)

Fresh, mature leaves of *Jatropha tanjorensis* were collected from healthy, non-contaminated stands within cultivated home gardens in Uyo, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. At harvest, the plants were free from visible disease symptoms and insect damage. Both leaves and small portions of the stem were initially collected for proper taxonomic identification; however, only the leaves were used for feed preparation, while the stems served solely for authentication purposes.

The plant material was authenticated by the Laboratory Technologist, Department of Botany, University of Uyo, Nigeria, and a voucher specimen was deposited for reference. After harvest, the leaves were rinsed with clean water to remove surface debris and soaked in water for 30 h to reduce anti-nutritional factors, unlike the method of Adejoro *et al.* (2013), who soaked for 24 h. The soaked leaves were drained and oven-dried at 55 °C for 72 h (three days) until a constant weight and crispy texture were achieved, after which they were milled into powder using a mechanical milling machine and sieved through a 2-mm mesh to remove coarse fibre, yielding fine *Jatropha tanjorensis* leaf meal (JTLM).

Preparation of Experimental Diets Containing JTLM

Other feed ingredients, including soybean seeds, maize meal, fish meal, cassava flour, and vitamin–mineral premix, were purchased from a reputable commercial feed store in Uyo, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. Soybean seeds were toasted according to the methods described by Tiamiyu *et al.* (2015) and Okomoda *et al.* (2020) to reduce anti-nutritional factors, while the remaining ingredients were used as purchased.

All ingredients were weighed according to the formulated diet compositions and thoroughly mixed to obtain a homogeneous blend. The appropriate proportions of JTLM

were incorporated into the basal diet to replace part of the conventional protein source as required for each treatment. The mixed diets were pelleted, air-dried, and stored in airtight containers until use for the feeding trial.

Diet formulation and preparation

The powdered meal produced was mixed directly with the basal diet. It was added to the diets at concentrations of 0%, 5%, 10% and 20% of feed labelled Control, JTLM 1, JTLM 2 and JTLM 3, respectively (Table 1). Compounded feeds were pelletized (2mm) using the pelletizing machine, sundried, allowed to cool in the open air, packed and stored in an opaque nylon bag.

Warm water was added to the premixed ingredients and homogenised until a dough-like paste was formed. The dough was then passed through a pelleting machine. The moist pellets were sundried to a constant weight and were kept in air-tight containers prior to the experiment. The percentage composition of the experimental diets is given in Table 1.

Experimental design and feeding

A total of 160 apparently healthy *Clarias gariepinus* fingerlings with an average initial weight of 4.54 ± 0.47 g were purchased from Fish Feed Solution Cooperative, No. 5 Osuk Ntan, off Ikot Akpanobong, Ibiono Ibom, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. The fish were transported to the experimental facility and acclimatised for 7 days in holding tanks, during which they were fed a control diet and observed for health and activity.

After acclimatisation, fish were randomly assigned to four dietary treatments in duplicate, giving a total of 8 experimental tanks. Each tarpaulin tank (100 × 50 cm) was stocked with 20 fingerlings, resulting in a total of 160 fish and a uniform stocking density across treatments. Randomisation was done by assigning fish sequentially to tanks after gentle mixing to avoid size bias.

Each tank was filled with 15,000 mL (15 L) of unchlorinated water. Manual aeration was provided by gently stirring the water in each tank at regular intervals (morning, afternoon, and evening) to enhance oxygen diffusion and prevent stratification. In addition, uneaten feed and faeces were siphoned daily to maintain water quality. Water was partially exchanged (75% twice weekly) throughout the experimental period.

Table 1. Composition of the experimental diets (g kg⁻¹ feed).

Tabela 1. Sestava poskusnih krmnih mešaníc (g/kg krme).

Ingredients	Experimental diets			
	Control	JTLM 1 (5%)	JTLM 2 (10%)	JTLM 3 (20%)
JTM	0	5	10	20
Fish meal	25.00	25.00	25.00	25.00
Maize	32.60	27.60	22.60	12.60
Soybeans	20.00	20.00	20.00	20.00
Wheat meal	15.00	15.00	15.00	15.00
Salt	0.20	0.20	0.20	0.20
Vitamin premix	0.20	0.20	0.20	0.20
Fish oil	7.00	7.00	7.00	7.00
Total	100	100	100	100

Note: C (0%) – 0 % inclusion of JTLM; JTLM 1 - 5%; JTLM 2 - 10%; JTLM 3 - 20%

The fish were fed experimental diets containing graded levels of *Jatropha tanjorensis* leaf meal (JTLM) for 10 weeks (70 days). Feeding was done twice daily at 07:00 h and 17:00 h at a rate of 5% of body weight (Kassaye, 2012). On sampling days, fish were fed three hours after weighing to reduce handling stress.

Fish in each tank were batch-weighed weekly, and the feeding ration was adjusted accordingly to reflect 5% of the updated biomass. Mortalities, if any, were recorded immediately and removed from the tanks, and the number of fish per tank was noted for accurate calculation of growth and feed utilisation indices.

Throughout the experiment, tanks were kept under similar environmental conditions to minimise variation among treatments, ensuring that any observed differences could be attributed to the dietary treatments.

The study was conducted in accordance with all applicable international, national, and/or institutional guidelines for the care and use of animals. The research did not involve the killing of any of the fish samples. Additionally, the number of fish used (160 samples) did not exceed the threshold requiring ethical approval (200 samples and above) as per the local regulations. The study was performed on a private fish farm licensed by the State Government, which lies outside the jurisdiction of the Ethical Approval Research Committee in Nigeria. For these reasons, no formal ethical approval number was issued for this study.

Analysis of physicochemical parameters

The physicochemical parameters of the culture water were monitored weekly throughout the 10-week experimental period. Parameters measured included pH, temperature, dissolved oxygen (DO), electrical conductivity, total suspended solids (TSS), and biological oxygen demand (BOD₅). Water samples were collected from each experimental tank in the morning between 08:00 and 09:00 h, prior to feeding, to minimise diurnal variation and ensure consistency in sampling conditions. All instruments were calibrated before each sampling event in accordance with the manufacturers' instructions to ensure accuracy and reliability of measurements. The pH meter was calibrated using standard buffer solutions of pH 4.0, 7.0, and 10.0. The dissolved oxygen meter was calibrated using the air-saturation method, while the conductivity meter was calibrated using a standard potassium chloride (KCl) solution. Thermometers were verified against a reference thermometer before use.

Water pH was measured using a digital mini pH meter (Model 55, Fisher Scientific, Denver, CO, USA). Water temperature was determined using a mercury-in-glass thermometer (0–100 °C range), which was immersed in the water sample for approximately 5 minutes to attain thermal equilibrium before recording.

Dissolved oxygen was measured in situ using a YSI Model 58 dissolved oxygen meter (Yellow Springs

Instrument Co., OH, USA). Electrical conductivity was determined using an electrolytic conductivity meter and expressed in $\mu\text{S cm}^{-1}$.

Total suspended solids (TSS) were determined using the gravimetric method. A known volume (100 mL) of water sample was filtered through a pre-weighed glass-fibre filter paper. The filter paper was dried in an oven at 105 °C for 24 hours, cooled in a desiccator, and re-weighed. TSS was calculated as the difference in weight of the filter paper before and after filtration, divided by the volume of the sample filtered and expressed in mg L^{-1} .

Biological oxygen demand (BOD_5) was determined using the 5-day incubation method. Water samples were transferred into 300-mL BOD bottles, with appropriate dilution using oxygen-saturated distilled water where necessary. Initial dissolved oxygen (DO_1) was measured immediately after sample preparation. The bottles were incubated at 20 ± 1 °C for 5 days in the dark to prevent photosynthesis. After incubation, the final dissolved oxygen (DO_5) was measured. BOD_5 was calculated as the difference between DO_1 and DO_5 , taking dilution factors into account. Nitrification inhibition was applied where necessary following standard procedures.

All analyses were conducted in accordance with the Standard Methods for the Examination of Water and Wastewater as described by APHA (1998).

Fish Growth Performance and Feed Utilisation

Growth performance and nutrient utilisation parameters were evaluated using standard formulae described by Dabrowski (1986), Jauncey (2008), Jamabo and Alfred-

Ockya (2008), and Pangni *et al.* (2008).

Statistical Analysis

Data obtained from the experiment were subjected to a One-Way Analysis of Variance using the IBM-SPSS statistical package version 22. Means of parameters were separated using Duncan's Multiple Range Test with an acceptable value of $p \leq 0.05$.

Results

Proximate Composition of the Soaked and oven-dried *Jatropha tanjorensis* Leaf Meal (JTLM)

Table 2 reveals that *Jatropha tanjorensis* leaf meal (JTLM) used in this study contained 25.5% crude protein as the highest and moisture level (0.9%) as the lowest in concentration.

Physicochemical Parameters of Water

The average values across the 10-week period are presented in Table 3. The DO decreased with increasing JTLM inclusion. DO in the 20% JTLM group (4.8 mg L^{-1}) was significantly lower than the control (5.3 mg L^{-1}). Conductivity increased significantly from $430 \mu\text{S cm}^{-1}$ (0%) to $470 \mu\text{S cm}^{-1}$ (20%). The TSS increased significantly in the 10% and 20% JTLM groups. BOD progressively increased with higher JTLM inclusion. The 20% group (2.6 mg L^{-1}) had significantly higher BOD than the control (1.8 mg L^{-1}).

Tabela 2. Proximate Composition of *Jatropha tanjorensis* Leaf Meal (JTLM). Expressed as mean \pm SD.

Table 2. Sestava listne moke *Jatropha tanjorensis* (JTLM). Izraženo kot povprečje \pm SD.

Nutrient Component	Percentage (%)
Crude Protein	25.5
Crude Fibre	5.0
Crude Fat (Ether Extract)	20.3
Ash	9.5
Moisture	0.9
Nitrogen-Free Extract (NFE)	38.8

Tabela 3. Water Quality Parameters. Expressed as mean \pm SD.Table 3. Parametri kakovosti vode. Izraženo kot povprečje \pm SD.

Parameter	0% JTLM	5% JTLM	10% JTLM	20% JTLM	Optimal Range (FME, 2006)
pH	6.7 \pm 0.10 ^a	6.8 \pm 0.11 ^a	6.9 \pm 0.12 ^a	7.0 \pm 0.09 ^a	6.5–8.5
Temperature (°C)	27.4 \pm 0.4 ^a	27.5 \pm 0.3 ^a	27.6 \pm 0.5 ^a	27.5 \pm 0.4 ^a	25–30
DO (mg L ⁻¹)	5.3 \pm 0.2 ^a	5.1 \pm 0.2 ^b	5.0 \pm 0.2 ^b	4.8 \pm 0.2 ^c	\geq 5.0
Conductivity (μ S cm ⁻¹)	430 \pm 12 ^a	440 \pm 15 ^b	460 \pm 14 ^b	470 \pm 16 ^b	< 500
TSS (mg L ⁻¹)	12.0 \pm 2.1 ^a	13.5 \pm 2.4 ^{ab}	14.2 \pm 2.5 ^b	15.0 \pm 2.6 ^b	< 50
BOD (mg L ⁻¹)	1.8 \pm 0.3 ^a	2.0 \pm 0.2 ^a	2.3 \pm 0.3 ^b	2.6 \pm 0.4 ^c	< 10

Note: Values with different superscripts across rows are significantly different at $p \leq 0.05$ using Duncan's Multiple Range Test. JTLM = *Jatropha tanjorensis* Leaf Meal; DO = Dissolved Oxygen; TSS = Total Suspended Solids; BOD = Biological Oxygen Demand.

Tabela 4. Growth Performance and Feed Utilisation of *Clarias gariepinus* Fed Different Levels of *Jatropha tanjorensis* Leaf Meal (JTLM). Expressed as mean \pm SD.Table 4. Rast in izkoristek krme pri ribi *Clarias gariepinus*, krmljeni z različnimi količinami listne moke *Jatropha tanjorensis* (JTLM). Podatki so izraženi kot povprečje \pm SD.

Parameter	0% JTLM	5% JTLM	10% JTLM	20% JTLM
Initial Mean Weight (g)	4.62 \pm 0.34	4.85 \pm 0.51	4.58 \pm 0.49	4.12 \pm 0.52
Final Mean Weight (g)	12.00 \pm 0.48 ^a	14.00 \pm 0.42 ^b	13.70 \pm 0.46 ^b	10.00 \pm 0.39 ^c
Weight Gain (g)	7.39 \pm 0.28 ^a	9.22 \pm 0.31 ^b	9.13 \pm 0.33 ^b	5.95 \pm 0.26 ^c
Initial Total Length (cm)	6.17 \pm 0.51	7.77 \pm 0.39	7.85 \pm 0.41	6.64 \pm 0.31
Final Total Length (cm)	8.90 \pm 0.42 ^a	10.50 \pm 0.39 ^b	10.77 \pm 0.43 ^b	9.10 \pm 0.37 ^a
Initial Standard Length (cm)	4.71 \pm 0.36	4.91 \pm 0.45	6.43 \pm 0.31	4.21 \pm 0.26
Final Standard Length (cm)	6.55 \pm 0.35 ^a	7.12 \pm 0.34 ^b	8.20 \pm 0.38 ^c	6.12 \pm 0.32 ^a
Daily Growth Rate (g day ⁻¹)	0.106 \pm 0.01 ^a	0.132 \pm 0.01 ^b	0.130 \pm 0.01 ^b	0.085 \pm 0.01 ^c
Specific Growth Rate (% g day ⁻¹)	1.36 \pm 0.04 ^a	1.52 \pm 0.03 ^b	1.56 \pm 0.03 ^b	1.28 \pm 0.04 ^c
Feed Conversion Ratio (FCR)	3.94 \pm 0.02 ^b	3.58 \pm 0.05 ^a	3.52 \pm 0.06 ^a	4.18 \pm 0.07 ^c
Condition Factor (K)	1.70 \pm 0.04 ^a	1.22 \pm 0.03 ^c	1.10 \pm 0.03 ^c	1.33 \pm 0.03 ^b
Initial Number of Fish	40	40	40	40
Final Number of Fish	35	33	37	30
Survival Rate (%)	87.5	82.5	92.5	75.0

Note: Superscripts (a, b, c) within rows indicate statistically significant differences ($p \leq 0.05$). Values with the same letter are not significantly different, while those with different letters are significantly different.

Figure 1. Showing some growth parameters.

Slika 1. Prikaz nekaterih parametrov rasti.

Growth Performance and Feed Utilisation of *Clarias gariepinus* Fingerlings

The growth performance indices of *Clarias gariepinus* fingerlings fed diets containing 0%, 5%, 10%, and 20% JTLM for 10 weeks are shown in Table 4.2. Each group started with distinct average initial weights and length parameters. Fish fed 5% and 10% JTLM diets exhibited significantly higher final weights and weight gains ($p \leq 0.05$) compared to the control (0%) and 20% groups. The daily growth rate recorded was the highest in the 5% (0.132 ± 0.01 % g day⁻¹) JTLM group, followed closely by 10% (0.130 ± 0.01) JTLM group. While the specific growth rate was recorded as the highest in 10% (1.56 ± 0.03 % g day⁻¹) in the JTLM group, followed closely by 5% (1.52 ± 0.03 % g day⁻¹). Best (lowest) FCR was recorded in the 5% and 10% groups (3.58 ± 0.05 and 3.52 ± 0.06), which were statistically superior to both the 0% (3.94) and 20% (4.18) inclusion levels.

The highest K was observed in the control group (1.70). However, fish in all groups maintained a healthy range (>1.0). The survival rate was high across treatments (75.0% to 92.5%), but 20% JTLM (75%) had a significantly lower survival rate than the others. Statistical analysis (ANOVA)

showed significant differences ($p \leq 0.05$) in weight gain, DGR, SGR, FCR, PI and K among treatments. Figure 1 is a graphical representation of some growth parameters in this study. Here, the fish fed diets containing 5% and 10% JTLM showed significantly higher final mean weight, total length, and standard length compared with the control (0%) and 20% JTLM groups. The 10% JTLM treatment produced the highest overall growth performance. In contrast, fish fed 20% JTLM recorded the lowest growth values, indicating reduced growth at higher inclusion levels. Initial weight and length were similar across all treatments.

Discussion

The proximate composition of *Jatropha tanjorensis* leaf meal (JTLM) indicates that it is a moderately protein-rich plant ingredient with potential value as a supplementary feed component in aquaculture diets. The crude protein content (25.5%) obtained in this study is comparable to values reported by Obikaonu *et al.* (2012) and Asuquo and Ifon (2021), although lower than the 35–45% dietary protein requirement of *Clarias gariepinus* fingerlings (FAO, 2017).

Kumar *et al.* (2008) reported higher crude protein values (35.3–35.6%) for processed and raw JTLM, while Ugboqu *et al.* (2014) reported 29.4% for *Jatropha curcas* seeds. Although the protein level in JTLM is below the optimal requirement for sole use, it remains nutritionally relevant when incorporated with conventional protein sources such as fishmeal and soybean meal (Asuquo and Ifon, 2021). Protein remains the most critical and expensive dietary component in fish production (Essien *et al.*, 2024); therefore, identifying cost-effective plant-based supplements without compromising fish health is of considerable importance.

The fibre (5.0%) and carbohydrate (NFE 38.8%) fractions suggest that JTLM may influence nutrient utilisation depending on inclusion level. High fibre content can impair digestibility and feed conversion in carnivorous fish such as *C. gariepinus*, which have limited capacity to digest complex plant polysaccharides (Olukunle, 2013). At moderate inclusion (5–10%), fibre may support gut motility without adversely affecting nutrient absorption. However, excessive fibre at 20% inclusion likely exceeded the digestive tolerance threshold, contributing to reduced feed utilisation efficiency.

The crude fat content (20.3%) indicates the presence of beneficial lipids essential for energy metabolism and physiological functions (NRC, 2011). This moderate lipid level likely supported an adequate energy supply without excessive fat deposition. Additionally, *Jatropha tanjorensis* contains phytochemicals such as flavonoids and saponins (Adeniyi *et al.*, 2015), which may contribute antioxidative and antimicrobial benefits, potentially enhancing fish health.

The ash content (9.5%) reflects the mineral composition and is within acceptable ranges for plant-based feed ingredients (NRC, 2011). Moisture content (9.8%) was below the 12% threshold associated with microbial spoilage (Al-Thobaiti *et al.* 2018), suggesting adequate processing and storage conditions.

The present study demonstrates that dietary inclusion of JTLM at moderate levels (5–10%) enhances growth performance and feed utilisation in *C. gariepinus* fingerlings, whereas higher inclusion (20%) results in reduced performance. Fish fed 5% and 10% JTLM showed significantly higher weight gain, specific growth rate (SGR), and improved feed conversion ratio (FCR) compared with the control and 20% groups ($p < 0.05$). The 10% inclusion level produced the most consistent growth response. These findings align with reports by Fagbenro *et al.* (2010), Al-Thobaiti *et al.* (2018), and Asuquo and Ifon (2021), who

observed improved performance at moderate plant-protein inclusion levels. Similarly, Adene *et al.* (2022) reported optimal performance of *C. gariepinus* at 10% inclusion of *Jatropha curcas* meal.

This pattern suggests that JTLM exerts a dose-dependent effect on growth, with beneficial outcomes at moderate inclusion and diminishing returns at excessive levels. However, the mechanisms underlying these responses cannot be definitively established from the present data. While reduced growth at higher inclusion levels may be associated with increased fibre content, altered nutrient balance, or anti-nutritional factors such as saponins and tannins (Musa *et al.*, 2018; Jimoh *et al.*, 2020), digestibility, palatability, toxicity, and metabolic responses were not directly measured. Consequently, these explanations remain plausible hypotheses rather than confirmed causal mechanisms.

Feed conversion efficiency was significantly improved at 5–10% inclusion and deteriorated at 20%, suggesting that excessive plant material may limit nutrient utilisation capacity in *C. gariepinus*. Although survival remained relatively high across treatments, slight reductions at 20% inclusion may reflect cumulative anti-nutritional effects, consistent with findings by Musa *et al.* (2018) and Jimoh *et al.* (2020).

Water quality parameters remained within acceptable limits for freshwater fish culture (APHA, 1998; Anyanwu *et al.*, 2012; Okon *et al.*, 2020). Temperature (27–28°C), pH (6.7–7.0), and dissolved oxygen ($\geq 4.8 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$) were within optimal ranges, and no significant differences were observed among treatments ($p > 0.05$). Slight increases in BOD and TSS at higher JTLM inclusion levels were likely attributable to increased organic load from undigested plant material, as similarly observed by Amosu *et al.* (2023). However, these changes did not exceed critical thresholds and were unlikely to have constrained growth.

Several limitations of the present study should be acknowledged. Digestibility, palatability, and toxicity assessments were not conducted, limiting mechanistic interpretation. Haematological and biochemical indices were not evaluated, restricting assessment of physiological stress or metabolic alterations. The experimental duration was relatively short, and no cost-benefit analysis was performed to assess economic feasibility. Recognition of these limitations is essential for accurate interpretation and to guide future research.

Despite these constraints, the findings provide clear

evidence that JTLM can be incorporated into the diets of *C. gariepinus* fingerlings at moderate levels without compromising growth. The consistent pattern of enhanced growth and feed efficiency at 10% inclusion, coupled with reduced performance at 20%, indicates that JTLM functions effectively as a supplementary ingredient within a narrow optimal inclusion range rather than as a high-level replacement for conventional protein sources. Biologically, the results suggest that *C. gariepinus* can utilise JTLM-derived nutrients efficiently at moderate levels, but excessive inclusion may exceed the species' capacity to process plant-based components. Under the conditions of this study, a 10% inclusion level is therefore statistically and biologically justified.

Conclusion

The results revealed that diets containing 5% and 10% JTLM significantly improved growth parameters, including weight gain, specific growth rate (SGR) and feed conversion ratio (FCR), compared to the control (0%) and the 20% JTLM group. The 10% JTLM group recorded the best overall performance, indicating an optimal balance of protein supplementation and digestibility. Water quality parameters such as pH, temperature, and dissolved oxygen remained within acceptable ranges across treatments, although BOD, TSS, and conductivity showed a slight increase at 20% inclusion. This suggests a threshold above which increased plant material may begin to compromise water quality and fish health. Furthermore, fish survival and condition factor remained high across all treatments, but a notable decline in survival rate at the 20% inclusion level indicates the possible impact of anti-nutritional factors and high fibre content at excessive JTLM incorporation. The proximate composition of JTLM, especially its moderate protein (22.5%), fat (4.3%), and carbohydrate level, supports JTLM as a potential cost-effective, plant-based ingredient in sustainable aquaculture feed formulation when properly included.

Recommendations

Based on this and similar studies, it is recommended that *Jatropha tanjorensis* leaf meal be included at 5% to 10% of total feed composition for *Clarias gariepinus* fingerlings to achieve optimal growth and feed efficiency without compromising water quality or fish health. Also,

- JTLM should be well-dried, crushed, or fermented to reduce anti-nutritional factors such as tannins, saponins, and phytic acid, thereby improving nutrient availability and palatability.

To enhance JTLM-based diets, it is recommended to supplement with higher-protein sources like fishmeal, soybean meal, or amino acid concentrates to meet the nutritional requirements of catfish, especially during early growth stages.

- Further studies should be conducted to examine the long-term effects of JTLM inclusion on their proximate analysis, biochemical and haematological profiles, and JTLM should be used in other aquaculture species such as tilapia or *Heterobranchus spp.* for broader application.
- Future research integrating digestibility trials, physiological assessments, long-term feeding experiments, and economic evaluations will be necessary to fully define the nutritional and commercial potential of JTLM in aquaculture feeds.

Author's Contribution

Conceptualization, E.A.E., A.O.O. and E.P.U.; methodology, E.A.E., A.O.O., E.P.U., P.O.I., B.O.B., E.N.D. and B.O.E.; software, E.A.E.; validation, E.A.E., A.O.O., E.P.U. and E.N.D.; formal analysis, E.A.E.; investigation, E.A.E., A.O.O. and E.P.U.; resources, E.A.E., A.O.O., P.O.I., B.O.B., E.N.D. and B.O.E.; data curation, E.A.E., A.O.O. and E.N.D.; writing—original draft preparation, E.A.E.; writing—review and editing, E.A.E., A.O.O., E.P.U. and E.N.D.; supervision, A.O.O., E.P.U. and E.N.D.; funding acquisition, E.A.E., P.O.I., B.O.B. and B.O.E. All authors read and approved the final manuscript

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Data Availability

The research data is deposited at Zenodo (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19056885>).

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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Original Research

Pseudomonas stutzeri AK17 Mediated Modulation of Plant Defence Responses under Drought Stress

Ritika Jain^{1*}, Meenu Saraf², Dhaval Acharya¹, Rachana Shukla¹, Tisha Vyas¹, Shreya Modi¹, Tanvi Panchal¹

Abstract

Drought is one of the severe abiotic stresses that limits the growth and yield of crops, mainly in arid and semi-arid regions. Cluster bean (*Cyamopsis tetragonoloba* L.) is relatively tolerant but suffers physiological and biochemical detriments during prolonged water scarcity. Plant growth-promoting rhizobacteria provide a sustainable biological strategy for improving plant resilience under drought stress. This study demonstrates the potential of *P. stutzeri* AK17 in mitigating drought stress, which is currently underexplored. Greenhouse experiments were conducted to study the effect of drought on treated and untreated plants by withholding water for 4, 8 and 12 days. Various parameters such as osmolyte production, antioxidant enzyme activities (APX, SOD, CAT) and expression of drought-responsive genes (P5CS, BADH and CAT) in cluster bean were studied. It has been observed that *P. stutzeri* AK17 inoculation significantly enhanced the osmolyte accumulation under drought stress as compared to uninoculated plants. Decrease in the antioxidant enzyme activities in the *P. stutzeri* AK17-treated plants under severe stress suggests an efficient ROS homeostasis. Gene expression study revealed an upregulation of P5CS and BADH gene, while downregulation of the CAT gene on the 12th day of drought stress, which is correlated with the biochemical results. These findings indicate that there is some crosstalk between various defence mechanisms, and *P. stutzeri* AK17 has an important role in enhancing the defence systems. Therefore, the present work demonstrates the potential of *P. stutzeri* AK17 as a bioinoculant for enhancing drought tolerance in cluster bean under controlled greenhouse conditions, and future studies are required to evaluate its performance under field conditions for broader agricultural applicability.

Keywords

Drought stress, Cluster bean, *Pseudomonas stutzeri*, osmolytes, antioxidant enzymes, gene expression

¹ Gandhinagar Institute of Science, Gandhinagar University, Gujarat, India

² Department of Microbiology and Biotechnology, Gujarat University, Gujarat, India

* Corresponding author:

E-mail address: ritikajain3010@gmail.com

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Modulacija obrambnih odzivov rastlin pod vplivom suše, ki jo povzroča *Pseudomonas stutzeri* AK17

Izvleček

Suša je eden izmed abiotičnih stresov, ki omejuje rast in pridelek poljščin, predvsem v sušnih in plosušnih regijah. Grozdasti fižol (*Cyamopsis tetragonoloba* L.) je relativno odporna rastlina, vendar pri daljšem pomanjkanju vode utrpri fiziološke in biokemične posledice. Rizobakterije, ki spodbujajo rast rastlin, zagotavljajo trajnostno biološko strategijo za izboljšanje odpornosti rastlin v sušnih razmerah. Naša študija predstavlja potencial *P. stutzeri* AK17 pri blaženju sušnega stresa, ki je trenutno premalo raziskan. V kontroliranem poskusu v rastlinjaku smo testirali učinek suše na obdelane in neobdelane rastline z zadrževanjem vode za 4, 8 in 12 dni. Proučevali smo različne parametre, kot so proizvodnja osmolita, aktivnost antioksidativnih encimov (APX, SOD, CAT) in ekspresija genov, ki se odzivajo na sušo (P5CS, BADH in CAT). Ugotovljeno je bilo, da je inokulacija s *P. stutzeri* AK17 ob suši znatno povečala kopičenje osmolita v primerjavi z neinokuliranimi rastlinami. Zmanjšanje aktivnosti antioksidativnih encimov v rastlinah, obdelanih s *P. stutzeri* AK17, v pogojih hude suše kaže na učinkovito homeostazo ROS. Študija genetske ekspresije je pokazala povečano ekspresijo genov P5CS in BADH, medtem ko se je 12. dan sušnega stresa zmanjšala ekspresija gena CAT, kar je v skladu z biokemičnimi rezultati. Ti rezultati kažejo, da obstaja medsebojna povezanost med različnimi obrambnimi mehanizmi, pri čemer ima *P. stutzeri* AK17 pomembno vlogo pri krepitvi obrambnih sistemov rastline. Študija dokazuje potencial *P. stutzeri* AK17 kot bioinokulanta za povečanje sušne tolerance pri fižolu v nadzorovanih rastnih pogojih, pri čemer so potrebne nadaljnje študije za oceno njegove učinkovitosti v poljskih pogojih za širšo uporabo v kmetijstvu.

Gljučne besede

sušni stres, grozdasti fižol, *Pseudomonas stutzeri*, osmoliti, antioksidativni encimi, genska ekspresija

Introduction

The most severe economic losses in agriculture are caused by drought stress, which restricts crop growth and yield, especially in arid and semi-arid regions. This type of abiotic stress affects the plant's water relationship at the cellular and systemic levels, leading to both specific and generalised reactions and damages (Chaffai et al., 2024). Basic physiological indicators involve diminished water content, lowered leaf water potential, loss of turgor, stomatal closure, and impaired cellular development and expansion. Acute water stress ultimately leads to plant mortality by inhibiting photosynthesis and altering metabolic processes (Qiao et al., 2024). Plants have many strategies to cope with drought, such as osmotic adjustment via producing compatible solutes (such as proline, glycine betaine, trehalose) and by expression of some stress-responsive genes (Chieb & Gachomo 2023). However, the inbuilt tolerance of many plants is limited, and an enhanced mechanism is needed to mitigate drought stress and sustain agricultural productivity under stress.

One promising approach to mitigate drought stress is the use of plant growth-promoting rhizobacteria (PGPR). The interaction of these beneficial bacteria with plants manifests a variety of physiological, biochemical, and molecular activities (Nad et al. 2024). PGPR improves drought tolerance ability in plants through multiple, often synergistic mechanisms, such as producing phytohormones, improving nutrient uptake, production of exopolysaccharide (EPS), which helps to retain soil moisture and lowering stress-induced ethylene levels by ACC deaminase activities (Jain & Saraf, 2023). Moreover, inoculation with PGPR also results in increased osmolytes accumulation, decreased lipid peroxidation and ROS accumulation, and improved activities of antioxidant enzymes such as superoxide dismutase (SOD), catalase (CAT) and ascorbate peroxidase (APX) under drought stress (Al-Turki et al. 2023). A recent review shows that PGPR-induced drought tolerance consists of an integrated network of physiological, biochemical, and molecular modifications in host plants (Liu et al. 2025).

Among PGPR, *Pseudomonas* species have been studied extensively for their stress-ameliorating poten-

tial. Some recent studies show that *Pseudomonas* spp. play an important role in improving plant tolerance to abiotic stresses. For example, *Pseudomonas* ms22 possesses various plant growth-promoting activities which improve the growth of its host plant, i.e., sorghum under drought-mimicking conditions (Mulugeta et al. 2025). Inoculation of *Arabidopsis thaliana* with *Pseudomonas koreensis* S4T10 helps the plant cope with drought and salt stress (Kalleku et al. 2024). *Pseudomonas stutzeri* also shows promising results under abiotic stress such as salinity stress. For example, inoculation of *P. stutzeri* mitigates salt stress in lettuce, sunflower, barley and sorghum (Szymańska et al. 2022) and also heavy metal stress in *Lemna* species (Gulmez et al. 2023). These studies show that *P. stutzeri* possesses adapted stress-mitigating properties that extend beyond salinity, potentially into drought stress scenarios.

Cluster bean (also known as guar, *Cyamopsis tetragonoloba*) is a leguminous crop of economic importance in arid and semi-arid regions. It grows under conditions of water scarcity, which makes it a suitable source for drought mitigation studies. Only a few studies were reported on PGPR-induced drought tolerance in cluster bean, particularly with *Pseudomonas stutzeri*. Our previous research (Jain & Saraf, 2023) revealed *P. stutzeri* AK17 as a promising strain by screening for abiotic stress tolerance, plant growth-promoting characteristics, and pot trials.

In this study, we aim to examine the role of *Pseudomonas stutzeri* AK17 in augmenting drought tolerance in cluster bean in greenhouse conditions. We hypothesise that inoculation with *P. stutzeri* AK17 enhances drought tolerance in cluster bean by regulating physiological, biochemical and molecular defence mechanisms. Mainly, we propose that inoculation of AK17 (i) enhances osmolytes accumulation to maintain cellular osmotic balance (ii) reduces oxidative damage by regulating ROS levels and lipid peroxidation (iii) regulates key stress-responsive genes, including pyrroline-5-carboxylate synthase (P5CS), Betaine aldehyde dehydrogenase (BADH) and catalase (CAT) under drought stress. These hypotheses were tested through integrated physiological, biochemical and gene expression analyses.

Material and methods

On the basis of abiotic stress tolerance, plant growth-promoting traits and pot study from our previous study (Jain

& Saraf, 2023), *Pseudomonas stutzeri* AK17, which was isolated from the rhizosphere of cluster bean, was selected for this study.

Seed sterilisation and biopriming

Surface sterilisation of cluster bean seeds was done by treatment with 75% ethanol for 1 min, followed by dipping the seeds in 1% sodium hypochlorite (NaOCl) for 30 sec, and afterwards washing them properly with sterile distilled water 4 to 5 times. The soil used for the pot study was collected from Gujarat University, Ahmedabad, India. The soil was of loamy texture with a pH of 7.5, electrical conductivity 0.42 ds/m, organic carbon content 0.74%, available nitrogen 0.08%, available phosphorus 0.012 %, and available potassium is 0.015%. Prior to the pot study, the soil was sterilised by autoclaving at 15 psi at 121 °C for 20 min, 2 times at an interval of 24 h. The AK17 strain was inoculated in nutrient broth and incubated for 24h – 38h under shaking conditions at 100 rpm for activation. The activated broth was centrifuged at 8000 rpm for 10 min. The pellet was resuspended in sterile distilled water, and cell density was maintained at 10⁸ CFU/ml. The sterilised cluster bean seeds were allowed to soak in this bacterial suspension for 20 min and then allowed to air-dry. The seeds were then used for planting in pots; untreated seeds soaked in sterile distilled water were used as a control.

Experimental setup

The experiment was conducted in a completely randomised design with three replicates per treatment. Five seeds were planted per pot (8.0 cm × 11 cm size) filled with 2 kg sterile loam soil. The plant survival rate was recorded after 15 days of sowing. The cluster bean seeds were allowed to germinate and grow for 21 days under greenhouse conditions maintained at 28 ± 2 °C temperature, 60-70% relative humidity. Plants were irrigated at regular intervals for 21 days. After that, three levels of drought stress were given by withholding water for 4 days, 8 days and 12 days. Soil inoculation with bacterial suspension was done prior to the initiation of drought stress.

Leaf samples were collected at different time intervals, i.e., 0, 4, 8, 12 days of drought stress, to study various defence mechanisms developed by treated and untreated plants. Three plants were selected randomly from each treatment.

Proline content

The method described by Ahmed and Hassan (2011) was used to measure the proline content of leaves. Fresh leaves (0.5 g) from each treatment were collected and homogenised with 10 mL of 3% sulfosalicylic acid. The homogenised mixture was centrifuged for 5 min at 10,000 rpm. After centrifugation, 2 mL of the supernatant was collected in a fresh test tube and mixed with an equal amount of glacial acetic acid and freshly prepared ninhydrin reagent. This mixture was heated in a water bath at 90 °C for 1 h, and then the mixture was quickly transferred to ice to stop the reaction. 5 mL of toluene was added to the reaction mixture, followed by 15 sec of vortexing. The tubes were incubated for 20 min at room temperature in the dark to allow the toluene and aqueous phases to separate. The upper layer, containing the extracted proline, was collected in a separate test tube. Afterwards, the absorbance was measured at 520 nm using a spectrophotometer. The standard curve was prepared by using different concentrations of pure proline ranging from 0 to 100 µg/mL

Total amino acid content

The total amino acid content of the leaves was determined using the ninhydrin method. Freeze-dried leaf sample of 1000 mg was ground in 5 mL methanol-chloroform-water solution (60:25:15 v/v) and incubated at 60 °C for 2 h. The samples were then centrifuged at 10,000 rpm for 30 min. Total amino acid content was evaluated by heating 1 mL of the supernatant with 1 mL of 0.1M acetate buffer and 1 mL of 5% ninhydrin (in ethanol) at 95 °C for 15 min, and this was then finally cooled to room temperature. Absorbance was measured at 570 nm using a spectrophotometer. The amino acid leucine was used to prepare the standard curve (Starcher 2001).

Total soluble sugar content

Total soluble sugar content was calculated according to the method described by Dubois et al. (1951). Fresh leaves from all treatments were collected and ground with 3 mL of 80% methanol, followed by heating them in a water bath at 70 °C for 30 min. Then concentrated sulphuric acid H₂SO₄ (1.5 mL) was combined with an equal volume of extract (0.5 mL) and 5% phenol before being incubated again for 30 min in the dark. The absorbance of the sample was measured at

490 nm. Glucose was used to prepare a standard curve, and the sugar content was expressed as µg/g FW.

Glycine betaine content

Glycine betaine content was calculated using the spectrophotometer method described by Grieve and Grattan (1983). The collected leaves were shaken mechanically in deionised water at 25 °C for two days. Followed by filtration, the cell-free supernatant was diluted with 1.5 mL H₂SO₄ (2 N) sulfuric acid. Afterwards, it was allowed to cool down, and then 0.05 mL of cold KI-I₂ (potassium iodide-iodine reagent) was added to the mixture. A complex form after incubation was separated from the acid mixture by centrifugation. This complex in crystal form was dissolved in 1, 2-dichloro ethane (9 mL) and then incubated for 2 h. After incubation, the absorbance was analysed at 365 nm. Glycine betaine of Himedia was used to plot a standard curve, and the glycine betaine value was calculated as µg/g.

Lipid peroxidation

The amount of lipid peroxidation in cluster bean leaves was measured by the method described by Wu et al. (2014). The thiobarbituric acid test was used to measure the content of malondialdehyde (MDA) in the leaves. 0.5 g of fresh leaves were mixed with the 100 mM phosphate buffer to acquire a final volume of 8 mL. After centrifugation at 15,000 rpm for 20 min at 4 °C, the supernatant was collected. To this collected supernatant (1.5 mL), a reaction mixture (2.5 mL) containing 5% Trichloroacetic acid (TCA) and Thiobarbituric acid (TBA) was added. This solution mixture was incubated in a water bath at 100 °C for 30 min and then allowed to cool down at room temperature. After that, the mixture was centrifuged at 4800 rpm for 10 min, and the supernatant was collected in a fresh tube. Using a spectrophotometer, the absorbance of the supernatant was taken at 532 nm. The mixture of TCA and TBA was used as a blank for the spectrophotometer.

Hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂) content

The H₂O₂ content of the leaves was calculated by the method described by Velikova et al. (2000) with some modifications. The 0.25 g leaves were crushed in 5% TCA (3 mL) and 0.1 g activated charcoal at 0 °C. The mixture was centrifuged for 15 min at 12,000g. Take 0.5 mL of supernatant and

add an equal volume of 10mM potassium phosphate buffer and 0.75 ml potassium iodide (1M). The absorbance was measured by a UV-VIS spectrophotometer at 390 nm, and the H₂O₂ content was determined as $\mu\text{mol g}^{-1}$ DW.

Non-enzymatic mechanism: total phenol and total flavonoid content

The plant leaves were shade-dried at room temperature and finely powdered. The powdered material was extracted with 95% ethanol in 1:10 w/v by maceration for 48h at room temperature with intermittent shaking. The extraction was repeated three times to ensure complete recovery of bioactive compounds. The solvent was evaporated in the rotary evaporator, and the dried extract was obtained. About 10-50 mg of the dried extract was dissolved in methanol and used to calculate phenol and flavonoid content.

Total phenol content was studied using the method described by Wolfe et al. (2003). Folin-Ciocalteu reagent, which had previously been prepared as a 10% v/v dilution in distilled water, was combined with 0.5 ml of the leaf extract solution. The mixture turned blue after the addition of 4 mL of 75% anhydrous sodium carbonate. The resulting mixtures were vortexed and incubated at 40°C for 30 min. Afterwards, the absorbance was measured at 765nm using a UV-VIS spectrophotometer. Tannic acid was used to create the standard curve, and the sample's unknown content was estimated.

Utilising Ordonez's aluminium chloride technique, total flavonoid content was calculated (Ordonez et al. 2006). An equivalent volume of 2% aluminium chloride made using ethanol was mixed with 0.5 mL of the sample extract from the crushed leaves. After one hour of incubation at room temperature, the absorbance of the mixture at 420 nm was measured. A variety of quercetin concentrations were used for the calibration of the standard curve.

Enzymatic defence mechanism: superoxide dismutase, catalase, and ascorbate peroxidase

Plant leaves weighing 500 mg were crushed in the buffer containing 5 mL of a 50 mM phosphate buffer (pH 7.0) and 1% (v/v) polyvinylpyrrolidone (PVPP). The supernatant was obtained after centrifuging the crude extract at 10,000 g at 4 °C for 15 min, and this supernatant was used for antioxidant enzyme analysis.

The assay for superoxide dismutase, which relies on its capacity to prevent the photochemical reduction of nitro blue tetrazolium (NBT), was carried out using standard methodology (Ellouzi et al., 2013). The reaction mixture consists of 100 μl of the enzyme extract or the supernatant in 50 mM phosphate buffer, 75 μM NBT, 13 mM methionine, 2 μM riboflavin and EDTA (0.1 mM), making up the volume to 3 ml. This reaction mixture was incubated for 10 min at room temperature for the development of purple colour formazan. The absorbance was measured at 560 nm, and distilled water was used as a blank.

The catalase activity in the leaves of cluster bean was calculated according to the method described by Kumar et al. (2010). Equal parts of 300 mM H₂O₂ and H₂O were added to the enzyme extract (0.1 mL), along with 2.8 mL of 100% diluted 50 mM phosphate buffer. Catalase activity was calculated using the extinction coefficient of H₂O₂. One unit of catalase activity was defined as the amount of enzyme required to decompose 1 μmol of H₂O₂ per minute. The decrease in absorbance was measured at 240 nm.

The Starlin and Gopalakrishnan method (2010) was used to conduct the APX assay. 300 mM H₂O₂ (0.1 mL), 7.5 mM ascorbate (0.1 mL), 100% diluted 50 mM phosphate buffer (2.7 mL), and 1 mL of enzyme extract were added. In the reaction solution, distilled water was used as a blank in place of the enzyme solution. APX activity was calculated using the extinction coefficient of ascorbate (2.8 mM⁻¹ cm⁻¹). One unit of APX activity was defined as the amount of enzyme required to oxidise 1 μmol of ascorbate per minute. At a time interval of 0–60 seconds, the absorbance was measured at 290 nm.

Correlation analysis was performed to evaluate the relationships among enzymatic and non-enzymatic antioxidant parameters, including proline, total soluble sugar (TSS), glycine betaine (GB), phenol, flavonoid and malondialdehyde (MDA) content. Person correlations were

Expression of drought stress-responsive genes

Total RNA was extracted from young, fully expanded leaves of cluster bean plants. After harvesting, leaves were immediately frozen in liquid nitrogen and stored at -80°C until further processing. RNA was extracted within 1 week of sample collection to ensure RNA integrity. All equipment, such as the mortar, pestle, glassware, spatula,

and other necessary items, was heated at 180°C for 5–6 hours. DEPC-treated sterile Milli-Q was used to treat the gel electrophoresis assembly and other plastic products. As per the requirement, the reagent was prepared with DEPC water as well. Approximately 0.1 g of plant leaves from each treatment were collected under sterile conditions and crushed in a pre-chilled mortar pestle with liquid nitrogen to form a fine powder. Total RNA was extracted using the PureLink™ RNA Mini Kit as per instructions. The purified RNA was quickly placed on ice for quantification and then stored at -80 °C for long-term use.

Total RNA samples were used to prepare the first strand of cDNA by reverse transcription using Verso cDNA synthesis kit (Thermo Scientific) according to the manufacturer's instructions. The synthesised cDNA was diluted five times with deionised water before use for the gene expression study. The expression of a specific gene was determined by using gene-specific primers (Suppl. Mat. Table S1), and the analyses of expression level by RT-PCR throughout the experiments were maintained by the reference gene. The expression level of three genes was studied under no stress and drought stress, i.e., CAT, BADH and P5CS and one reference gene, actin (ACT7). The primers were designed using IDT primer Quest software from the sequence of respective genes downloaded from the National Centre for Biotechnology Information (NCBI). qRT-PCR was performed using 2X Brilliant III SYBR green QPCR (Agilent Technologies, United States) in triplicate. The comparative Ct approach was used to assess the relative expression of the target gene in relation to a housekeeping gene (actin) and the samples (Rao et al., 2013). The relative expression of the gene was analysed by using the $2^{-\Delta\Delta Ct}$ method (Livak and Schmittgen, 2001). By studying the melting curve, the dissociation curve analysis of each sample was done to verify the specificity of the reaction (Sah et al. 2014).

Statistical analysis

The result of all the experiments was expressed as mean \pm standard deviation of three replicates. The data were analysed using two-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) to evaluate the effects of inoculation and drought stress duration and their interaction. When significant differences were observed ($p \leq 0.05$), Tukey's HSD test was applied for mean separation. Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS version 24.0.

Results

Proline and amino acid content

An increase in the proline and amino acid content was observed with increasing drought stress in the *Pseudomonas stutzeri* AK17-treated plant, as well as in uninoculated control plants. However, accumulation was much higher in the treated plant under severe drought stress (Figure 1a, b). Treated plants show 1.3-fold and 1.7-fold higher accumulation of amino acid and 1.8-fold and 2.7-fold higher accumulation of proline as compared to control on the 8th and 12th day of drought stress, respectively.

Total soluble sugar (TSS) content

Total soluble sugar content of the treated and untreated plants was found to be increased under drought stress. Under the no stress condition, i.e., on 21st DAS, the *Pseudomonas stutzeri* AK17-treated plant shows 40% higher TSS as compared to the control. On the 4th, 8th and 12th day of drought stress, the AK17 inoculated plants showed 78%, 83% and 98% higher TSS content as compared to the uninoculated control, respectively (Figure 1c).

Glycine betaine content

The glycine betaine content of the control plants increased under drought stress, but at a very slow rate, while the *Pseudomonas stutzeri* AK17-treated plants showed an increase in the glycine betaine content till 12th day of drought stress and had higher accumulation of GB content. The AK17-treated plants showed an increase in the GB content by 1.5 fold, 2.3 fold and 3.0 fold on the 4th, 8th and 12th day of drought stress, respectively, compared to the control (Figure 1d).

Lipid peroxidation

The amount of lipid peroxidation of the cells due to drought stress was measured by calculating the malondialdehyde (MDA) content in plants. MDA levels increased during lipid peroxidation of plant cell membranes if plants were under drought stress. No significant difference was observed in the MDA content of control and treated plants in the absence of drought stress, but under drought stress, a significant difference was found between the treated

Figure 1. Analysis of a) Proline content, b) total amino acid content, c) Total soluble sugar content, and d) Glycine betaine content of treated and untreated plants on different days of drought stress.

Slika 1. Analiza a) vsebnosti prolina, b) skupne vsebnosti aminokislin, c) skupne vsebnosti topnih sladkorjev in d) vsebnosti glicinbetaina pri obdelanih in neobdelanih rastlinah na različnih dneh sušnega stresa.

and untreated plants. The inoculation with *Pseudomonas stutzeri* AK17 reduces the MDA level by 61% and 76.9% at the 8th and 12th day of drought stress, respectively, as compared to uninoculated control plants (Figure 2: a).

Hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂) content

The production of H₂O₂ increased with an increase in drought stress in the treated and untreated plants. However, the plant treated with *Pseudomonas stutzeri* AK17 shows less increase in the H₂O₂ content than the untreated plant under drought stress. The AK17-treated plants show 1.2 fold, 1.85 fold and 1.7 fold decreases in the H₂O₂ content at 4th, 8th and 12th day of drought stress as compared to control (Figure 2: b).

Total phenol and flavonoid content

An increase in the phenol and flavonoid content of the treated and untreated plant leaves was observed under drought stress. The *Pseudomonas stutzeri* AK17-treated plants show 2-fold and 2.1-fold increases in the phenol and flavonoid content of the plant at the 12th day of drought stress compared to the control (Figure 3: a, b).

Enzymatic mechanism

Under well-watered conditions, not much difference was observed in the inoculated and uninoculated plants. On the 4th day of drought stress, the *Pseudomonas stutzeri* AK17-treated plant shows the highest SOD activity, and

Figure 2. Analysis of a) MDA content and b) H₂O₂ content of treated and untreated plants at different days of drought stress.

Slika 2. Analiza a) vsebnosti MDA in b) vsebnosti H₂O₂ pri obdelanih in neobdelanih rastlinah v različnih dneh sušnega stresa.

Figure 3. Analysis of a) Total phenol content (TPC) and b) Total flavonoid content (TFC) of treated and untreated plants at different days of drought stress.

Slika 3. Analiza a) skupne vsebnosti fenolov (TPC) in b) skupne vsebnosti flavonoidov (TFC) pri obdelanih in neobdelanih rastlinah v različnih dneh sušnega stresa.

then the activity was decreased with an increase in drought stress as compared to the untreated control plant. The AK17-treated plant shows 36.6 % lower SOD activity compared to the control at the 12th day of drought stress. The antioxidant activity of the CAT and APX were also studied, which shows that the *Pseudomonas stutzeri* AK17-treated plants have an increase in the activity of both the enzymes with an increase in drought stress, but the increase in activity was significantly lower as compared to that of the untreated control plants (Figure 4: a, b, c). This decrease in the antioxidant enzyme activity in the *Pseudomonas stutzeri* AK17-treated plant suggests that inoculation with AK17 results in minimising the ROS production in the plant, thus helpful in mitigating the effect of drought stress.

Relationship between the various defence systems

A correlation between the various types of enzymatic and non-enzymatic defence mechanisms was studied. The correlation revealed a near-perfect correlation between the glycine betaine, phenol and flavonoid content. Also, there was a strong correlation between the proline, amino acid and total soluble sugar (TSS) content. A negative correlation was found in the MDA and proline, TSS, GB, phenol, and flavonoid content. This suggests that as the production of osmolytes and antioxidant compounds increased, the MDA content decreased, leading to a reduction in the lipid peroxidation of the cells under drought stress (Figure 5).

Figure 4. Analysis of the enzymatic activity of a) SOD, b) APX, and c) CAT of treated and untreated plants at different days of drought stress.

Slika 4. Analiza encimske aktivnosti a) SOD, b) APX in c) CAT pri obdelanih in neobdelanih rastlinah v različnih dneh sušnega stresa.

Figure 5. Relationship between the studied parameters ($p \leq 0.05$): MDA malondialdehyde, TSS total soluble sugar, APX Ascorbate peroxidase, GB glycine betaine, H₂O₂ hydrogen peroxide, SOD superoxide dismutase, and CAT catalase.

Slika 5. Razmerje med preučevanimi parametri ($p \leq 0,05$): MDA (malondialdehid), TSS (skupni topni sladkorji), APX (askorbat peroksidaza), GB (glicin betain), H₂O₂ (vodikov peroksid), SOD (superoksid dismutaza) in CAT (katalaza).

AK17 inoculation alters stress-related gene expression

In order to confirm the result of the biochemical analyses, qRT-PCR analysis of three stress-responsive genes, namely, pyrroline-5-carboxylate synthase (P5CS), betaine aldehyde dehydrogenase (BADH) and catalase (CAT) genes, was carried out in *Pseudomonas stutzeri* AK17-treated plants and untreated plants at different levels of drought stress. The relative expression of the gene on the 0th, 4th, 8th and 12th day of drought stress was studied.

The result shows the significant differential expression of the genes at various levels of drought stress, and the expression data are shown to be correlated with our biochemical results. Under no stress conditions, the AK17-

treated plant shows 2.7-fold upregulation in the P5CS expression compared to the untreated plant. Under the drought stress conditions, a gradual increase in the expression of the P5CS gene was observed in the inoculated and uninoculated plants. The maximum expression was found in the *Pseudomonas stutzeri* AK17 inoculated plant at the 12th day of drought and was 4.2-fold higher compared to the uninoculated control at that level of drought stress (Figure 6a). A similar pattern of expression was found for the BADH gene. Under no stress conditions, the gene expression in the treated plants was 1.7-fold higher compared to the untreated plants. An increase in the expression of the gene was observed in both the plants with an increase in drought level, but the upregulation of the gene was much higher in the treated plant compared to the untreated one. There was

a 5.3-fold higher expression of the BADH gene in the *Pseudomonas stutzeri* AK17 inoculated plant at the 12th day of drought compared to the uninoculated control (Figure 6b).

A different pattern of expression was found in the catalase (CAT) gene under drought stress. There was no significant difference in the expression pattern of the CAT gene in treated and untreated plants under non-stress conditions. But the expression of the CAT gene was changed at various levels of drought stress. A gradual increase in the gene expression with an increase in drought stress was observed in the uninoculated control plant, but in the inoculated plant, the expression of the gene was up-regulated till 4th day of drought stress, and then a gradual decrease in the expression of the gene was observed. The *Pseudomonas stutzeri* AK17-treated plant shows 3-fold higher gene expression on the 4th day of drought stress compared to the control, and then the gene was down-regulated till the 12th day of drought stress by 2.1-fold

Discussion

The results from the present study explained that inoculation of *Pseudomonas stutzeri* AK17 significantly improved drought-associated physiological and biochemical parameters such as osmolytes accumulation, ROS management, antioxidant defence mechanism and expression of some stress-responsive genes compared to uninoculated plants ($p \leq 0.05$). These findings support and deepen the present understanding of how the PGPR promotes growth in cluster bean plants under drought stress.

The current study shows the higher accumulation of proline, soluble sugar, amino acid and glycine betaine in AK17-treated plants, especially under severe drought stress (i.e., 8th and 12th day of stress). Chandra et al. (2018) observed an increase in the proline content in the wheat plant by 1.53 and 1.75-fold when treated with *Pseudomonas palleroniana* strain DPB16 and *Pseudomonas fluorescens* strain DPB15, respectively, under drought stress for 5 days. Similarly, Kour et al. (2020) found an increase in the proline content of wheat by 2-fold at 75% water regime when treated with *Pseudomonas libanensis* EU-LWNA-33. Proline is also important for maintaining the nitrogen content of cells and guards against dehydration-induced protein misfolding (Ghosh et al. 2017). Another strategy for preparing for osmotic adjustment during drought stress is the accumulation of soluble sugar as osmolytes (Mishra et

al. 2016). Batool et al. (2020) found an increase in the TSS content of the potato plant by 59% and 75% under moderate and severe drought stress conditions, respectively, when treated with PGPR as compared to the untreated control. An increase in the GB content by 1.2-fold was observed in the wheat plant at 75% water regime when treated with *Pseudomonas libanensis* EU-LWNA-33 (Kour et al. 2020). Some studies show that the accumulation of glycine betaine and soluble sugar serves as a reliable biochemical marker of PGPR-mediated drought tolerance (Gowtham et al., 2022). In the present study, we observed an increase in the accumulation of proline, soluble sugar and glycine betaine during severe drought stress (8th and 12th day), which suggests that AK17 inoculation induces a prolonged osmotic adjustment response, which may result from a better root water uptake system or bacterial signaling for osmolyte synthesis.

Drought stress results in the accumulation of reactive oxygen species (ROS) such as hydrogen peroxide (H_2O_2), which cause damage to biomolecules such as lipid, protein and DNA. One way to measure lipid damage is by Malondialdehyde (MDA) content, which increases during drought in treated as well as in untreated plants, significantly higher in the latter. In the present study, inoculation of AK17 reduces the MDA content by 61% and 76.9% on the 8th and 12th day of drought stress, respectively, as compared to the untreated one. This shows that the AK17 treatment protects cell membrane integrity during severe drought. Mishra et al. (2016) found a significant decrease in the MDA content of the wheat on the 7th day of drought stress when treated with PGPR compared to the untreated control. In contrast to non-inoculated plants, PGPR inoculation reduced MDA buildup, which prevented membrane damage during drought. Chandra et al. (2018) found a decrease in the level of MDA at the 5th day of drought stress by 69.5% and 47.7% in the wheat plant inoculated with *Pseudomonas fluorescens* strain DPB15 and *P. palleroniana* strain DPB16, respectively. A significant decrease in the MDA content of the jujube (*Ziziphus jujuba*) under moderate and severe drought stress was observed when treated with *Pseudomonas lini* and *Serratia plymuthica* as compared to the untreated control plant (Zhang et al. 2020). The concentration of H_2O_2 also increases during drought stress, but the plant treated with AK17 has a lower level of H_2O_2 , which indicates that AK17 treatment results in scavenging or preventing the higher accumulation of ROS during drought stress. Similar results were observed by Batool et al. (2020), who found a

Figure 6. a) Semiquantitative RT-PCR analysis of P5CS transcript level in the leaves of cluster bean plant under drought stress; b) Semiquantitative RT-PCR analysis of BADH transcript level in the leaves of cluster bean plant under drought stress; c) Semiquantitative RT-PCR analysis of CAT transcript level in the leaves of cluster bean plant under drought stress.

Slika 6. a) Polkvantitativna analiza RT-PCR ravni transkripta P5CS v listih rastline fižola pod sušnim stresom; b) Polkvantitativna analiza RT-PCR ravni transkripta BADH v listih rastline fižola pod sušnim stresom; c) Polkvantitativna analiza RT-PCR ravni transkripta CAT v listih rastline fižola pod sušnim stresom.

significant decrease in the H_2O_2 content of the two varieties of potato under moderate and severe drought stress when treated with PGPR compared to the untreated control. So, together by lowering MDA content and H_2O_2 accumulation, the *Pseudomonas stutzeri* AK17 treatment develops an effective ROS detoxification system.

Antioxidant enzymes such as SOD, CAT, and APX play a very important role in detoxifying ROS along with non-enzymatic antioxidants such as phenols, flavonoids, etc. (Gowtham et al., 2022). The present study shows a significant increase in the phenol and flavonoid content in the AK17-treated plant compared to the control. While a complex pattern was observed for antioxidant enzyme activity, i.e., superoxide dismutase activity was higher at moderate drought stress (4th day) but decreased under severe stress. CAT and APX activity increase during drought stress, but it is lower in the AK17-treated plant as compared to the control. This pattern observed may be due to higher accumulation of osmolyte during severe drought

stress, due to which plants experience less accumulation of ROS to be detoxified by enzyme activity. A similar result was observed by Sandhya et al. (2010), which shows a lower antioxidant enzyme activity in the maize plant treated with various *Pseudomonas* spp. compared to the untreated control under drought stress conditions. Similarly, Tiwari et al (2016) found the reduction in the SOD and CAT enzyme activity in the chickpea (*Cicer arietinum* L.) plant treated with *Pseudomonas putida* under drought stress conditions as compared to the untreated control.

The study of gene expression is particularly significant as it links the biochemical observation with molecular regulation. In the present study, an upregulation of P5CS (involved in proline biosynthesis) and BADH (involved in glycine betaine biosynthesis) was observed in AK17-treated plants under drought stress. This is correlated with the higher accumulation of proline and glycine in the AK17-treated plant. Ghosh et al. (2017) observed an increase in the expression of the P5CS gene in the Arabidopsis

thaliana inoculated with *Pseudomonas putida* strain at 2 to 7 days of drought stress.

Upregulation was observed in CAT (involved in catalase synthesis) during the earlier drought stress period (4th day), but later during severe drought stress, its expression was downregulated in the treated plant as compared to the control. These results correlate with Tiwari et al. (2016) observation, where there was a 2.5-fold down-regulation in the expression of the CAT gene in chickpea (*Cicer arietinum* L.) plant treated with *Pseudomonas putida* under drought stress conditions, while the untreated control shows the up-regulation of this gene.

The observation in the present study shows that CAT is upregulated in the initial period of drought stress, but afterwards its expression decreases, which may suggest that *Pseudomonas stutzeri* AK17 enhances early responses, helps the plant to manage stress effectively, thus reducing the requirement of prolonged expression. This may reduce wastage of energy or prevent overactivation of antioxidant pathways, which can be expensive.

Conclusion

This study suggests that the inoculation of *Cyamopsis tetranogoloba* with *Pseudomonas stutzeri* AK17 helps in mitigating the various levels of drought stress by interacting with the physiological, biochemical and molecular mechanisms of the cluster bean plant. Inoculation with *Pseudomonas stutzeri* AK17 helped cluster bean to mitigate the osmotic stress at the advent of drought, which enabled it to grow and survive under severe drought stress. The expression

of three genes at different levels of drought stress corroborated our biochemical analysis. The ability of AK17 to enhance osmolytes accumulation, reduce ROS and membrane damage, activate the antioxidant defence system and regulate the expression of drought-responsive genes under controlled greenhouse conditions makes it a compelling option for bioinoculant development. This research also suggests that there was a crosstalk between different types of mechanisms adopted by the cluster bean plant to effectively mitigate the deleterious effects of drought. However, further studies under field conditions are required to confirm its effectiveness under natural agricultural conditions.

Author Contributions

Conceptualization, R.J. and M.S.; methodology, R.J.; investigation, R.J.; formal analysis, T.V., S.M. and T.P.; data curation, R.J.; writing-original draft preparation R.J.; writing-review and editing, M.S., D.A., and R.S.; supervision, M.S.; project administration, M.S. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

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Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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Original Research

Erigeron sumatrensis (Asteraceae): a new alien species to the flora of Kosovo

Bujar Kadriaj¹, Naim Berisha^{1*}

Abstract

Erigeron sumatrensis is a South American annual weed that has become widely established outside its native range, including much of Europe and the Balkan Peninsula. Despite its regional distribution, the species had not previously been confirmed for the flora of Kosovo. This study documents the first verified record of *E. sumatrensis* in Kosovo and provides initial data on its distribution and habitat preferences. Field surveys conducted in 2025 across a broad range of habitats recorded the species at least 29 localities, primarily along roadsides and highways, urban margins, construction sites, waste ground, abandoned fields and disturbed agricultural areas. Additional occurrences along riverbanks and alluvial corridors indicate an ability to extend beyond strictly anthropogenic habitats. Species identification was based on diagnostic morphological characters and comparison with regional floras, with voucher specimens deposited in the Herbarium of the University of Prishtina (UPH). The widespread occurrence of *E. sumatrensis* suggests that the species is already well established in Kosovo. Given its known invasive behaviour and its strong association with transport corridors and disturbed environments, early monitoring and management measures are recommended to limit further spread and potential ecological and agricultural impacts.

Keywords

Alien flora; Compositae; Biodiversity; SE Europe

¹ Department of Biology, Faculty of Mathematics and Natural Sciences, University of Prishtina, Kosovo

* Corresponding author:

E-mail address: naim.berisha@uni-pr.edu

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Erigeron sumatrensis (Asteraceae): nova tuja vrsta v flori Kosova

Izvleček

Erigeron sumatrensis je južnoameriška enoletna plevelna rastlina, ki se je široko razširila zunaj svojega izvornega območja, vključno z večjim delom Evrope in Balkanskega polotoka. Kljub regionalni razširjenosti ta vrsta doslej ni bila potrjena v flori Kosova. Ta študija dokumentira prvi potrjen zapis *E. sumatrensis* na Kosovu in zagotavlja začetne podatke o njegovi razširjenosti in preferencah glede habitata. Terenske raziskave, izvedene leta 2025 na širokem spektru habitatov, so zabeležile vrsto na vsaj 29 lokacijah, predvsem ob cestah in avtocestah, na obrobju mest, gradbiščih, zapuščenih zemljiščih, opuščenih poljih in motenih kmetijskih območjih. Dodatni pojavi ob rečnih bregovih in aluvialnih koridorjih kažejo na sposobnost širjenja tudi izven strogo antropogenih habitatov. Identifikacija vrste je temeljila na diagnostičnih morfoloških značilnostih in primerjavi z regionalno floro, z vzorčnimi primerkami, deponiranimi v herbariumu Univerze v Prištini (UPH). Široka razširjenost *E. sumatrensis* kaže, da je vrsta že dobro uveljavljena na Kosovu. Glede na njeno znano invazivno vedenje in močno povezanost s prometnimi koridorji in motenimi okolji se priporočajo zgodnji ukrepi spremljanja in upravljanja, da se omeji nadaljnje širjenje in potencialni ekološki in kmetijski vplivi.

Ključne besede

Tujska flora; Compositae; Biotska raznovrstnost; Jugovzhodna Evropa

Introduction

Biological invasions represent one of the main drivers of global biodiversity change and have intensified significantly in recent decades. Alien plant taxa can alter ecosystem functioning, reduce native biodiversity, disrupt nutrient cycling and cause substantial agricultural and economic losses, especially in human-modified landscapes (Vilà et al., 2011; Pyšek et al., 2012; 2020; Seebens et al., 2021). Europe has seen a continuous increase in the arrival and establishment of invasive alien plants, with many species expanding rapidly due to climate change, land-use transformation and intensifying transport networks (Essl et al., 2011; Riera et al., 2021).

Within this broader context, the Balkan Peninsula is regarded as a region of high ecological sensitivity to biological invasions due to its heterogeneous landscapes, intensively used agricultural areas and climatic gradients that favour the establishment of disturbance-adapted alien taxa (Lambdon et al., 2008; Šilc et al., 2012). Several alien plant species have already become naturalised or invasive across the region (Kalusová et al., 2024), raising concerns about their ecological and socio-economic impacts.

The genus *Erigeron* L. (Asteraceae), comprising more than 458 accepted species worldwide (POWO, 2025),

includes several globally invasive taxa. Among these, *Erigeron sumatrensis* Retz. (syn. *Conyza sumatrensis*) - Sumatran fleabane has become one of the most successful invaders in tropical, subtropical and increasingly temperate regions (Galkina & Vinogradova, 2020). Native to South America, the species has invaded Europe, North America, Australasia, Asia, and Africa, establishing particularly dense populations across roadsides, croplands, wastelands, and other disturbed habitats (Rasool et al., 2016; Cheng et al., 2025). The invasion success of *E. sumatrensis* is attributed to high fecundity, efficient wind dispersal, extended germination periods, rapid growth and high tolerance of environmental variability (Hao et al., 2009; Bellache et al., 2022). In agricultural systems, the species is a highly invasive weed that competes with crops such as soybean, cotton, and cereals, causing significant yield losses (Wang et al., 2018; Bellache et al., 2022; Lorenzetti et al., 2025). Effective management has become increasingly challenging because the species has developed resistance to multiple herbicides, including glyphosate, paraquat, diquat, and ALS inhibitors, across several continents (Florentine et al., 2021; Heap, 2025).

In Kosovo, 21 invasive alien plant species have been documented to date (Kadriaj et al., 2023; Kadriaj, 2024), with two additional alien species recently recorded (Millaku et al., 2024). Although this number appears comparatively

low, it most likely reflects the still-limited systematic assessment and monitoring of alien flora in the country rather than the actual extent of biological invasions. The genus *Erigeron* is represented by two invasive alien species: *E. canadensis* (syn. *Conyza canadensis*) and *E. annuus*, but no verified records of *E. sumatrensis* (syn. *Conyza sumatrensis*; *Conyza albida*) existed until now. Given its invasive behaviour elsewhere and its potential for rapid spread once introduced, documenting its presence is crucial for early detection and management.

The aim of this study is to report the first confirmed occurrence of *E. sumatrensis* in Kosovo, describe its habitat characteristics and provide initial field observations that form a baseline for future monitoring and management of invasive alien species in the region.

Materials and Methods

Field surveys to detect the presence of *Erigeron sumatrensis* Retz. in Kosovo were conducted between spring and late autumn of 2025 across a wide range of habitats, including lowland agricultural areas, urban and peri-urban zones, roadside corridors and hilly to sub-montane environments (Figure 2, 1–C). Survey sites were selected based on known disturbance gradients, where invasive alien plant species typically establish and spread. For each locality where the species was observed, coordinates and altitude were recorded. When populations were encountered, representative individuals were photographed in situ and subsequently sampled. Collected material was pressed, dried, mounted, and deposited in the Herbarium of the Faculty of Mathematics and Natural Sciences, University of Prishtina (Herbarium acronym: UPH).

Specimens were identified using standard European floras and regional taxonomic keys for the genus *Erigeron*. Diagnostic characters were compared with descriptions in authoritative works, including Flora of Croatia (Nikolić, 2020) and regional floras. Particular attention was paid to characters distinguishing *E. sumatrensis* from the morphologically similar species *E. canadensis* and *E. bonariensis*, such as leaf morphology, capitulum structure, pappus length and stem indumentum (Figure 1 – A, B). The most reliable characters distinguishing *E. sumatrensis* from the morphologically similar *E. bonariensis* and *E. canadensis* are the architecture of the synflorescence, relative length of peduncles, involucrel indumentum and colouration,

capitulum width and ligule conspicuousness (Table 1), as derived from critical comparison of the examined material with relevant taxonomic literature (Marshall, 1973; Tutin et al., 1976; Davis et al., 1988; Vladimirov et al., 2016; Nesom, 2018). All verified records were compiled with their geographic coordinates. Spatial data were processed and visualised to produce a distribution map showing confirmed occurrences of *E. sumatrensis* in Kosovo.

Results and Discussion

Erigeron sumatrensis Retz. (Asteraceae) (Figure 1) is a rapidly spreading annual plant native to South America that arrived in Europe in the late 19th century, with the earliest confirmed record from 1875 in France (Pruski & Sancho, 2006). Its expansion accelerated during the 20th century, reflecting the broader continental trend of increasing alien plant introductions linked to globalisation, land-use change and intensifying propagule pressure (Pyšek et al., 2009; Chytrý et al., 2009). Today, *E. sumatrensis* is established in all Balkan countries, with published records from Albania (Baltisberger & Lippert, 1987), North Macedonia (Vladimirov et al., 2016), Serbia (Vrbničanin et al., 2004), Bosnia and Herzegovina (Maslo & Šarić, 2020), Croatia (Čarni, 1996; Milović, 2004), Bulgaria (Vladimirov, 2009; Vladimirov & Petrova, 2023), Greece (Baliouisis, 2014), Montenegro (Stešević & Petrović, 2010; Stesević et al., 2014), Slovenia (Čarni, 1996; Poldini & Kaligarić, 2000), Romania (Anastasiu & Memedemin, 2012; Sîrbu et al., 2023), and European Turkey (Davis et al., 1988). Despite its widespread regional presence, no verified occurrence had previously been documented for Kosovo, making the present findings the first confirmed national record.

Our field surveys conducted throughout 2025 indicate that *E. sumatrensis* is already widely distributed in Kosovo, occurring in at least 29 localities ranging from lowland agricultural zones to hilly-submontane belts (Figure 2). These records likely represent only a fraction of its actual range, as the species was frequently encountered opportunistically outside targeted sampling plots. The most common habitats are roadsides (Figure 1–C), urban edges, construction sites, waste grounds, abandoned fields, and disturbed agricultural soils. These patterns are fully consistent with European-scale assessments showing that ruderal, arable, urban, and traffic-associated habitats exhibit the highest levels of alien plant invasion (Chytrý et

Figure 1. *Erigeron sumatrensis* Retz. (Asteraceae). A. Capitula at fruiting stage showing pappus-bearing achenes; B. Leafy stem with characteristic narrow, pubescent leaves; C. Typical habitat in Kosovo, with dense populations established along highway embankments. Photos by: Naim Berisha (A, B), Bujar Kadriaj (C).

Slika 1. *Erigeron sumatrensis* Retz. (Asteraceae). A. Cvetna glavica v fazi plodovanja, ki kaže plodove s perjem; B. Listnato steblo z značilnimi ozkimi, dlakavimi listi; C. Tipično življenjsko okolje v Kosovu, z gosto populacijo ob avtocestnih nasipih. Fotografije: Naim Berisha (A, B), Bujar Kadriaj (C).

al., 2009). High propagule supply, recurrent disturbance, and nutrient enrichment make these habitats ideal sites for initial establishment.

Beyond anthropogenic environments, *E. sumatrensis* was also found in semi-natural habitats, notably along riverbanks and gravelly alluvial corridors. Riparian zones are recognised as among the most vulnerable natural ecosystems to alien plant invasion due to continuous disturbance, high nutrient loads and effective hydrochorous transport,

with watercourses acting as efficient vectors for the downstream dispersal of propagules (Zelnik, 2012; Chytrý et al., 2009). The occurrence of *E. sumatrensis* in such habitats in Kosovo illustrates its capacity to move beyond strictly human-modified zones, indicating an early stage of naturalisation within riverine ecosystems. In nearly all localities, the species co-occurred with *Erigeron canadensis*, another well-established neophyte, suggesting similar ecological niches and dispersal pathways.

Figure 2. Distribution of recorded localities of *Erigeron sumatrensis* Retz. in Kosovo. Red circles indicate sampling sites

Slika 2. Porazdelitev zabeleženih lokalitet *Erigeron sumatrensis* Retz. na Kosovu. Rdeči krogi označujejo mesta vzorčenja.

Patterns observed in Kosovo also reflect broader land-use and biogeographical gradients. According to the recent biogeographical regionalisation of Kosovo (Berisha et al., 2025), the species is primarily concentrated in the Continental regions, where urbanisation, road infrastructure and agricultural activity are most pronounced. These areas exhibit the highest propagule pressure, reinforcing the strong link between human activity and early invasion dynamics. Occasional occurrences in the foothills of the montane region indicate the possibility of future upward expansion along valleys and river systems, a pathway well documented for other invasive neophytes in Europe (Pattison et al., 2016). However, given its predominantly sub-Mediterranean to warm-temperate ecological affinity,

upward expansion into higher montane zones may be constrained by climatic conditions, particularly lower temperatures and shorter growing seasons.

Dispersal pathways in Kosovo align with general invasion patterns observed elsewhere in Europe, where wind dispersal enables background spread, while secondary, often anthropogenic, vectors play a crucial role in accelerating range expansion (Higgins & Richardson, 1996). In Kosovo, these vectors likely include vehicle-induced air turbulence, roadside management, and the transport of soil, gravel, and construction materials. River corridors serve as additional conduits, particularly during flood events, which transport diaspores downstream into newly disturbed substrates (Zajac et al., 2011).

Tabela 1. Diagnostic morphological characters distinguishing *Erigeron sumatrensis*, *E. bonariensis*, and *E. canadensis*.Table 1. Diagnostične morfološke značilnosti, ki razlikujejo *Erigeron sumatrensis*, *E. bonariensis* in *E. canadensis*.

Character	<i>E. sumatrensis</i>	<i>E. bonariensis</i>	<i>E. canadensis</i>
Plant height	50–180 (–200) cm	Up to 250 cm	10–150 cm
Stem colour	Greyish-green	Grey-green	Green
Stem indumentum	Densely pubescent with two types of eglandular hairs: short appressed hairs & scattered longer patent hairs	Densely hirsute, often with longer spreading hairs	Sparsely patent-hirsute to nearly glabrous
Leaf shape	Lanceolate to narrowly lanceolate or elliptic-lanceolate; remotely dentate	Linear to linear-oblongate	Lower oblanceolate and petiolate (often deciduous); upper linear
Upper leaves	Sessile, densely pubescent	Narrow, densely hairy	Linear, less hairy
Synflorescence outline	Rhombic to narrowly pyramidal	Broadly pyramidal to funnel-shaped	Narrow, elongated panicle with a dominant central axis
Side branches of synflorescence	Not overtopping the central axis	Usually overtopping the central axis	Strictly shorter than the central axis
Involucre length	4–5 mm	4–6 mm	3–4 mm
Involucral bracts	Densely pubescent, greyish-green, often reddish at apex	Densely hirsute, often purple-tipped	Glabrous or nearly so
Pappus length & colour	4–5 mm, Pale brownish	4–6 mm, Dirty white	3–4 mm, Whitish
Capitulum width	3–6 mm	Often 1 cm or more	Less than 1 cm
Ligules	Shorter than 0.5 mm, inconspicuous	Up to 0.5 mm	0.5–1 mm, Whitish and conspicuous

Although impacts have not yet been quantified for Kosovo, studies from other regions demonstrate significant ecological consequences of *E. sumatrensis* invasion, including suppression of native early-successional flora, alteration of competitive dynamics and interference with agricultural productivity (Hao et al., 2009; Liendo et al., 2021). In Slovenia, Zelnik (2012) documented substantial biodiversity reduction in invaded riparian habitats, a pattern likely to be mirrored where *E. sumatrensis* forms dense stands.

Overall, our results indicate that *E. sumatrensis* is already spreading rapidly across Kosovo. Its affinity for disturbed, nutrient-rich and traffic-associated habitats, combined with its capacity to enter semi-natural riverine systems, positions it as a potentially aggressive invader with the ability to expand further. Given the accelerating rate of alien plant introductions in southeastern Europe (Pyšek et al., 2009) and the high ecological sensitivity of river corridors and agricultural systems, early monitoring and targeted management will be essential to prevent further spread and potential ecological impacts.

This study documents the first confirmed occurrence of *Erigeron sumatrensis* in Kosovo and shows that the species

is already widespread across various habitat types. Its rapid expansion, effective dispersal mechanisms, and ecological flexibility highlight the urgent need for early detection, long-term monitoring, and coordinated management strategies. As Kosovo continues to urbanise and experiences increased movement of goods, soil and construction materials, the risk of further spread remains high. Integrating this species into national invasive plant monitoring frameworks is therefore essential to mitigate potential ecological and agricultural impacts.

Author Contributions

Conceptualization: NB, Methodology: NB, BK, Investigation (fieldwork): NB, BK, Data curation: BK, Formal analysis: BK, Resources (herbarium material): NB, Writing – original draft: BK, Writing – review & editing: NB, BK, Visualization: BK, Supervision: NB.

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Data Availability

The research data is available on Zenodo (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18750518>).

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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Review

Pregled monitoringov biodiverzitete kmetijske krajine v Sloveniji in primerjava z izbranimi primeri iz tujine

Irena Bertonselj^{1*}

Povzetek

Kmetijstvo predstavlja enega glavnih pritiskov na biodiverzitetu v Evropi, tako zaradi intenzifikacije rabe kot tudi zaradi opuščanja tradicionalnih kmetijskih praks. Za učinkovito upravljanje in vrednotenje naravovarstvenih ukrepov je nujen zanesljiv in dolgoročen monitoring biodiverzitete, ki temelji na kombinaciji več kazalnikov na različnih biotskih in prostorskih nivojih. Prispevek podaja celovit pregled obstoječih mednarodnih in nacionalnih monitoringov biodiverzitete v slovenski kmetijski krajini ter jih primerja s tremi uveljavljenimi dolgoročnimi shemami iz Norveške, Francije in Švice. Analiza kaže, da so v Sloveniji dobro razviti monitoringi ptic in metuljev, predvsem za vrste v interesu Evropske unije, medtem ko so splošno razširjene vrste, rastlinske vrste, habitatni tipi, oprashaevalci in talni organizmi še vedno pomanjkljivo pokriti. Mednarodne sheme, kot so LUCAS, EMBAL, eBMS in PECBMS, ponujajo metodološko usklajeno in primerljivo izhodišče, ki bi ga bilo mogoče učinkoviteje izkoristiti tudi na nacionalni ravni. Tuji primeri poudarjajo pomen naključnega izbora vzorčnih mest, rednega spremljanja pogostih in srednje pogostih vrst ter povezovanja biotskih kazalnikov z rabo tal, krajinskimi elementi in kmetijskimi praksami. V razpravi so podana priporočila za nadgradnjo obstoječih monitoringov v Sloveniji, vključno z uporabo LUCAS in EMBAL vzorčnih točk, razširitvijo monitoringa metuljev in oprashaevalcev, vzpostavitev monitoringa rastlin in habitatnih tipov, biodiverzitete tal ter boljšim spremljanjem učinkov kmetijsko-okoljskih ukrepov Skupne kmetijske politike (SKP). Tak celostni pristop bi prispeval k boljšemu upravljanju, izpolnjevanju zahtev evropske zakonodaje in učinkovitejšemu varstvu biodiverzitete v kmetijski krajini.

Ključne besede

Kazalniki biodiverzitete, mednarodne monitoring sheme, skupna kmetijska politika, kmetijsko-okoljsko-podnebni ukrepi

1 Kmetijski inštitut Slovenije, Hacquetova ulica 17, SI-1000 Ljubljana

* Corresponding author:

E-mail address: irena.bertoncelj@kis.si

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Overview of biodiversity monitoring in agricultural landscapes of Slovenia and comparison with selected practices from abroad

Abstract

Agriculture is one of the main pressures on biodiversity in Europe, driven both by land-use intensification and the abandonment of traditional farming practices. Effective management and evaluation of conservation measures require robust, long-term biodiversity monitoring based on a combination of indicators across multiple biological and spatial levels. This paper provides a comprehensive review of existing international and national biodiversity monitoring schemes in the Slovenian agricultural landscape and compares them with three long-established programmes from Norway, France, and Switzerland. The analysis shows that bird and butterfly monitoring in Slovenia is relatively well developed, particularly for species of European conservation concern, whereas widespread common species, plant habitat types, pollinators, and soil organisms remain poorly covered. International schemes such as LUCAS, EMBAL, eBMS, and PECBMS offer harmonised and comparable methodological frameworks that could be more effectively utilised at the national level. The foreign case studies highlight the importance of random site selection, regular monitoring of common species, and the integration of indicators such as land use, landscape elements, and farming practices. The discussion provides recommendations for upgrading biodiversity monitoring in Slovenia, including the use of LUCAS and EMBAL sampling sites, expansion of butterfly and pollinator monitoring, establishment of systematic monitoring of plant species, habitat types and soil biodiversity, and improved assessment of Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) agri-environmental measure effectiveness. Such an integrated approach would better support evidence-based decision-making, fulfil European policy requirements, and enhance biodiversity conservation in agricultural landscapes.

Keywords

Biodiversity indicators, international monitoring schemes, Common agricultural policy, agri-environment schemes

Uvod

Poročilo o stanju narave v EU za leto 2020 navaja kmetijstvo kot najpogostejši pritisk na habitate in vrste oziroma biodiverzitet (European Environment Agency, 2020). Izgubo biodiverzitet v kmetijski krajini povzročata dva nasprotna si pojava in sicer na eni strani intenzifikacija kmetijstva, ki ogroža biodiverzitet zaradi povečane uporabe agrokemikalij in pretvorbe kompleksnih naravnih ekosistemov v poenostavljene homogene ekosisteme (Stoate et al., 2009; Tschardtke et al., 2012). Po drugi strani pa opuščanje rabe travšč vodi v njihovo zaraščanje in posledično zmanjšanje števila rastlinskih vrst (Elliott et al., 2023; Kaligarič & Ivajnsič, 2014).

Za zagotavljanje povratne informacije upravljavcem o vplivih njihovih posegov v naravno okolje in posledicah za biodiverzitet je nujno potreben monitoring biodiverzitet,

ki omogoči oceno sprememb v času in v prostoru (Niemelä, 2000). Na splošno je monitoring definiran kot »občasni (redni ali neredni) nadzor, ki se izvaja z namenom ugotovitve obsega skladnosti z vnaprej določenim standardom ali stopnjo odstopanja od pričakovane norme« (Hellawell, 1991). Biodiverzitet pa je v Konvenciji o biološki raznovrstnosti definirana kot »raznolikost živih organizmov iz vseh virov, ki vključuje med drugim kopenske, morske in druge vodne ekosisteme ter ekološke komplekse, katerih del so; to vključuje raznovrstnost znotraj samih vrst, med vrstami in raznovrstnost ekosistemov«.

Noss (1990) je za spremljanje biodiverzitet predlagal štiri glavne nivoje: nivo pokrajine, nivo združbe ali ekosistema, nivo vrste ali populacije in genetski nivo znotraj vrste. Splošno sprejeto vodilo je, da za monitoring biodiverzitet potrebujemo več komplementarnih kazalnikov na različnih nivojih (De Morais et al., 2018; Jones et al.,

2011; Noss, 1990). Predlagani so bili že številni kazalniki, od katerih je najpogosteje uporabljena vrstna pestrost izbranih skupin organizmov (Sizemore, 2015), ki naj bi odražala vrstno pestrost ostalih skupin organizmov in stanje ekosistema (McGeoch, 1998). V nadaljevanju bom za te skupine uporabljala izraz indikatorski taksoni. Več avtorjev je že predlagalo sezname lastnosti, ki naj bi jih indikatorski taksoni imeli. Na primer Monks et al. (2013) so predlagali naslednje lastnosti: dobro poznana biologija, relativno številčni taksoni, enostavno vzorčenje, identifikacija in spremljanje na terenu, jasno merljiva številčnost, taksoni, prisotni v ekosistemu že pred preučevano spremembo, na okoljske spremembe relativno visoko občutljivi taksoni ter geografsko široko razširjeni taksoni.

Za primerjavo različnih indikatorskih taksonov so Billeter et al. (2007) opravili obširno raziskavo, v kateri so v 25 različnih evropskih pokrajinah primerjali odzive višjih rastlin, ptic, čebel (Apoidea), raznokrilcev (Heteroptera), hroščev krešičev (Carabidae), muh trepetavk (Syrphidae) in pajkov (Araneae) na kmetijske prakse. Zaključili so, da nobeden od preučevanih indikatorskih taksonov ni mogel predvideti odzivov vseh ostalih in zato nobeden od njih ne more biti samostojen kazalnik. V preglednem članku so Eglinton et al. (2012) ugotovili, da je vrstna pestrost ptic, kot enega najpogosteje preučevanih indikatorskih taksonov, samo šibko odražala vrstno pestrost drugih skupin organizmov, delno pa je bilo to odvisno tudi od tipa preučevanega habitata. Pri pregledu obstoječih meta analiz Tälle et al. (2023) niso našli zanesljive indikatorske vrednosti za krovne, ključne in karizmatične vrste. Najboljše rezultate je pokazala raba raznovrstnosti višjih taksonov (npr. rodov, družin) kot pokazateljev raznovrstnosti nižjih taksonov (vrst) (De Oliveira et al., 2020; Tälle et al., 2023).

Kot je predlagal že Noss (1990), pa so v rabi tudi številni drugi kazalniki na različnih nivojih kot na primer: raba tal, stanje evropsko pomembnih habitatnih tipov, površina zavarovanih območij in stopnja ekološke povezljivosti v pokrajini (Burkmar, 2017; Taylor et al., 2024). V preglednem članku so Tälle et al. (2023) zaključili, da poleg nujnosti uporabe več indikatorskih taksonov priporočajo tudi kombinacijo le-teh s kazalniki na drugih nivojih.

V tem prispevku je pregled obstoječih mednarodnih in nacionalnih monitoringov biodiverzitete v slovenski kmetijski krajini in trije primeri dolgoročnih monitoringov biodiverzitete v evropskih državah. V razpravi so podana priporočila za razširitev ali nadgradnjo obstoječih monitoringov na območju Slovenije.

Pregled monitoringov biodiverzitete v kmetijski krajini

Mednarodni monitoringi biodiverzitete v slovenski kmetijski krajini

V slovenski kmetijski krajini poteka pet mednarodnih shem monitoringa biodiverzitete na različnih nivojih. Projekt **LUCAS (Land Use and Coverage Area Frame Survey)** je namenjen spremljanju rabe tal. Vodi ga Statistični urad EU v sodelovanju z Generalnim direktoratom za kmetijstvo in razvoj podeželja in poteka od leta 2006 na več kot 250.000 popisnih točkah v vseh državah članicah EU. Popis rabe tal poteka z obiski točk na terenu in fotointerpretacijo ortofoto posnetkov okvirno na tri leta (Orgiazzi et al., 2018). Na podzorcju terenskih točk izvajalci podrobneje popišejo ekološke in upravljavske kazalnike travšč (Oppermann, 2018). Leta 2009 so uvedli dodaten »LUCAS Soil modul«, pri katerem na 10 % terenskih točk odvzamejo vzorec tal za določitev vrednosti različnih parametrov v tleh. Od leta 2018 naprej na 1000 vzorčnih točkah spremljajo tudi biodiverzitetu talnih organizmov s pomočjo analiz okoljske DNA (Orgiazzi et al., 2018). V Sloveniji je bil LUCAS popis izpeljan v letih 2009, 2012, 2015, 2018 in 2022, poročila pa so izdelana na EU ravni za popisa iz leta 2009 in 2015 (European Commission. Directorate General for the Environment., 2010; European Commission. Joint Research Centre., 2020).

Evropska komisija je vzpostavila tudi **EMBAL (European Monitoring of Biodiversity in Agricultural Landscapes)**, katerega cilj je spremljanje stanja biodiverzitete v vseh članicah EU. Po uspešno izvedeni pilotni študiji leta 2020 so v letih 2022 in 2023 EMBAL prvič izvedli v vseh 27 državah članicah EU na skupno 3000 kvadratov velikosti 500m x 500m (Kleinewillinghofer et al., 2024). EMBAL se osredotoča na spremljanje potenciala kmetijskih površin za opraševalce, omogoča pa tudi spremljanje rabe tal, krajinskih elementov in habitatnih tipov (EMBAL, 2021). Na njivah in travščih metoda EMBAL določa tudi transektni popis pokrovnosti indikatorskih rastlinskih taksonov, ki so poenoteni za vse države, beleženje števila barv cvetov, število vrst cvetočih rastlin ter EUNIS habitatni tip. (EMBAL, 2021). Izbor kvadratov je potekal po principu naključnega vzorčenja z vhodnimi informacijami o biogeografski regiji, nadmorski višini in državi kvadrata. Število izbranih kvadratov za posamezno državo in biogeografsko regijo je

odsev površine kmetijskih zemljišč in hkrati zadostuje za oceno stanja biodiverzitete na nivoju posamezne države. Kot izhodišče za izbor kvadratov so uporabili 2 km x 2 km mrežo »LUCAS Master grid« in tako prostorsko uskladili oba monitoringa (Kleinewillinghofer et al., 2024). V prvem popisu Slovenije so bili v EMBAL vključeni 103 kvadrati, znotraj katerih je bilo po EMBAL metodi pokrovnosti indikatorskih rastlinskih taksonov popisanih 6-9 transektov. Preliminarni rezultati prvega EMBAL popisa 2022/2023 so bili javno predstavljeni septembra 2025, končno poročilo pa še ni na voljo.

Evropski monitoring dnevnih metuljev **eBMS (EU Butterfly Monitoring Scheme)** sta zasnovali organizaciji Ohranjanje metuljev Evrope (Butterfly Conservation Europe) in Center za ekologijo in hidrologijo iz Velike Britanije (Centre for Ecology and Hydrology) s prvimi popisi že leta 1976 v Veliki Britaniji (Van Swaay et al., 2008, 2022). Cilj je spremljanje trendov izbranih vrst travniških metuljev za izračun indeksa travniških vrst dnevnih metuljev Evrope. Popisi potekajo po metodi transeкта, kjer se štejejo vse prisotne vrste vzdolž 0,5 do 3 km dolgega transeкта (Van Swaay et al., 2022). V Sloveniji popis poteka od leta 2007 vsako leto na 10 transektih, razporejenih po celi državi. Monitoring vodi Društvo za proučevanje in ohranjanje metuljev Slovenije na prostovoljni ravni. Rezultate popisov zbirajo v skupnem portalu in približno vsako drugo leto izdelajo poročilo na EU ravni (Van Swaay et al., 2022).

Na nivoju EU je bil izveden poskusni monitoring oprasovalcev **EUPoMS (Pollinator species monitoring scheme)**, v katerega so bili vključeni metulji, čebele in muhe trepetavke. Ekspertna skupina STING (Science and Technology for pollinating insects) je izdelala metodološke smernice (European Commission. Joint Research Centre., 2021), ki so jih partnerji v okviru projekta SPRING (Strengthening Pollinator Recovery through Indicators and Monitoring) leta 2023 pilotno preizkusili v več državah članicah EU, tudi v Sloveniji (Settele et al., 2024). Po povratnih informacijah iz terenskih vzorčenj je ekspertna skupina STING metodološke smernice dopolnila (European Commission. Joint Research Centre., 2024) in priporočila izvajanje osnovne sheme, z možnostjo razširitve z dopolnilnimi moduli. Osnovna shema predvideva i) popis divjih čebel, muh trepetavk in dnevnih metuljev na 500 m dolgih transektih s časovno omejitvijo, ii) popis nočnih metuljev s standardiziranimi nočnimi pastmi ter iii) popis redkih in ogroženih vrst z uporabo vrstno specifičnih metod (European Commission. Joint Research Centre., 2024).

Informacij o nadaljevanju izvajanja EUPoMS monitoringa na nivoju EU trenutno ni na voljo.

Vseevropski monitoring pogostih vrst ptic **PECBMS (PanEuropean common Bird monitoring scheme)** vključuje tudi ptice kmetijske krajine. Začel se je leta 2002, vzpostavila pa sta ga Evropski svet za popis ptic (European Bird Census Council) in mednarodna organizacija BirdLife International. Cilj je centralno zbirati podatke iz različnih nacionalnih monitoringov za izračun skupnega evropskega indeksa pogostih vrst ptic, ki je sestavljen iz indeksa pogostih ptic kmetijske krajine (Farmland bird index, FBI), indeksa pogostih ptic gozda in indeksa drugih pogostih ptic. Metodologija popisa v Sloveniji je bila strokovno osnovana že leta 2006 (Denac et al., 2006). V Sloveniji ga od leta 2008 izvaja Društvo za opazovanje in preučevanje ptic Slovenije (DOPPS) za določitev vrednosti slovenskega indeksa ptic kmetijske krajine. Podatke pošiljajo v centralno evidenco za izračun indeksa na nivoju Evrope (PECBMS, 2024).

Nacionalni monitoringi biodiverzitete kmetijske krajine v Sloveniji

Na nivoju države potekajo monitoringi nekaterih vrst, ki jih določa 11. člen Direktive o habitatih ter 4. in 12. člen Direktive o pticah. Osredotočajo se na vrste v interesu skupnosti iz prilog Direktive o habitatih, rezultati pa služijo za spremljanja stanja in poročanja po 17. členu te direktive. Nekatere od vključenih skupin so tudi prebivalke kmetijske krajine (npr. metulji, ptice kmetijske krajine). Metoda monitoringa in način izbora vzorčnih mest je za vsako skupino oz. vrsto drugačen.

Nacionalni monitoring izbranih ciljnih vrst metuljev vodi Center za kartografijo favne in flore (CKFF) v sodelovanju s partnerji. Poteka vsako leto od leta 2008, pri čemer spremljajo velikost izbranih populacij na območju sklenjene razširjenosti ter v območjih robnih in izoliranih populacij (Zakšek et al., 2023). V monitoring so vključene vrste iz prilog II in IV Direktive o habitatih, z monitoringom pa zbirajo podatke o najbolj ogroženih populacijah, njihovi populacijski dinamiki in stanju habitatov. Monitoring ni vezan na Natura 2000 območja, ampak poteka tudi izven njih, tam kjer se te vrste pojavljajo.

V okviru **monitoringa populacij izbranih ciljnih vrst ptic na območjih Natura 2000** DOPPS spremlja tudi nekatere vrste kmetijske krajine, kjer so metode prilagojene posamezni vrsti (od popisa pojočih samcev pri koscu do štetja gnezdečih parov pri beli štorčliji). Popisi potekajo od leta

2004 in so prostorsko omejeni na Natura 2000 območja (Denac et al., 2023).

Poleg izbranih ciljnih vrst ptic pa poteka tudi **monitoring splošno razširjenih vrst ptic**, v okviru katerega DOPPS spremlja ptice kmetijske krajine. Za izračun slovenskega indeksa ptic kmetijske krajine uporabijo terenske podatke, pridobljene po metodi vseevropske sheme PECBMS, ki je opisana v prejšnjem poglavju. V zadnjem poročilu so izvajalci podali oceno indeksa med leti 2008-2023 za 29 indikatorskih vrst na podlagi 152 popisanih transektov (Kmecl et al., 2023).

Monitoring divjih opravevalcev so raziskovalci Nacionalnega inštituta za biologijo (NIB) s partnerji projekta zasnovali in preizkusili v okviru Ciljnega raziskovalnega projekta CRP V1-1938 (Zasnova metodologije monitoringa divjih opravevalcev v Sloveniji) med leti 2019-2023 (Bevk et al., 2023). Projekt se je osredotočal na monitoring divjih čebel in sicer na oceno stanja populacij ter na zasnovo metodologije njihovega monitoringa. Uporabili so metodologijo mednarodnega projekta SPRING (Settele et al., 2024) in monitoring leta 2023 testno izvedli na izbranih območjih po Sloveniji, ki so se razlikovala v rabi prostora in niso bila omejena na Natura 2000 območja (Bevk et al., 2023). Po letu 2023 monitoring ni bil ponovljen in reden monitoring ni bil vzpostavljen.

Trije primeri nacionalnih monitoringov biodiverzitete kmetijske krajine v Evropi

Za primerjavo z monitoringi v tujini sem izbrala tri najdalj trajajoče sheme iz Norveške, Francije in Švice, za katere je dostopna literatura v angleščini. Pri opisih sem se osredotočila na informacije o namenu, spremljanih kazalnikih, izboru in številu vzorčnih mest, časovnem razponu in viru financiranja.

1. Norverški monitoring program za kmetijsko krajino (3Q program)

Monitoring 3Q poteka že od leta 1998 in vključuje štiri sklope: prostorska oblikovanost krajine, biodiverziteta, kulturna dediščina in dostopnost (Stokstad & Fjellstad, 2019). Cilj tega monitoringa kmetijske krajine je učinkovito usmerjanje kmetijskih in okoljskih politik. Na podlagi ortofoto posnetkov pridobijo natančen popis rabe tal, ki vključuje približno 100 kategorij rabe. Poleg tega beležijo tudi vse naravne in kulturne elemente krajine, ki so ožji od 2 m oz. objekte, velike med 4 m² in 100 m². Ker nekatere

podrobnosti niso razvidne iz posnetkov, vsako leto izvedejo tudi terenski popis 10 % kvadratov, pri katerem popišejo prisotnost ptic, višjih rastlin in kulturne dediščine (Stokstad & Fjellstad, 2019). Na teh točkah preverjajo zanesljivost popisov iz ortofoto posnetkov, ki je ostajala relativno konstantna čez čas, kljub spremembam v kvaliteti posnetkov.

Na začetku je 3Q temeljil na analizah ortofoto posnetkov 1474 vzorčnih kvadratov velikosti 1 km x 1 km. Zaradi premajhne količine sredstev so naključno izbrali 70 % teh vzorčnih kvadratov, ki so jih poimenovali »prioritetni«. Po prvih 10 letih so se odločili za prenovljen izbor kvadratov, kar je precej vplivalo na časovno zveznost podatkov (Stokstad & Fjellstad, 2019). Izbor kvadratov s terenskimi popisi pri prenovi niso spreminjali. Monitoring financirata norveški ministrstvi za okolje in za kmetijstvo. Temelji na petletnem ciklu, kjer vsako leto popišejo približno 20 % vseh kvadratov in tako so vsakih pet let popisani vsi kvadrati (Stokstad & Fjellstad, 2019).

2. Francoski monitoring netarčnih učinkov kmetijskih praks (500 ENI)

Kot del državnega načrta za zmanjšanje uporabe pesticidov (Ecophyto), francosko ministrstvo za kmetijstvo od leta 2012 financira program 500 ENI, da bi ocenili netarčne učinke kmetijskih praks vključno z netarčnimi učinki pesticidov (Andrade et al., 2021). Osredotočili so se na biodiverzitetno indikatorskih taksonov deževnikov, rastlin, hroščev in ptic, za katere spremljajo pogostost pojavljanja in številčnost osebkov. Rastline in hrošče vzorčijo na robovih kmetijskih zemljišč, ki jih obravnavajo kot pol-naravne ekosisteme, ki pa so močno izpostavljeni vplivom kmetijske pridelave (pesticidom, gnojilom itd.). Pri popisu rastlin morajo popisovalci prepoznati 100 indikatorskih vrst, ostale pa določijo do rodu ali družine. Popis 31 najpogostejših vrst ptic izvedejo dvakrat letno v sezoni gnezdenja. Zabeležijo vse ptice znotraj popisnega zemljišča in v 200 m okoliškem pasu med opravljanjem 10 minutnega audi-vizualnega transeкта v dolžini 150 m.

Popisovalci v okolici vsake popisne ploskve beležijo tudi sestavo, diverzitetno in razporeditev glavnih vrst pridelkov ter pol-naravnih krajinskih elementov, in sicer v treh koncentričnih krogih oddaljenosti od točke popisa (125, 250 in 500 m). Popisovalci opravijo tudi intervju z lastnikom popisnega zemljišča, ki traja med 1,5 in 4 ure, v katerem popišejo približno 80 spremenljivk o upravljanju: kolobar, obdelava tal, raba gnojil in fitofarmaceutskih sredstev, namakanje itd. Vsako leto vzorčijo tudi tla (pH, tekstura, organska snov).

Program 500 ENI poteka na 500 kmetijskih zemljiščih po celotni državi, tako da pokriva različne pedo-klimatske pogoje za kmetijstvo (Andrade et al., 2021). V analizo so vključene štiri glavne kmetijske rabe tal: njiva z enoletno kulturo (ozimno žito in koruza), vinograd, pridelava zelenjave. Poleg tega se vzorčna zemljišča delijo glede na pridelavo: ekološka pridelava (20 % zemljišč) in konvencionalna (80 % zemljišč).

3. Švicarski monitoring vrst in habitatov kmetijske krajine (ALL-EMA)

Monitoring ALL-EMA poteka od leta 2008 in je eden od treh monitoringov biodiverzitete v Švici, ki se osredotoča na »srednje pogoste« vrste in habitatne tipe (HT). S tem dopolnjuje monitoring najbolj pogostih vrst in HT (BDM – Biodiversity Monitoring Switzerland) ter monitoring redkih vrst in HT (WBS - Monitoring the Effectiveness of the Conservation of Swiss Habitats of National Importance). V okviru ALL-EMA beležijo: tip habitata, stanje habitata, krajinskih elementov, prisotnost tujerodnih rastlinskih vrst in popolni popis vegetacije na izbranih točkah (Riedel et al., 2018).

Izbor popisnih mest je potekal v več korakih, v katerih so od 509 ploskev površine 1 km² za BDM monitoring izločili 455 ploskev s kmetijskimi površinami, od katerih so jih 170 naključno izbrali z obtežitvijo glede na površino kmetijske krajine znotraj kvadrata. V naslednjem koraku so vsakega od izbranih kvadratov prekrili z mrežo 50m x 50m in popisne točke habitatov umestili na stičišča mreže. V povprečju 190 stičišč znotraj kvadrata pade na kmetijska zemljišča, tako da skupno opravijo 32000 popisov habitatov. Popis vegetacije opravijo na podzorcju 10 % teh habitatnih popisov - skupno 3230 popisov. Popis habitatnih tipov popisovalec opravi v radiju 10 m okrog točke popisa, popis krajinskih elementov pa opravi v radiju 200 m okrog točke popisa (Riedel et al., 2018). Vsako leto popišejo eno petino od 170 izbranih kvadratov (torej 34), ki so enakomerno porazdeljeni glede na podnebne značilnosti kvadratov. Tako so vsakih pet let popisani vsi kvadrati (Riedel et al., 2018).

Razprava in sklepi

Zaradi nezajezenelega upada biodiverzitete je njeno ohranjanje in izboljšanje del številnih zakonodajnih in strateških dokumentov kot so Zakon o ohranjanju narave, Konvencija o biološki raznovrstnosti, Strategija EU za biotsko raznovrstnost do leta 2030 ter Cilja 14 in 15 trajnostnega razvoja

Organizacije združenih narodov (Strategic Development Goals). Monitoring biodiverzitete po slovenski zakonodaji predvideva 108. člen Zakona o ohranjanju narave, po zakonodaji Evropske unije pa 11. člen Direktive o habitatih ter 4. in 12. člen Direktive o pticah. Uredba EU o obnovi narave uvaja obveznost rednega spremljanja ključnih kazalnikov, kot so indeks travniških metuljev, indeks splošno razširjenih ptic kmetijske krajine, stanje populacij opraševalcev, zaloga organskega ogljika v obdelovalnih mineralnih tleh ter delež kmetijskih zemljišč z visokoraznovrstnimi krajinskimi značilnostmi. Nedavno sprejeta Direktiva evropskega parlamenta in sveta o spremljanju in odpornosti tal pa predvideva tudi spremljanje biodiverzitete talnih organizmov.

Obstoječi nacionalni monitoringi ptic in metuljev se osredotočajo na vrste v interesu Evropske skupnosti iz prilog Direktive o pticah in Direktive o habitatih, rezultati pa služijo za spremljanja stanja in poročanja po 17. členu slednje. Te vrste so povečini ekološko gledano specialisti. Kot je razvidno iz treh predstavljenih monitoring shem iz tujine, vse vključujejo tudi splošno razširjene pogoste in srednje pogoste vrste (ekološko gledano generaliste) na naključno izbranih lokacijah po državi. Glede na zaskrbljujoče ugotovitve o splošnem upadu številčnosti pogostih vrst v Evropi (Rigal et al., 2023; Sánchez-Bayo & Wyckhuys, 2019), bi tak monitoring potrebovali tudi na nivoju Slovenije. Za splošno razširjene vrste ptic poteka metodološko usklajen monitoring z mednarodno PECBMS shemo, ki je dovolj obsežen, da omogoča izračun indeksa ptic kmetijske krajine na nivoju države. Nasprotno pa monitoring splošno razširjenih vrst metuljev v okviru mednarodne sheme eBMS v Sloveniji poteka na povsem prostovoljni ravni. Posledično je število lokacij premajhno, da bi trende izračunali na nivoju države. Z dodatnimi sredstvi bi se eBMS shema lahko prostorsko razširila, zbiranje in analiza podatkov pa bi bila na voljo tudi na nivoju Slovenije, kar predvideva tudi EU Uredba o obnovi narave. Vzpostavljeni so bili tudi prvi zametki monitoringa divjih čebel na nacionalnem nivoju po mednarodno usklajeni metodologiji projekta SPRING (Settele et al., 2024), ki pa še niso prešli v reden monitoring opraševalcev.

Nacionalni monitoring zelo slabo pokriva rastlinske vrste in HT, za katere so v svoji oceni raziskanosti populacijskih trendov ter površin in stanja HT (Udovč et al., 2020) podali oceno »neznano«. Po trenutno dostopnih podatkih je bilo izhodiščno stanje s kartiranjem HT opisano na 34 % površin območij Natura 2000 oziroma za 53 % vseh negozdnih površin Slovenije (Udovč et al., 2020). Monitoring izbranih 8 % rastlinskih vrst se nesistematično in

neredno izvaja v Natura 2000 območjih, izven njih pa monitoringa rastlinskih vrst ni (Udovč et al., 2020). Potrebo po rednem spremljanju izbranih kvantitativnih in kvalitativnih kazalnikov HT so v projektu CRP V4-1814 (Metodologija za finančno ovrednotenje instrumentov v I. in II. stebru SKP) identificirali tudi Udovč et al. (2020). Prav tako še ni vzpostavljen monitoring biodiverzitete talnih organizmov, za katere smo v okviru pravkar zaključenega projekta CRP V4-2221 (Strokovna izhodišča za monitoring izbranih organizmov nadzemne in podzemne biote v kmetijski krajini za spremljanje učinkovitosti naravovarstvenih ukrepov SKP) preizkusili uporabnost QBS indeksa (Menta et al., 2018; Parisi, 2001) za vrednotenje zdravja tal na podlagi združbe talnih živali (Naglič et al., 2025).

Tri monitoring sheme iz tujine (3Q program, 500 ENI, ALL-EMA) posvečajo veliko pozornosti izboru vzorčnih mest, ki naj bi bil čimbolj naključen. Prav tako izbor LUCAS točk in EMBAL kvadratov temelji na naključnem izboru iz sistematične mreže 2 km x 2 km »LUCAS Master grid«. S tega vidika bi bilo smiselno v Sloveniji za monitoring splošno razširjenih vrst uporabiti LUCAS in EMBAL točke ali kvadrate in tako hkrati zagotoviti naključen izbor vzorčnih lokacij in primerljivost z rezultati teh dveh mednarodnih shem. Ker EMBAL in LUCAS popisa beležita tudi številne komplementarne kazalnike, bi tako popise indikatorskih taksonov lahko dopolnili s kazalniki kot so raba tal in prisotnost krajinskih elementov.

EMBAL transektni popis indikatorskih taksonov predstavlja možno izhodišče za vzpostavitev monitoringa rastlin in HT. Pri tem so popisovalci beležili tudi barvo cvetov in število vrst cvetočih rastlin. Uporabnost slednjih dveh kazalnikov smo preizkusili na 48 transektih znotraj šestih območjih v Sloveniji in ugotovili, da sta z gotovostjo lahko razločila samo travišča z zelo intenzivno kmetijsko rabo od ostalih bolj ali manj ekstenzivnih travišč (Šabić et al., 2025). V okviru CRP V4-2221 smo predlagali nadgraditev seznama EMBAL rastlinskih indikatorskih taksonov in beleženje vseh prisotnih vrst ter oceno njihove pokrovnosti. Za prvi izveden EMBAL popis 2022/2023 že vemo, da je potekal na 103 kvadratih v Sloveniji, znotraj katerih je bilo popisanih skupno med 618 in 927 transektov. Natančna številka bo znana po objavi končnega poročila, vendar pričakujem, da bo glede na veliko število transektov Slovenija dobro pokrita.

Prvi korak k vzpostavitvi mednarodnega monitoringa talnih organizmov so izvedli v okviru LUCAS popisa leta 2018. Ko bo na voljo zaključno poročilo bomo izvedeli število vzorčnih mest v Sloveniji, na katerih so spremljali bio-

diverziteto talnih organizmov in tako preverili uporabnost teh podatkov za spremljanje na nivoju Slovenije. Glede na to, da so bili vzorci odvzeti na 1000 točkah po celotni EU, je bilo teh točk v Sloveniji verjetno zelo malo.

Vsi trije predstavljeni monitoringi iz tujine vključujejo natančne popise rabe tal. V Sloveniji imamo prostorsko zelo natančen in prosto dostopen sloj rabe tal (Evidenca dejanske rabe kmetijskih in gozdnih zemljišč), ki je dodatno nadgrajen s podatki o kmetijskih rastlinah na območjih kmetijskih zemljišč. Sloj je redno posodobljen in tako zagotavlja ažurne informacije o rabi tal. V 3Q, 500 ENI in ALL-EMA shemah na popisnih točkah beležijo tudi krajinske elemente. Monitoring deleža kmetijskih zemljišč z visokoraznovrstnimi krajinskimi značilnostmi predvideva tudi Uredba EU o obnovi narave. V Sloveniji imamo trenutno na voljo sloj evidence krajinskih značilnosti za območja intenzivnega kmetijstva, ki so ga avtorji izdelali v okviru CRP V4-2018 (Krajinske značilnosti in ukrepi bodoče kmetijske politike v Sloveniji) in bo lahko služil za izhodišče pri izpolnjevanju te zahteve EU Uredbe o obnovi narave.

Monitoring biodiverzitete je nujen tudi za informiranje upravljavcev in odločevalcev o učinkovitosti naravovarstvenih ukrepov SKP. Države EU imajo različne pristope za prostorsko usmerjanje naravovarstvenih ukrepov SKP (Underwood & Grace, 2017). Na primer na Danskem so izdelali prostorsko natančen (ločljivost 10 m x 10 m) sloj kmetijske krajine visoke naravne vrednosti (HNV) na podlagi 14 slojev o krajinskih elementih, HT, redkih vrstah in rabi tal (Underwood & Grace, 2017). Do sredstev naravovarstvenih ukrepov SKP na Danskem so upravičena kmetijska zemljišča na območjih Natura 2000, izven njih pa samo kmetijska zemljišča na HNV območjih (Underwood & Grace, 2017). Zemljevide upravičenih območij posodablajo vsako leto.

V Sloveniji je v Programu upravljanja območij Natura 2000 (PUN 2023-2028, priloga B) za vsako vrsto in HT opredeljeno, kateri SKP kmetijsko-okoljsko-podnebni ukrepi (KOPOP) so predvideni za njihovo ohranjanje. Sloj območij znotraj Natura 2000, na katerih se kmetijska zemljišča lahko vključujejo v posamezne KOPOP ukrepe, so izdelani na podlagi razširjenosti (con) vrst in HT, za katere je ta KOPOP opredeljen. V primeru prekrivanja različnih KOPOP ukrepov imajo prednost zahtevnejši. Nimamo pa trenutno vzpostavljenega monitoringa učinkov KOPOP ukrepov na vrste in HT. Pri preučevanju učinkovitosti ukrepov KOP za ohranjanje travišč visoke naravne vrednosti v Sloveniji v SKP 2007-2013 so to potrebo že izpostavili Kaligarič et al. (2019). Glede na nizko učinkovitost naravo-

varstvenih ukrepov v preteklih programih SKP (Evropsko računsko sodišče, 2020; Kleijn et al., 2006) in na svarila o pričakovani neučinkovitosti naravovarstvenih ukrepov SKP 2023-2027 (Pe'er et al., 2014) bi bil tak monitoring uporaben za oblikovanje ukrepov SKP v prihodnosti. Ker so kljub priporočilom strokovnjakov naravovarstveni ukrepi SKP 2023-2027 kratkoročni (Pe'er et al., 2022), bi bil velik vložek energije za monitoring učinkovitosti ukrepa na isti površini v času lahko hitro izgubljen, če bi se upravljalec premislil in iz ukrepa izstopil. Zato bi bilo učinkovitost takih ukrepov bolj smiselno spremljati s prostorsko primerjavo v ukrepe vključenih površin in takih, ki v ukrepe niso vključene.

Nekoliko drugačen pristop monitoringa kazalnikov biodiverzitete na nivoju kmetij pa so uporabili v evropskem projektu BIOBIO (Biodiversity Indicators for organic and low-input farming systems). Na podlagi pregleda literature so pripravili velik nabor kazalnikov, ki so ga po posvetu z deležniki zožili na nabor 23 kazalnikov iz štirih področij: raznolikost habitatov (8 kazalnikov); raznolikost vrst (4 kazalniki); genetska pestrost sort in pasem (3 kazalniki) in kmetijske prakse (8 kazalnikov) (Herzog et al., 2012). Kot indikatorske taksone so predlagali deževnike, višje rastline, čebele in ose ter pajke in zanje predlagali popoln popis vrst. Kazalnike so preverjali na 195 kmetijah v 12 evropskih regijah (Herzog et al., 2012). Podali so tudi oceno stroška, in sicer bi za kmetijo velikost 85 ha porabili 15 delovnih dni in dodatnih 1000€ za identifikacijo vrst (delo specialistov). Tako bi za 0,25 % skupne vrednosti, ki jo Evropska

unija porabi za SKP, lahko v monitoring biodiverzitete po BIOBIO metodologiji vključili 50.000 kmetij iz celotne EU (Herzog et al., 2012). Monitoring na nivoju kmetije bi omogočil pomembne informacije o vzročno posledično povezavi med kmetijskimi praksami in njihovimi vplivi na biodiverzitetu. V 500 ENI beležijo tudi kmetijske prakse popisanih parcel na podlagi intervjujev s kmeti (obdelava tal, gnojenje, število košenj itd.), česar v Sloveniji v okviru nacionalnih monitoringov biodiverzitete ne spremljamo.

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Review

Plastika v kmetijstvu: uporaba in vplivi ostankov plastike na tla ter zelenjadarske pridelovalne sisteme

Špela Železnikar^{1*}, Nina Kacjan-Maršič¹

Izvleček

Plastika je zaradi nizkih stroškov, vsestranske uporabnosti in obstojnosti postala nepogrešljiv material sodobnega kmetijstva, pri čemer ima njena uporaba kljub razmeroma majhnemu deležu v svetovni proizvodnji pomemben vpliv na delovanje agroekosistemov. V kmetijski praksi prispeva k večji produktivnosti in učinkovitejši rabi naravnih virov, hkrati pa predstavlja vir onesnaževanja tal, saj se s staranjem in razgradnjo kopiči v tleh v obliki manjših plastičnih delcev, ki lahko prehajajo v vodne in prehranske verige. Namen članka je ovrednotiti znanje o virih, poteh vnosa in okoljskih učinkih mikroplastike (MP) v kmetijskih tleh. Glavni viri vnosa plastičnih delcev v kmetijska tla vključujejo uporabo kompostiranih in fermentiranih organskih ostankov, komunalnega blata, namakanje z odpadno vodo ter razgradnjo in zaoravanje plastičnih zastirnih folij, dodatno pa tudi izluževanje iz neustrezno upravljanjih odlagališč odpadkov. Po vnosu v tla se plastični delci vežejo na mineralne in organske komponente ter postanejo del talnega sistema, kar lahko povzroči spremembe gostote tal, stabilnosti agregatov, sposobnosti zadrževanja vode in vodoodbojnosti. Posebna pozornost je v članku namenjena uporabi plastičnih materialov v zelenjadarski pridelavi, kjer kritine rastlinjakov in tunelov, zastirne folije ter namakalni sistemi pomembno prispevajo k uravnavanju mikroklimatskih razmer in stabilnosti pridelave. Na podlagi pregleda literature ugotavljamo, da tudi biorazgradljivi materiali v realnih talnih razmerah pogosto ne dosegajo pričakovane stopnje razgradnje, kar poudarja potrebo po celostni oceni materialov ter razvoju trajnostnih in odgovornih kmetijskih praks za zmanjšanje onesnaženosti tal s plastiko.

Ključne besede

kmetijska plastika; pridelava zelenjave; mikroplastika; onesnaženje

¹ Univerza v Ljubljani, Biotehniška fakulteta, Oddelek za agronomijo, Jamnikarjeva 101, Ljubljana, Slovenia

* Corresponding author:

E-mail address: spela.zeleznikar@bf.uni-lj

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Plastics in agriculture: use and impact of residues on soil and vegetable production systems

Abstract

Plastic has become an indispensable material in modern agriculture due to its low cost, versatility, and durability, and its use, despite representing a relatively small share of global production, significantly impacts agroecosystem functioning. In agricultural practice, plastics contribute to higher productivity and more efficient natural resource use, while also acting as a source of soil contamination, as they accumulate during aging and degradation in the form of smaller particles that can enter aquatic and food chains. This article aims to evaluate current knowledge on the sources, pathways, and environmental impacts of microplastics (MP) in agricultural soils. Major sources of plastic particle input into soils include the application of composted and fermented organic residues, sewage sludge, irrigation with treated wastewater, and the degradation and incorporation of plastic mulches, as well as leaching from improperly managed waste disposal sites. Once incorporated into soils, plastic particles interact with mineral and organic components, becoming part of the soil matrix and potentially altering soil bulk density, aggregate stability, water retention capacity, and hydrophobicity. Special attention is given to the use of plastics in vegetable production, where greenhouse and tunnel coverings, mulching films, and irrigation systems play a key role in regulating microclimatic conditions and stabilizing yields. A review of the literature indicates that even biodegradable materials frequently fail to achieve their expected degradation rates under field conditions, highlighting the need for comprehensive evaluation of materials and the development of sustainable and responsible agricultural practices to mitigate soil plastic contamination.

Keywords

agricultural plastic; vegetable production; microplastics; pollution

Uvod

Plastika je nepogrešljiv material v številnih sektorjih zaradi nizkih stroškov proizvodnje ter vsestranske uporabnosti in obstojnosti (Niu et al., 2024; Rillig & Lehmann, 2020). Svetovna proizvodnja plastike se je povečala z 1,5 milijona ton leta 1950 na 367 milijonov ton leta 2020 (Klingelhöfer et al., 2020; Zhou et al., 2020b), leta 2021 pa je proizvodnja že preseгла 390 milijonov ton, od tega je bilo 90,2 % plastike proizvedene iz fosilnih virov (Hachem et al., 2023; Salama & Geyer, 2023). Po ocenah bo kumulativna proizvodnja plastike v obdobju 1950–2050 dosegla kar 34 milijard ton. Takšen obseg proizvodnje in uporabe postavlja plastiko v središče razprav o trajnostnem razvoju in krožnem gospodarstvu (Environment, 2022).

Od začetka proizvodnje v prvi polovici 20. stoletja je plastika temeljito preoblikovala delovanje številnih gospodarskih sektorjev. Danes je nepogrešljiva v embalažni in avtomobilski industriji, gradbeništvu, elektroniki ter kmetijstvu, kjer zaradi svojih fizikalno-kemijskih lastnosti pogosto nadomešča tradicionalne materiale, kot so les, kovina ali

steklo (Klingelhöfer et al., 2020; Zhou et al., 2020a).

Kmetijska pridelava predstavlja približno 3,1 % svetovnega povpraševanja po plastiki (Niu et al., 2024). Kljub temu ta relativno majhen delež pomembno vpliva na agroekosisteme. Plastika se v kmetijstvu uporablja predvsem v obliki folij za zastiranje tal, kritin rastlinjakov, namakalnih cevi, vreč za siliranje in različnih embalažnih materialov (FAO, 2021; Klingelhöfer et al., 2020). Uporaba teh plastičnih izdelkov prispeva k povečanju pridelka, boljšemu upravljanju z vodo in hranili ter zaščiti rastlin pred stresnimi dejavniki (Cillis et al., 2022; Geyer et al., 2017).

Hkrati pa uporaba plastike v kmetijstvu predstavlja resen vir onesnaževanja tal in širših agroekosistemov z ostanki plastike. Zaradi vremenskih vplivov, mehanske obremenitve in nepopolnega odstranjevanja ob koncu uporabe se plastični materiali razgrajujejo v manjše delce, ki se ohranjajo v tleh, in lahko prehajajo v vodo in prehranske verige (An et al., 2020; Astner et al., 2023; Zhou et al., 2020a). Ti manjši delci so opredeljeni kot mikroplastika (MP), tj. plastični delci z velikostjo manj kot 5 mm, ki zaradi svoje obstojnosti in kemijske stabilnosti v okolju dolgo

vztrajajo ter predstavljajo potencialno tveganje za tla, vodne ekosisteme in prehranske verige.

Kmetijska plastika

Proces proizvodnje plastike se začne z ekstrakcijo neobnovljivih fosilnih surovin, kot sta nafta in zemeljski plin, ki se nato predelata v različne vrste polimerov. Izraz kmetijska plastika (KP) (angl. Agricultural Plastics) zajema vse vrste konvencionalnih fosilnih plastičnih izdelkov, ki se uporabljajo v rastlinski pridelavi in vzreji živali, pa tudi alternativne materiale na biološki osnovi ter biorazgradljive materiale. Biorazgradljiva plastika je definirana kot material, ki ga mikroorganizmi v specifičnem okolju popolnoma razgradijo, brez negativnih vplivov na okolje ali ekotoksičnosti (Briassoulis, 2023). Certificiranje biorazgradljivih plastičnih izdelkov izvajajo neodvisne institucije, skladno z mednarodnimi standardi in validiranimi metodami. Primer takšnega standarda je EN 17033 (2018) (*SIST EN 17033:2018 - Biodegradable Mulch Films for Agriculture* &, n.d.) za biorazgradljive folije za zastiranje tal, pri katerem se zahteva najmanj 90-odstotna pretvorba ogljika iz folije v CO₂ v dveh letih v naravnih tleh (*ISO 17556, 2019*).

Izraz *biorazgradljiva kmetijska plastika (KP)* se nanaša na plastične izdelke, ki so certificirani kot biorazgradljivi v tleh in/ali kompostabilni v skladu z veljavnimi mednarodnimi standardi (npr. EN 17033, 2018; EN 13432, 2000), pri čemer je biorazgradljivost lastnost materiala in ni nujno povezana z njegovim izvorom.

Pojem *bioplastika* zajema širšo skupino materialov, ki vključuje plastiko na biološki osnovi, biorazgradljivo plastiko ali kombinacijo obeh lastnosti. Plastika na biološki osnovi je delno ali v celoti proizvedena iz obnovljivih bioloških surovin, vendar ni nujno tudi biorazgradljiva, medtem ko je biorazgradljiva plastika lahko izdelana tako iz bioloških kot fosilnih virov (Briassoulis, 2023). Delež ogljika biološkega izvora se določa z ustreznimi testnimi metodami (npr. EN 16785-1, 2015; EN 16640, 2017). Večina bioplastike je izdelana iz mešanic biopolimerov ali kombinacij bioloških in konvencionalnih biorazgradljivih polimerov ter dodatkov, zato se delež vsebnosti biomase lahko precej razlikuje.

Uporaba kmetijske plastike

V kmetijstvu se uporablja široka paleta plastičnih izdelkov (Slika 1) iz polimerov in biopolimerov, ki se razlikujejo po vsebnosti dodatkov in fizikalnih lastnostih (npr. trdnost,

prosojnost, izolacijska sposobnost, vodoodpornost), prilagojenih specifični uporabi posameznega izdelka. Med najpogosteje uporabljenimi je polietilen nizke gostote (LDPE), ki je prožen, lahek in ima dobre pregradne lastnosti, zato se uporablja predvsem za zastirne folije in tunelske rastlinjake. Polietilen visoke gostote (HDPE) je trdnější in odporen na kemikalije, zato je primeren za zaščitne mreže, posode ter debelejšje folije. Polipropilen (PP) je lahek, kemično odporen ter se lahko uporablja v tkanih in netkanih oblikah, kar omogoča uporabo za vreče, vrvice, zaboje, mreže in prekrivke. Ekspandirani polistiren (EPS) je lahek, izolativen in tog, zato se uporablja predvsem za embalažo. Polivinilklorid (PVC) je lahko tog ali prožen ter zelo obstojen, kar omogoča njegovo uporabo pri zastirnih folijah, ceveh za kapljično namakanje in kritinah v rastlinjakih. Polietilen tereftalat (PET) je tog, prosojen in kemično odporen, zato je pogosta izbira za embalažo tekočin ter za vlakna. Polikarbonat (PC) in najlon imata raznolike mehanske lastnosti, kar omogoča njuno uporabo za posode za pesticide in različne mreže (FAO, 2021). Med bioplastiko sodijo tudi nekateri biorazgradljivi polimeri, kot je polimlečna kislina (PLA), ki je polimer na biološki osnovi; njegova biorazgradljivost je odvisna od okoljskih pogojev in je praviloma potrjena za industrijsko kompostiranje ter izkazuje dobro mehansko stabilnost, zaradi česar se pogosto uporablja za proizvodnjo zastirnih folij, mrež in vrvic. Polihidroksialkanoati (PHA) so mikrobiološko proizvedeni polimeri, ki so po lastnostih primerljivi s konvencionalnimi polietilenom (PE) in polipropilenom (PP); njihova glavna vloga je nadomestitev sintetičnih polimerov, kot so PE, PP in PET. Polibutilen sukcinat (PBS) je popolnoma biološko razgradljiv polimer s toplotno obstojnostjo, ki se uporablja predvsem pri izdelavi zastirnih folij ter kot funkcionalna zamenjava za PP. Polibutirat adipat tereftalat (PBAT) je fleksibilen material s fizikalnimi lastnostmi, podobnimi LDPE, kar omogoča njegovo uporabo pri proizvodnji zastirnih folij. Škrobne zmesi s PBAT predstavljajo cenovno ugodnejšo alternativo, vendar imajo slabše mehanske lastnosti; kljub temu se pogosto uporabljajo za folije in embalažo za enkratno uporabo. Polikaprolakton (PCL) je hidrofoben polimer, ki se zaradi svojih specifičnih lastnosti pogosto dodaja škrobnim zmesem za izboljšanje obstojnosti končnih materialov (FAO, 2021; Zhou et al., 2020a).

Kljub vse širši uporabi KP ter številnim raziskavam o njenem vplivu na okolje, se njeni dolgoročni učinki na agroekosisteme še vedno premalo raziskani. V praksi se plastika v kmetijstvu uporablja predvsem zaradi krat-

koročnih koristi, kot so izboljšane rastne razmere in s tem večja učinkovitost pridelave, ohranjanje vlage in zmanjšanje rasti plevelov, vendar pa se z razgradnjo in akumulacijo plastike v tleh pojavljajo pomembni izzivi. Celovito razumevanje vplivov KP na tla, rastline in kmetijsko pridelavo predstavlja izhodišče za pripravo tega prispevka. Namen članka je celostno predstaviti obseg in načine uporabe plastike v kmetijstvu, analizirati njene vplive na agroekosisteme ter osvetliti problematiko onesnaženosti kmetijskih zemljišč z MP. Poseben poudarek je namenjen virom MP v tleh, njenim vplivom na izbrane fizikalne in biološke lastnosti tal ter uporabi plastičnih materialov pri pridelavi zelenjadnic, vključno s kritinami za zavarovane prostore, plastičnimi in biorazgradljivimi zastirkami.

Metodološki okvir

Analiza raziskovalnega področja kmetijske plastike

Celovito razumevanje vloge KP v agroekosistemih ter njenih vplivov na tla, rastline in talne organizme zahteva tudi kvanti-

tativni pregled obstoječih raziskav. Izvedena bibliometrična analiza raziskovalnega področja s pomočjo programskega orodja VOSviewer prikazuje raziskovalne trende, tematske povezave in ključne raziskovalne usmeritve v literaturi. Slika 2 prikazuje analizo raziskovalnega področja KP in njenega vpliva na agroekosisteme z uporabo programskega orodja (VOSviewer - *Visualizing Scientific Landscapes*, n.d.), s katerim smo vizualizirali so-pojavnost avtorjevih ključnih besed iz baze Web of Science (2015–2026, iskalna sintaksa AK=(agricultural plastic* AND effect), 6.417 znanstvenih del). V analizo so bile vključene ključne besede s pragom pojavnosti najmanj pet. Rezultati kažejo, da raziskave o kmetijski plastiki tvorijo jasno strukturirano tematsko mrežo z desetimi glavnimi grozdi (klastri), ki so barvno označeni, medtem ko črtne povezave predstavljajo stopnjo so-pojavnosti. V središču mreže se nahaja pojem »microplastics«, ki se najpogosteje povezuje z izrazi, kot so »soil«, »pollution«, »toxicity« in »accumulation«, kar odraža osrednji raziskovalni interes. Posamezni grozdi nakazujejo raziskovalne usmeritve (Preglednica 1). Analiza prikazuje 3.000 pojmov, povezanih s 122.658 povezavami, z visoko skupno močjo povezav (200.439), kar potrjuje kompleksnost in medsebojno prepletenost raziskav s tega področja.

Slika 1. Najpogostejši plastični izdelki v kmetijski rabi (Canva, 2025).

Figure 1. Most frequently used plastic products in agriculture (Canva, 2025).

Slika 2. Mreža so-pojavnosti ključnih besed iz raziskav o kmetijski plastiki in vplivu na agroekosisteme (VOSviewer). Velikost vozličč odraža pogostost, barve tematske skupine, povezave pa so-pojavnost izrazov. Vir podatkov: Web of Science (2015–2026).

Figure 2. Co-occurrence network of keywords from research on agricultural plastics and their impact on agroecosystems (VOSviewer). Node size reflects frequency, colors reflect thematic groups, and links reflect co-occurrence of terms. Data source: Web of Science (2015–2026).

Tabela 1. Pregled glavnih klastrov ključnih besed, povezanih z raziskavami KP v agroekosistemi.

Table 1. Overview of the main clusters of keywords related to KP research in agroecosystems.

Barva klastra	Glavne ključne besede	Raziskovalna usmeritev
Rdeč	microplastics, pollution, toxicity, oxidative stress, accumulation	Onesnaževanje z mikroplastiko, toksični učinki in vpliv na okolje ter organizme
Zelen	mechanical properties, cellulose, biodegradable, composites, biomass	Razvoj bioplastike, kompozitov in raziskave materialnih lastnosti
Moder	yield, irrigation, water use efficiency, loess plateau, mulching	Učinki plastičnih folij na pridelke, učinkovitost rabe vode in namakalne prakse
Vijoličen	growth, temperature, evapotranspiration, fruit quality, heat stress	Vplivi plastike na mikroklimo, temperaturo, rast, kakovost in stres pri rastlinah
Rumen/Oranžen	soil, microbial community, impact, organic carbon, ecosystem	Spremembe lastnosti tal, vpliv na mikrobne združbe in kroženje hranil

Vpliv plastike na agroekosisteme

Številne študije poročajo o izvajanju terenskih, laboratorijskih poskusov in analiz, z namenom kvantifikacije virov, poti in usode onesnaženja s plastiko v kopenskih in vodnih okoljih. V raziskavah so avtorji preučili razporeditev, razširjenost in značilnosti plastičnih ostankov v tleh in sedimentih, oceanih, rekah, jezerih, s čimer so pojasnili obseg

in prostorsko razporeditev onesnaženja s plastiko po svetu (Adekanmbi et al., 2024; Hoang et al., 2024).

Ključni izsledki raziskav izpostavljajo razširjenost onesnaženja ekosistemov s plastiko in večplastno vplivanje na okolje in zdravje. Ob dolgotrajni izpostavljenosti naravnim dejavnikom, kot so UV sevanje, mehanska obraba, erozija tal in biotska razgradnja, plastični ostanki postopoma razpadajo v mikrodolce, tj. MP, ki predstavlja

plastične delce velikosti 1–5 mm (Adekanmbi et al., 2024; Barnes et al., 2009). Prisotnost MP je bila dokazana v tleh, vodi, zraku in živilih, kar vzbuja skrb glede njenih morebitnih vplivov na kmetijsko produktivnost, varnost hrane in zdravje ljudi (Hoang et al., 2024; An et al., 2020).

Onesnaženost kmetijskih zemljišč z mikroplastiko

Kmetijska tla predstavljajo pomemben ponor plastičnih delcev v kopenskih ekosistemih. Kljub temu so podatki o koncentracijah in razširjenosti MP v evropskih kmetijskih tleh še vedno pomanjkljivi. Glavni razlog je pomanjkanje standardiziranih metod za identifikacijo in kvantifikacijo MP v tleh ter odsotnost zakonskih okvirjev, ki bi zahtevali sistematično spremljanje onesnaženosti tal z MP (Železnikar et al., 2025; Ai et al., 2023; Fan et al., 2023).

Glavni viri vnosa MP v tla na kmetijskih površinah so uporaba kompostiranih in fermentiranih organskih ostankov in komunalnega blata, okoljska razgradnja plastičnih materialov, namakanje z odpadno vodo, kakor tudi zaoravanje ostankov zastirnih folij ter izluževanje z neustrezno upravljanih odlagališč komunalnih odpadkov (Fan et al., 2023; Gao et al., 2020; Bläsing & Amelung, 2018).

Po ocenah Nizzetto et al. (2016) prispeva uporaba komunalnega blata na evropska kmetijska zemljišča približno 5,8 kg MP na hektar letno (približno 1,6 mg/kg tal). Piehl et al. (2018) pa poročajo, da vsebujejo kmetijska tla v Nemčiji povprečno $0,34 \pm 0,36$ delcev MP/kg suhe snovi. Zelo visoke koncentracije, okoli 1 % ali več, so bile dokazane predvsem v posebej onesnaženih območjih, kot so bližina mestnih središč ali zemljišča z intenzivno uporabo

plastičnih zastirnih folij (J. Li et al., 2020). Ti podatki nakazujejo, da mnoge dosedanje študije verjetno ne odražajo realnih razmer v večini kmetijskih sistemov. Kljub temu pa se z nadaljnjim širjenjem onesnaževanja s plastiko, zlasti v regijah z intenzivno kmetijsko pridelavo, pričakuje, da bodo podobne koncentracije v prihodnosti vse pogostejše.

Viri mikroplastike v kmetijskih zemljiščih

Raziskave o prisotnosti MP v kmetijskih tleh kažejo, da se v okolje vnaša prek številnih virov, med katerimi prevladujejo različne vrste plastičnih zastirk, dodatne vire pa predstavljajo kritine rastlinjakov, oprema in voda za namakanje, uporaba gnojil, komposta in blata ter različnih embalažnih materialov (Fan et al., 2023; Gao et al., 2020; Piehl et al., 2018). Kljub raznolikosti virov rezultati večine študij poročajo, da se MP najpogosteje kopiči v površinskih plasteh tal, čeprav so jo v nekaterih raziskavah identificirali tudi globlje v talnem profilu.

Količine MP, izmerjene v tleh, se med posameznimi študijami zelo razlikujejo, saj uporabljajo različne metodologije določevanja MP v tleh, obravnavajo različne tipe plastik in preučujejo različna okolja. Nekatere raziskave podajajo natančne koncentracije, druge pa se osredotočajo le na prisotnost mikro- in makroplastike brez kvantifikacije. Podobno so različna tudi časovna obdobja spremljanja, ki segajo od kratkoročnih eksperimentov do dolgoročnih terenskih opažanj.

Preglednica 2 povzema glavne značilnosti izbranih študij, pri čemer združuje informacije o virih plastike, izmerjenih koncentracijah, razporeditvi po globini tal in trajanju posameznih raziskav.

Tabela 2. Pregled študij o virih in pojavljanju MP v kmetijskih tleh.

Table 2. Overview of studies on sources and occurrence of MP in agricultural soils.

Vir (mikro)plastike	Koncentracija	Globina (tal) najdenih MP delcev	Trajanje raziskave	Raziskava
Plastične zastirne folije	Makroplastika: 6.796 (gnojena tla) ali 653 (ne gnojena tla) delcev/m;	Makroplastika: 0–20 cm; mikroplastika: 0–100 cm	32 let	i et al., 2022
	0,1–324,5 kg/ha (povp. 83,6kg/ha)	/	>30 let	et al., 2020
Biorazgradljive zastirne folije	1 % m/m (makro: 4–10 mm; mikro: 50 µm–1 mm)	/	več mesecev	2020; Serrano-Ruiz et al., 2021
Zastirne folije, namakanje, embalaža	320–12.560 delcev/kg (Kitajska)	0–10 cm	več mesecev	Pérez-Reverón et al., 2022
Zastirne folije, rastlinjaki, gnojila	4,94–40.800 delcev/kg (Kitajska); ≤1 mm	/	/	ang, 2023
Zastirne folije, rastlinjaki, blato, kompost	300–14.600 delcev/kg	največ v površinskem sloju; nekaj globlje	3 leta	Sa'adu & Farsang, 2023

Vpliv mikroplastike na izbrane lastnosti tal

Ko pridejo delci MP v tla, se lahko zaradi ponavljajočih se ciklov vlaženja in sušenja v tleh hitro razpršijo (Jin et al., 2022; Wang et al., 2020). Premikanje MP pa dodatno spodbuja tudi bioturbacija (Meng et al., 2024) ter različni načini obdelave tal (Wang et al., 2020). Po ugotovitvah Guo in sod., (2022) ter Wang in sod. (2023) ima pri vplivu MP pomembno vlogo tudi tekstura tal. V peščenih tleh, kjer prevladujejo večje pore, se delci MP lažje premikajo in posledično razpršijo globlje ter širše po talnem profilu. Nasprotno pa glinena in ilovnata tla z manjšimi porami delce veliko bolj zadržujejo, kar omejuje njihov vertikalni transport, hkrati pa spodbuja njihovo kopičenje v vrhnjih plasteh tal.

Ko MP pride v tla, se lahko veže na minerale ter organske snovi in tako postane del talnega sistema. To lahko vpliva na spremembe v fizikalnih lastnostih tal, kot so spremembe gostote tal, stabilnosti agregatov, sposobnosti zadrževanja vode ter vodoodbojnosti (Hasan & Tarannum, 2025; Qi et al., 2020; Železnikar et al., 2025a; Železnikar et al., 2025b). Rezultati raziskav dokazujejo, da hidrofobnost MP, njen površinski naboj in velikost delcev pomembno vplivajo na hidravlične lastnosti tal (Gong & Xie, 2020; Hanif et al., 2024). S porastom koncentracije MP v tleh se zmanjšuje število mikro- in makropor, kar vodi v zmanjšanje hidravlične prevodnosti tal (Guo et al., 2022; M. Kumar et al., 2020). Sajjad in sod. (2022) poudarjajo, da lahko MP mehansko zapira pore in tako ovira transport vode in hranil do rastlin. Poleg tega raziskave kažejo, da hidrofobna površina MP odbija vodne molekule, kar lahko dodatno zmanjšuje dostopnost vode v tleh za rastline (R. Kumar et al., 2023; Železnikar et al., 2025a). Zaradi tega se postavlja vprašanje, kako spremembe omočenosti tal, ki jih povzroča MP, vplivajo na nasičeno hidravlično prevodnost in sposobnost tal zadrževati vodo (Shafea et al., 2023).

Čeprav uporaba plastičnih materialov v kmetijstvu prinaša kratkoročne prednosti, se raziskovalci vse bolj osredotočajo na dolgoročne posledice njihove akumulacije v tleh ter na vpliv na kakovost tal in pridelavo rastlin (Dissanayake et al., 2022; Hasan & Tarannum, 2025; Jin et al., 2022).

Razumevanje vplivov MP na fizikalne lastnosti tal je ključnega pomena tudi v povezavi s sodobno rabo plastičnih materialov v kmetijski pridelavi rastlinske hrane. Plastični materiali za prekrivanje tunelov in rastlinjakov ter folije za zastiranje tal, namakalne cevi in drugi plastični pripomočki so v zelenjadarski pridelavi postali nepogrešljivi

zaradi svojih koristi, kot so boljši nadzor nad pleveli, večja učinkovitost rabe vode ter stabilnejše mikroklimatske razmere. Vendar se ob vse večji akumulaciji MP v tleh pojavljajo vprašanja o njihovih dolgoročnih posledicah. Zato je povezovanje znanja o fizikalnih procesih v tleh z razumevanjem prakse uporabe kmetijske plastike ključno za celovito oceno tveganj in za oblikovanje trajnostnih pristopov v zelenjadarski pridelavi.

Uporaba plastičnih mas pri pridelavi zelenjadnic

Kritine za različne oblike zavarovanih prostorov (rastlinjakov, tunelov)

Pridelava večine zelenjadnic poteka na gredicah na prostem, razen toplotno zahtevnejših zelenjadnic iz skupine plodovk, ki jih pridelujemo v različnih oblikah zavarovanih prostorov. S tem potrošniku zagotovimo stabilno oskrbo z lokalno, sveže pridelano zelenjavo skozi daljše časovno obdobje. Z uporabo nizkih in visokih tunelov dosežemo ugodnejše rastne razmere in s tem pospeševanje rasti v zgodnje pomladanskem obdobju ali podaljševanje rastne dobe v jesenskem in zimskem obdobju. Na mikroklimatsko ugodnejših legah lahko v neogrevanih ali delno ogrevanih rastlinjakih pridelujemo toplotno manj zahtevne vrtnine tudi v zimskem obdobju. V rastlinjakih je zaradi daljše rastne dobe mogoče pridelati 3–10 x več pridelka plodovk, glede na pridelavo na prostem (Yelmen in sod., 2019). Hitrejša rast in dozorevanje plodov ter s tem večji pridelki so posledica ugodnejših ravnih razmer in predvsem manjših temperaturnih nihanj, ki jih v rastlinjakih zagotovimo z izborom ogrevalnih sistemov in primernih materialov za kritine, kjer so pomembne predvsem njihove mehanske in optične lastnosti. Za kritino je pomembno, da dobro prepušča vidni del sončnega spektra (med 400 nm in 700 nm); dobro zadrži dolgo-valovno sevanje (valovne dolžine od 3.000 do 20.000 nm), je odporna na staranje in s tem zmanjševanje svetlobne prepustnosti, odporna na nabiranje umazanije in prahu ter kondenzacijo drobnih kapljic. Rastlinjaki so lahko prekriti s trdo kritino, za katero se najpogosteje uporabljajo materiali kot so polimetilmetakrilat (PMMA) in PC. Namenjeni so večmesečni pridelavi zelenjave, saj v njih s pomočjo različnih ogrevalnih sistemov zagotavljamo ustrezne rastne razmere v najhladnejšem delu leta. Za bolj sezonsko pridelavo zelenjadnic pa so rastlinjaki prekriti z mehкими, običajno dvoslojnimi kritinami, za katere se

uporabljajo materiali kot so polietilen (PE), ki je UV stabiliziran; etilenvinilacetat (EVA), pa tudi PVC (von Zabeltitz, 2010). Kritine iz plastičnih mas so še pred nekaj desetletji povzročale veliko onesnaženost tal z MP, saj je bila trajnost teh materialov le 1-2 leti. Danes so materialom za kritine dodani različni UV stabilizatorji iz skupine oviranih aminov (Hindered amine light stabilizer – HALS), ki jim podaljšajo možnost uporabe. Trajnost materialov in ohranjanje njihovih mehanskih in optičnih lastnosti je tesno povezana z vremenskimi razmerami. Pomemben vpliv imajo predvsem visoke temperature, sončno obsevanje, količina padavin na lokaciji, kjer se objekt nahaja in vetrne razmere (Yu in sod., 2021). Poleg okoljskih dejavnikov zmanjšuje trajnost kritine tudi uporaba fitofarmaceutskih sredstev znotraj rastlinjakov, predvsem tistih na bazi žvepla, halogenov, železa in klora. Tudi okoljski onesnaževalci iz vrst ogljikovodikov, didušikov oksid, žveplov oksid ter delci onesnaževal pospešujejo propadanje polimerov, saj povzročijo izločanje vodika iz polimerne verige, kar zmanjša trdnost polimerov in povzroči nadaljnjo depolimerizacijo (Dilara in Briassoulis, 2000).

Poleg mnogih koristi, ki jih imajo različni materiali za kritine rastlinjakov, se v zadnjih letih vse bolj zavedamo nevarnosti sproščanja mikro in nanoplastičnih delcev iz plastičnih kritih v okolje. Tam so ti delci izpostavljeni biotski in abiotski razgradnji. Biotsko razgradnjo opravljajo bakterije, glive ali alge, ki povzročijo encimatsko razgradnjo polimernih verig na manjše oligo ali monomere. Abiotska razgradnja pa je posledica foto degradacije, termo degradacije in mehanske degradacije plastičnih materialov. Nastajata mikro in nano-plastika, kratke verige polimerov, plini in druge majhne molekule, kot stranski produkti (Zhang in sod., 2021). V raziskavi, ki so jo opravili Sorasan in sod. (2024), so simulirali staranje polietilenske kritine z umetnim osvetljevanjem. Zanimala jih je razlika v staranju novega in že uporabljenega materiala in morebitno sproščanje razpadlih snovi v okolje, zato so za raziskavo uporabili novo folijo in 3 leta staro folijo. Razrezali so jo na koščke 5 mm × 5 mm, raztopili v vodi v koncentraciji 0,1 g/ml in obsevali s 100 W ksenonovo žarnico na oddaljenosti 18 cm. S tridnevnim obsevanjem so simulirali enomesečno izpostavljenost sončnemu sevanju na Iberskem polotoku, od koder je bil vzet material za kritino. Obsevali so 18 dni in tako simulirali 6 mesečno izpostavljenost materiala sončnemu sevanju, kar je običajno obdobje gojenja zelenjadnic v rastlinjakih na JV delu Španije, na območju Almerie, ki ga prekriva več kot 30.000 ha rastlinjakov s plastično PE kritino. Z različnimi analiznimi postopki za detekcijo

mikro in nano plastičnih delcev – s sledilnim sistemom za nanodelce (NTA – nanoparticle tracking system); pretočno citometrijo (FC), analizo celokupnega organskega ogljika (TOC) in elektronskim mikroskopom, povezanim s skenerjem (SEM) so ugotovili večjo razgradnjo na mikro delce že uporabljene kritine glede na novo, nerabljeno kritino. SEM in NTA analizi sta potrdili prisotnost nanodelcev plastike v raztopini obsevanega, kot tudi neobsevanega materiala. Foto degradacija nove polietilenske kritine je povzročila sproščanje še drugih snovi, ki v kritini predstavljajo različne stabilizatorje, kot so mineralna polnila, etilen vinilacetat kot vezivni material med dvema plastema PE ter aditivi na bazi kovinskih ionov in absorberji za povečano odpornost na dolgovalovno in UV sevanje.

Plastične zastirke za prekrivanje tal, ki se uporabljajo pri pridelavi zelenjadnic

Agrotehnični ukrepi intenzivne pridelave zelenjadnic vključujejo poleg pridelave v rastlinjakih tudi pridelavo na zastrtih tleh z različnimi umetnimi ali naravnimi materiali. Zastiranje tal je agrotehnični ukrep, pri katerem gredico prekrijemo - zastremo, najpogosteje s plastičnimi zastirnimi folijami z namenom, da se tla hitreje segrejejo. S tem omogočimo hitrejšo zasnovo posevkov in zgodnejši pridelek. Prednost zastrtih tal je tudi v daljšem ohranjanju vlage v tleh in učinkovitejšem sprejemu hranil iz tal, kakor tudi varovanje strukturnih agregatov ter preprečevanje spiranja hranil iz orne plasti tal v podtalje, v primeru obilnejših padavin. Pomembna prednost, ki jo zastrta tla omogočajo, je preprečitev rasti plevelnih vrst, ki v kompeticiji z gojenimi rastlinami lahko povzročijo slabšo rast in manjši pridelek (Espí in sod., 2006). Slaba stran uporabe zastirk se izrazi po končanem obdobju pridelave, ko kmetje na koncu rastne sezone ne uspejo zastirke v celoti odstraniti, zato ostajajo v tleh majhni koščki plastike, ki se s časoma spremenijo v mikro ali nano plastiko in tako na dolgi rok ogrožajo okolje (Qi in sod., 2020). Šele v zadnjih nekaj letih znanstveniki opozarjajo na pretirano uporabo plastičnih zastirk v kmetijstvu zaradi vse večjega pojavljanja MP v tleh, ki narašča na tistih območjih, kjer poteka intenzivna pridelava zelenjave na zastrtih tleh, tako na prostem kot tudi v rastlinjakih (Liu in sod., 2018). Največje površine, kjer pridelujejo zelenjavo na zastrtih tleh s plastičnimi materiali so na Kitajskem, v Španiji in ZDA (Lwanga in sod., 2022). V obsežni raziskavi Yu in sod. (2021), ki so jo izvedli na največjem pridelovalnem območju v provinci Shounguang na Kitajskem, so ugotovili prisotnost MP v tleh. Zanimala jih je oblika in velikost

plastičnih delcev, njihova kemična sestava in porazdelitev v talnem profilu v rastlinjaških tleh in na prostem. Vzorčili so v treh globinah (0–5 cm, 5–10 cm in 10–25 cm), na 27 mestih v rastlinjaku in 18 mestih na polju. Rezultati za rastlinjaška tla so pokazali največ plastičnih delcev v velikosti <0,5 mm (65 %) 0,5–1 mm (19 %), 1–2 mm (10 %) in 2–5 mm (6 %). Količina najmanjših delcev se je z globino povečevala, medtem, ko je bilo večjih delcev (2–5 mm) največ v zgornji plasti tal. Prenos drobnih plastičnih delcev v globlje plasti naj bi bila posledica aktivnosti talnih živali, kot so deževniki. Ti pogosto zaužijejo majhne delce plastike, ki jih nato izločijo z iztrebki v talnih porah globljih plasti tal (Huerta Lwanga in sod., 2016). V globlje plasti se najdrobnejši plastični delci lahko tudi sperejo skozi pore in razpoke v tleh, večji delci pa so pritrjeni na površini talnih delcev in tako ostajajo v zgornjih plasteh tal (Zhang et al., 2020)). Razporeditev plastičnih delcev v tleh na prostem je bila drugačna od tiste v rastlinjaku. Največ drobnih plastičnih delcev (<0,5 mm) je bilo v globini 5–10 cm (71 %), kar so pripisali večjemu vplivu okoljskih dejavnikov, predvsem vetru in padavinam. Glede na obliko plastičnih delcev so prevladovali delci v obliki vlaken, kroglic, pene ter delcev v obliki folije in fragmentov. Po kemijski sestavi so med plastičnimi delci v tleh prevladovali polipropilen, ko-polimer etilen-propilen in polietilen (Zhang in sod., 2021). V raziskavi so razpravljali tudi o možnih virih onesnaženja tal s plastičnimi delci. Z μ -FT-IR analizo so ugotovili, da se najpogosteje za zastiranje tal uporabljajo plastične zastirke iz polietilena, ki v naravnih razmerah ni biorazgradljiv. Vsi lokalni pridelovalci so sicer zatrtili, da po končani pridelovalni sezoni zastirko poberejo s tal in reciklirajo. Vendar je iz prakse znano, da se del plastičnih zastirk poškoduje že pri polaganju zastirke na tla in kasneje v času presajanja rastlin, kar posledično privede do pojava fragmentov in plastičnih delcev v obliki folije v tleh. Kot možen vir onesnaženja tal s plastičnimi delci avtorji omenjajo tudi poplave. V poplavnih vodah so lahko plastični delci iz različnih virov kot so gospodinjski in industrijski odpadki, kot tudi cestni prah (Zhang et al., 2020). Ugotavljajo tudi, da predstavlja pomemben vir vnosa MP v tla tudi uporaba gnojil, predvsem tistih, ki so organskega izvora. Ugotovljeno je bilo, da kompostiran kokošji gnoj, ki je proizveden z biološko fermentacijo in kompostiranjem, vsebuje od 14 do 894 MP delcev/kg, delež fragmentov pa je bil 75–100 % (Huerta Lwanga in sod., 2016). Ne nazadnje je možen vir vnosa MP delcev v tla tudi voda za namakanje in prašni delci, ki pridejo v tla s padavinami, zato so ti najpogosteje najdeni v tleh pri pridelavi na prostem (Zhou in sod., 2020b).

Biorazgradljivi materiali za zastirke

Uporabo zastirk iz biorazgradljivih materialov je namenjena zmanjšanju kopičenja MP v tleh, vendar pa nekateri biorazgradljivi plastični materiali na kraju samem ne dosežejo pričakovane stopnje razgradnje. Ghimire in sod. (2020) so 4 leta spremljali razgradnjo biorazgradljive zastirke v tleh tako, da so jo po končani pridelovalni sezoni vdolali v tla. Po 2 letih je bil material v tleh prisoten v 70 %, po 4 letih pa še v 35 %.

Tudi uporaba PBAT kot biorazgradljivega materiala ne prinaša zelenih lastnosti po izboljšanju rasti razmer za pridelavo zelenjadnic, saj pogosto razpade še pred koncem rastne dobe. Pogosteje se to dogaja pri pridelavi na prostem, kjer je zastirka neposredno izpostavljena sončnemu sevanju, vetru, vlagi in temperaturnim nihanjem. Za izboljšanje mehanskih lastnosti se pogosto PBAT mešajo z drugimi biorazgradljivimi polimeri, kot so PLA, polipropilen karbonat (PPC) ali škrob (Touchaleaume in sod., 2016).

Drugi viri mikroplastike v tleh

Pri pridelavi zelenjadnic iz skupine plodovk (paradižnik, paprika, kumare) se za pritrjevanje rastlin k opori pogosto uporabljajo sintetične vrvice, največkrat iz polipropilena (PP). Po koncu rastne dobe se vrvice sicer odstranjujejo z objektov, vendar del materiala vedno ostane v tleh in se s časom spremeni v MP, ki se v tleh pojavlja v obliki vlaken. Kot vlaknati delci MP v kmetijskih tleh najdemo tudi ostanke vrvic v hmeljiščih in po žetvi žit, ko se vrvice uporabijo za vezanje bal sena (Guerrini in sod., 2017). Podobno se vlaknati materiali (PP) srednjih gostot (17–21 g/m²) uporabljajo za neposredno prekrivanje zelenjadnic v zgodnje pomladanskem obdobju, za zagotavljanje ustreznih rasti razmer za rast in s tem pospeševanje rasti v začetni fazi razvoja rastlin. Polipropilenski material najmanjših gostot (10 g/m²) pa se v integrirani in ekološki pridelavi uporabljajo za varovanje posevkov pred napadi škodljivcev (Giannoulis in sod., 2021). Prekrivke iz PP s posevka odstranimo, ko mine nevarnost napada škodljivcev, drobnih delci teh materialov pa ostajajo na njivah in predstavljajo neposreden vir vlaknatih oblik MP v tleh.

Neposreden vir MP predstavljajo tudi obloge iz plastičnih polimerov, ki obdajajo granule počasi delujočih mineralnih gnojil in pesticidov, čeprav raziskav o tem ni veliko. Katsumi in sod. (2021) poročajo o pojavu MP v tleh kot posledici uporabe mineralnih gnojil z oplaščenimi granulami za počasno sproščanje hranil. V tleh je bila količina delcev MP od 6 do 369 mg/kg tal.

Zaključki

Pregled obstoječe znanstvene literature potrjuje, da ima kmetijska plastika pomembno, a hkrati izrazito kompleksno vlogo v sodobnih agroekosistemih. Njena uporaba prinaša številne kratkoročne agronomske koristi, zlasti v intenzivni zelenjadarski pridelavi, kjer omogoča izboljšanje mikroklimatskih razmer, učinkovitejše upravljanje z vodo in hranili ter povečanje pridelka. Vendar pa dolgoročni procesi staranja, mehanskega razpada, fragmentacije in akumulacije plastičnih materialov v tleh, predvsem v obliki MP in nanoplastike, predstavljajo vse pomembnejši okoljski in agronomski izziv.

Bibliometrična analiza raziskovalnega področja je pokazala izrazito rast znanstvenega zanimanja za problematiko MP v tleh ter njene povezave s fizikalnimi, kemijskimi, biološkimi in ekotoksičnimi učinki, kar odraža jasen premik raziskovalnega fokusa od zgolj funkcionalnih in tehnoloških vidikov uporabe plastike k celostni obravnavi njenih okoljskih posledic. Kljub temu pregled literature razkriva številne raziskovalne vrzeli, zlasti glede dolgoročnih vplivov različnih tipov konvencionalnih, biološko osnovanih in biorazgradljivih materialov v realnih talnih razmerah ter njihove interakcije s talnimi organizmi, mikrobioto in ključnimi talnimi procesi.

Številne študije o onesnaženosti kmetijskih tal z MP poudarjajo večplastnost virov vnosa, ki so lahko neposredni (zastirne folije, kritine, prekrivke, vrvice, oplaščena mineralna gnojila in fitofarmaceutvska sredstva) ali posredni, preko uporabe organskih gnojil, kompostov, blata iz čistilnih naprav, namakalne vode ter poplavnih dogodkov. V talnem profilu se MP prenaša in prerazporeja s pomočjo fizikalnih, kemijskih in bioloških procesov ter okoljskih dejavnikov, kot so veter, intenzivne padavine in talna favna, kar omogoča njen prodor v globlje plasti tal in potencialno v podzemne vode.

Prisotnost MP v kmetijskih tleh predstavlja tveganje za delovanje talnih ekosistemov, kakovost površinskih in podzemnih vod ter posledično tudi za zdravje ljudi in varnost preskrbe s hrano. Prihodnje raziskave bi se morale osredotočiti na sistematično spremljanje pojava MP v talnih profilih in podtalnici, oceno prispevka posameznih virov ter na poglobljeno proučevanje vplivov MP in nanoplastike na fizikalne in kemijske lastnosti tal, rast in razvoj rastlin ter na sprejem in prenos plastičnih delcev v različne rastlinske organe. Ob tem je nujno razvijati in vrednotiti najboljše kmetijske prakse ter alternativne materiale, ki bodo omogočali učinkovito zmanjšanje onesnaženosti kmetijskih tal z MP ob hkratnem ohranjanju produktivnosti kmetijske pridelave.

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Konceptualizacija, Š.Ž. in N.K.M.; metodologija, Š.Ž.; formalna analiza, Š.Ž.; raziskava, Š.Ž. in N.K.M.; vir, Š.Ž. in N.K.M.; upravljanje podatkov, Š.Ž.; pisanje – priprava izvirnega osnutka, Š.Ž. in N.K.M.; pisanje – pregled in urejanje, Š.Ž. in N.K.M.; vizualizacija, Š.Ž.; nadzor, Š.Ž. in N.K.M.; upravljanje projekta, Š.Ž. in N.K.M.; pridobivanje sredstev, Š.Ž. in N.K.M. Vsi avtorji so prebrali in se strinjali z objavljeno različico rokopisa.

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Brief Note

Fruit-Derived Biostimulants Promote *In Vitro* Regeneration in Mature Calamansi (*Citrus microcarpa* Bunge) Embryos

Joseph Diaz^{1*}, Rich Milton Dulay^{2,3}, Sofronio Kalaw^{2,3},
Mary Jhane Valentino^{2,4}

Abstract

Several fruits in the Philippines are widely consumed for their delicious taste and health-promoting potential; however, some are discarded due to their unappealing taste, especially when overripe. The Saba banana (*Musa acuminata* var. *Balbiensis* L.) and mature coconut water (*Cocos nucifera* L.) are two of the most discarded fruits in the Philippines when over-ripe. Thus, to further utilise these products, their morphophysiological effects on the growth of mature Calamansi (*Citrus microcarpa* Bunge) embryos *in vitro* were assessed for their potential use as an alternative biostimulant during micropropagation. The study revealed that *in-vitro* growth of mature calamansi embryos was enhanced by the fruit extracts, even in the absence of synthetic hormone, 6-BAP, as shown by improvements in plant height, growth rate, shoot and root length, leaf size and leaf area, stomatal features such as density and aperture, chlorophyll content, and water retention percentage. These findings suggest that these commonly discarded fruits may serve as effective biostimulants and a cheaper alternative to synthetic hormones for plant tissue culture, particularly for calamansi micropropagation. This work supports the potential of agricultural by-products in advancing sustainable plant propagation practices.

Keywords

Micropropagation; morpho-physiology; calamansi embryo; discarded fruits; 6-benzyl-aminopurine

1 Department of Biology, College of Natural Sciences, Benguet State University, La Trinidad, Benguet, Philippines

2 Department of Biological Sciences, College of Science, Central Luzon State University, Science City of Muñoz, Nueva Ecija, Philippines

3 Center for Tropical Mushroom Research and Development, Department of Biological Sciences, College of Science, Central Luzon State University, Science City of Muñoz, Nueva Ecija, Philippines

4 Biotechnology and Analytical Laboratory, Department of Biological Sciences, College of Science, Central Luzon State University, Science City of Muñoz, Nueva Ecija, Philippines

* Corresponding author:

E-mail address: j.diaz@bsu.edu.ph

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Uporaba izbranih pogosto zavrženih filipinskih sadežev kot naravni biostimulant za *in vitro* regeneracijo zrelih zarodkov kalamansija (*Citrus microcarpa* Bunge)

Izvleček

Na Filipinih je, zaradi svojega okusnega okusa in zdravju koristnih lastnosti, razširjeno uživanje številnih vrst sadja. Kljub temu se nekateri plodovi, zlasti ko so prezreli, zavržejo zaradi neprivačnega okusa. Banana saba (*Musa acuminata* var. *balbiensis* L.) in voda zrelega kokosa (*Cocos nucifera* L.) sta med najbolj pogosto zavrženima sadežema na Filipinih, ko prezorita. Zato so bili za nadaljnjo uporabo teh proizvodov ocenjeni njihovi morfološko-fiziološki učinki na rast zrelega zarodka kalamansija (*Citrus microcarpa* Bunge) *in vitro*, z namenom raziskati njihovo morebitno uporabo kot alternativni biostimulant med mikropropagacijo. Raziskava je pokazala, da je bila *in vitro* rast zrelih zarodkov kalamansija izboljšana z izvlečki sadja, tudi v odsotnosti sintetičnega hormona 6-BAP, kar se je pokazalo v izboljšanju višine rastline, hitrosti rasti, dolžine poganjkov in korenin, velikosti listov in listne površine, lastnosti listnih rež, kot so gostota in odprtost, vsebnosti klorofila ter odstotka zadrževanja vode. Ti rezultati nakazujejo, da lahko pogosto zavrženo sadje služi kot učinkovit biostimulant in cenejša alternativa sintetičnim hormonom za tkivno kulturo rastlin, zlasti pri mikropropagaciji kalamansija. Delo podpira potencial kmetijskih stranskih proizvodov pri spodbujanju trajnostnih praks razmnoževanja rastlin.

Ključne besede

mikropropagacija; morfofiziologija; kalamansi zarodek; zavrženo sadje; 6-benzyl-aminopurine

Introduction

Global population growth and climate change continue to intensify abiotic stresses that limit crop productivity and threaten food security (Wallace et al., 2003; Parry, 2019). While conventional agricultural intensification has improved yields, it has also caused significant environmental degradation, prompting the search for sustainable and low-impact alternatives (Tilman et al., 2002; Foley et al., 2011). Among these, plant tissue culture has emerged as an effective strategy for the rapid propagation of uniform, disease-free planting materials, particularly for perennial horticultural crops.

Successful *in vitro* regeneration depends on the interaction between explant type, basal culture medium, and growth-regulating substances. Synthetic plant growth regulators (PGRs) are widely used to control morphogenesis; however, their high cost and environmental burden have stimulated interest in natural, plant-derived biostimulants (Bradford & Trewavas, 1994; Santner & Estelle, 2009). Fruit extracts, plant-derived liquids, and seaweed-based products contain endogenous phytohormones, vitamins, amino acids, and sugars that can promote cell division and differentiation *in vitro* (Hamdeni et al., 2022; Dumale et al., 2016; Azzam et al., 2022).

On the other hand, banana pulp and coconut water have been extensively used in plant tissue culture as organic supplements to enhance growth and regeneration. Nevertheless, most previous studies have incorporated these materials as additives to complex basal media or in combination with synthetic PGRs, limiting understanding of their independent biostimulant effects, particularly in citrus species (Bautista and Valentino 2023). Moreover, few studies have explored the use of locally discarded fruit materials as primary growth-promoting agents within simplified culture systems.

In the Philippines, overripe Saba banana (*Musa acuminata* var. *balbisiana*) and mature coconut water (*Cocos nucifera* L.) are commonly discarded in public markets despite their documented biochemical and biological potential (Tecson-Mendoza, 2007; Sidhu & Zafar, 2018; Diaz et al., 2025a). Their valorisation as natural biostimulants offers an opportunity to integrate sustainable waste utilisation with plant propagation technologies, contributing to circular bioeconomy approaches (Pontillas et al., 2025)

Calamansi (*Citrus microcarpa* Bunge) is a native and economically important citrus crop in the Philippines, valued for its culinary and industrial applications. However, its production has declined in recent years due to reduced planting areas, pest pressure, and climatic stress (PSA,

2017; PSA, 2023). In vitro propagation provides a promising means to support calamansi production by enabling rapid multiplication of high-quality planting materials. And recently, Diaz et al. (2025b) explored the use of exopolysaccharides from mushrooms as a biostimulant for Calamansi embryo culture in vitro.

Moreover, mature embryos were used as explants since they are developmentally stable, exhibit high regenerative potential, and reduce somaclonal variation compared with callus or vegetative tissues. Embryo culture also bypasses prolonged juvenile phases commonly encountered in citrus micropropagation and minimises contamination associated with field-derived explants (Miguel and Marum 2011; Catalano et al., 2022). Knudson C medium was selected as the basal medium due to its relatively simple nutrient composition, which allows clearer evaluation of biostimulant effects without interference from high salt concentrations or complex hormonal interactions characteristic of more commonly used media such as Murashige and Skoog (Hossain et al., 2010; Pradhan et al., 2016; Nongdam et al., 2023).

Hence, this study was to evaluate the effects of selected commonly discarded Philippine fruits as natural biostimulants on the in vitro regeneration of mature calamansi (*Citrus microcarpa* Bunge) embryos. It was hypothesised that fruit-derived extracts would enhance morphophysiological growth responses and could serve as cost-effective, sustainable alternatives to synthetic plant growth regulators in citrus micropropagation systems.

Materials and Methods

Plant Material and Sterilisation

Calamansi (*Citrus microcarpa*) seeds were obtained from a fresh, healthy Calamansi fruit. The seeds were then washed thoroughly with soap and running water and air-dried overnight. Once the seed coats became dry, they were manually removed and underwent further sterilisation. Seed sterilisation was done under a laminar airflow environment. The seeds were soaked in 5% NaOCl for 3-5 minutes, in bactericide for 10 minutes, 80% ethanol for 1 minute and 5 ppm plant preservation solution (PPS) for 15 minutes; and the seeds were rinsed with sterile distilled water three times after soaking. When fully sterilised, seeds were placed in a sterile petri plate with filter paper

for further drying, and 3 embryos from each seed were excised carefully and transferred to another petri plate with filter paper prior to inoculation.

Preparation of Tissue Culture Media

Knudson C Basal Media was used as basal medium for the mature Calamansi embryos. Over-ripe Saba banana extract and mature coconut water were supplemented on the Knudson C basal media at 2.5%, 5%, 7.5% and 10% concentration with and without 6-benzylaminopurine (6-BAP) at 1 ppm. Before autoclaving, the pH of the prepared media was adjusted to 5.7, and approximately 20 mL of the prepared media was poured into individual tissue culture bottles and sterilised (121°C, 15 psi) for 30 minutes.

Inoculation, Incubation and Morphophysiological Characterisation

Mature Calamansi embryos were inoculated aseptically on the previously sterilised tissue culture media with ten biological replicates (independent mature embryos) per treatment. After inoculation, the cultures were maintained in a plant growth chamber set at 25°C temperature, 40% humidity, and with a photoperiod of 16 hours light and 8 hours dark using cool white, fluorescent lamps at an intensity of approximately 60 mol m⁻² s⁻¹. After 21 days, the morphological characteristics such as shoots, roots and leaves were assessed along with the growth rate, fresh and dry weight. In addition, physiological parameters such as chlorophyll content, stomatal analysis and water loss percentage were recorded (Diaz et al., 2025b).

Plant Growth Rate (Height Increment)

Plant height was measured and calculated using a vernier calliper. The shoot length and root length of the plantlets were measured after 21 days, as well as the total length from the tip of the roots to the tip of the leaves. The average growth rate was computed by the total plant length divided by total incubation days (Diaz et al., 2025b).

Leaf Characterization

The leaf characters were evaluated after 21 days. The longest leaf length and width per treatment were measured using a vernier calliper. In computing the leaf size, the

length of the leaf is multiplied by its width (Schrader et al., 2021). The leaf area is computed by π (3.14) divided by 4 multiplied by the leaf length and leaf width (Shabani et al., 2016).

Chlorophyll Content Quantification

The fresh leaves of the plantlets were weighed, ground using a mortar and pestle with 3 mL of 80% acetone, and transferred to a conical tube. Chlorophyll extracts were collected and adjusted to 10 mL and centrifuged at 5000 rpm for 5 minutes. The derived supernatant was analysed for the total amount (mg/g) of chlorophyll estimation using a spectrophotometer at absorbances 645 and 663 nm. The obtained values were substituted in the formulas for the estimation of photosynthetic pigments (Lichtenthaler, 1987).

Water Loss Percentage

The total fresh weight from each treatment was measured using an analytical balance. To determine the oven-dry weight, the samples were placed in a drying oven at 40°C. The dry weight was recorded when the samples were at constant weight after several weighings. The percentage weight loss was calculated by subtracting the fresh and dry weight from the fresh weight multiplied by 100 (Diaz et al., 2025b).

Stomatal Analysis

The leaves from the plantlet were used by imprinting the stomata from the abaxial surface of the leaf using a thin layer of nail polish. Once dried, a piece of clear adhesive tape was pressed onto the nail-polished area, carefully removed, and mounted onto a glass slide. It was then viewed under a microscope at 400x magnification, and images were captured and processed using ImageJ software by obtaining the stomatal length, width, and aperture. Additionally, the stomatal density was obtained by calculating the number of stomata over the area of the field view (Diaz et al., 2025b).

Statistical Analysis

Data were expressed as mean \pm SD, with ten biological replicates (independent mature embryos) per treatment. The experiment followed a completely randomised design

(CRD). Differences among treatments were analysed using one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA), and mean values were compared using Dunnett's post-hoc test with Knudson C medium supplemented with 6-benzylaminopurine (BAP) as the positive control, using RStudio software. Data normality was assessed using the Shapiro–Wilk test, and homogeneity of variances was evaluated using Levene's test. When assumptions of ANOVA were not met, data were transformed or analysed using the Kruskal–Wallis test. A p-value < 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results

Plant Height and Growth Rate

As shown in Table 1, all treatments supplemented with Saba banana or mature coconut water extracts produced significantly greater plant height and growth rate compared to the control medium (Knudson C with 6-BAP). The control without 6-BAP exhibited minimal growth (3.30 mm plant height and 0.16 mm/day growth rate), highlighting the importance of organic supplementation for plant development. While treatments at 7.5% concentration showed numerically higher plant height, these values were not significantly different from the control beyond the overall treatment effect. The addition of 6-BAP did not consistently improve growth, as some treatments without 6-BAP showed comparable responses to the control.

Shoot and Root Length

Calamansi mature embryos grown in biostimulant-supplemented media, as shown in Table 1, exhibited greater shoot and root lengths compared to the control without 6-BAP (1.16 mm shoot length and 1.28 mm root length). Embryos cultured in mature coconut water (7.5–10%) without 6-BAP and in Saba banana extract (7.5%) without 6-BAP produced longer shoots than the control; however, these increases were not statistically significant beyond the overall treatment effect. Root length was also improved in organic extract treatments, with Saba banana extract (7.5%) without 6-BAP producing longer roots than the control, while coconut water treatments showed moderate increases. Overall, all organic extract treatments significantly improved shoot and root development compared to the control, which produced the shortest roots and shoots.

Tabela 1. Plant height, growth rate, shoot and root length of *in vitro* grown mature Calamansi Embryo in Knudson C with different fruit concentrations.Table 1. Višina rastline, hitrost rasti, dolžina poganjkov in korenin *in vitro* gojenega zrelega zarodka kalamansija v Knudson C z različnimi koncentracijami sadja.

Treatments	Plant Height (mm)	Growth Rate (mm/day)	Shoot (mm)	Root (mm)
Saba Banana (2.5%) w/o 6-BAP	40.29±10.98a	1.91±0.52a	21.14±5.62a	19.15±8.27a
Saba Banana (5%) w/o 6-BAP	46.48±15.49a	2.21±0.73a	24.83±13.61a	21.65±2.98a
Saba Banana (7.5%) w/o 6-BAP	59.51±2.62a	2.83±0.12a	35.50±2.67a	24.01±0.95a
Saba Banana (10%) w/o 6-BAP	47.22±6.73a	2.24±0.32a	24.04±3.23a	22.42±4.05a
Saba Banana (2.5%) w/ 6-BAP	25.93±8.42b	1.23±0.40a	18.55±2.77a	7.37±6.12a
Saba Banana (5%) w/ 6-BAP	34.87±5.58a	1.66±0.26a	23.15±2.83a	11.71±4.20a
Saba Banana (7.5%) w/ 6-BAP	36.19±8.52a	1.72±0.40a	21.68±5.49a	14.51±7.14a
Saba Banana (10%) w/ 6-BAP	31.48±9.85a	1.49±0.68a	21.35±9.59a	10.12±6.17a
Coconut Water (2.5%) w/o 6-BAP	31.93±5.38a	1.52±0.25a	22.24±8.20a	9.36±5.64a
Coconut Water (5%) w/o 6-BAP	42.53±9.43a	2.02±0.44a	27.61±16.73a	10.81±3.39a
Coconut Water (7.5%) w/o 6-BAP	46.81±1.47a	2.22±0.07a	38.67±16.73a	14.27±8.46a
Coconut Water (10%) w/o 6-BAP	41.89±24.07a	1.99±1.14a	37.75±3.14a	9.05±1.67a
Coconut Water (2.5%) w/ 6-BAP	31.43±16.69a	1.49±0.79a	22.57±6.63a	8.86±10.06a
Coconut Water (5%) w/ 6-BAP	33.87±8.90a	1.61±0.42a	25.25±5.83a	8.61±4.28a
Coconut Water (7.5%) w/ 6-BAP	30.52±7.78a	1.45±0.37a	22.60±5.46a	7.91±2.97a
Coconut Water (10%) w/ 6-BAP	27.91±8.42a	1.32±0.40a	19.55±7.83a	8.36±0.61a
Knudson C w/o 6-BAP	3.30±0.60b	0.16±0.02b	1.16±0.83b	1.28±0.18b
Knudson C w/ 6-BAP	30.47±6.47a	1.45±0.30a	22.78±4.51a	7.52±2.25a

Values are expressed as mean ± SD. Means with the same letter superscripts are not significantly different at 5% level of significance using Dunnett's Test (Knudson C w/ 6-BAP).

Tabela 2. Leaf characters, total chlorophyll content and percentage water loss of *in vitro* grown mature Calamansi embryo in Knudson C with different fruit concentrations.Table 2. Listne značilnosti, skupna vsebnost klorofila in odstotek izgube vode *in vitro* gojenega zrelega zarodka kalamansija v Knudson C z različnimi koncentracijami sadja.

Treatments	Leaf Size (mm)	Leaf Area (mm ²)	Total Chlorophyll Content (mg/g)	Water Loss (%)
Saba Banana (2.5%) w/o 6-BAP	13.20±8.41 ^b	10.36±6.60 ^b	5.19±1.63 ^b	70.14±0.40 ^a
Saba Banana (5%) w/o 6-BAP	19.63±15.14 ^b	15.41±11.88 ^b	6.49±2.14 ^b	80.45±8.82 ^a
Saba Banana (7.5%) w/o 6-BAP	60.38±14.27 ^a	47.40±11.20 ^a	27.81±0.94 ^a	75.21±11.71 ^a
Saba Banana (10%) w/o 6-BAP	19.62±0.81 ^a	15.40±0.63 ^b	13.71±5.67 ^b	72.46±7.82 ^a
Saba Banana (2.5%) w/ 6-BAP	15.24±6.80 ^b	12.47±2.68 ^b	5.53±1.93 ^b	77.57±0.52 ^a
Saba Banana (5%) w/ 6-BAP	46.14±29.71 ^a	12.63±4.68 ^b	4.64±1.04 ^b	78.98±8.33 ^a
Saba Banana (7.5%) w/ 6-BAP	62.20±43.76 ^a	12.68±4.07 ^b	4.26±0.60 ^b	72.40±8.17 ^a
Saba Banana (10%) w/ 6-BAP	19.30±11.61 ^a	15.15±0.63 ^b	4.07±0.74 ^b	65.32±8.92 ^a
Coconut Water (2.5%) w/o 6-BAP	8.03±5.81 ^b	6.30±4.56 ^b	4.54±1.27 ^b	77.42±6.97 ^a
Coconut Water (5%) w/o 6-BAP	18.78±8.17 ^b	14.74±6.41 ^b	4.81±1.36 ^b	79.56±8.51 ^a

Coconut Water (7.5%) w/o 6-BAP	52.32±59.65 ^a	41.07±46.83 ^a	12.24±3.28 ^b	82.24±7.67 ^a
Coconut Water (10%) w/o 6-BAP	78.98±3.96 ^a	62.01±3.11 ^a	34.74±7.2 ^a	67.26±9.22 ^a
Coconut Water (2.5%) w/ 6-BAP	21.87±20.04 ^a	23.30±13.50 ^a	10.22±3.09 ^b	82.40±7.67 ^a
Coconut Water (5%) w/ 6-BAP	77.86±58.61 ^a	20.35±13.62 ^a	16.90±5.59 ^b	82.88±3.44 ^a
Coconut Water (7.5%) w/ 6-BAP	103.32±9.58 ^a	20.56±13.75 ^a	14.09±2.68 ^b	71.95±4.55 ^a
Coconut Water (10%) w/ 6-BAP	23.23±17.43 ^a	18.23±13.68 ^a	12.98±7.85 ^b	59.31±10.32 ^a
Knudson C w/o 6-BAP	0.61±0.16 ^b	0.47±0.13 ^b	9.05±4.95 ^b	71.09±5.67 ^a
Knudson C w/ 6-BAP	36.32±9.70 ^a	28.5±10.39 ^a	39.73±3.91 ^a	69.60±10.43 ^a

Values are expressed as mean ± SD. Means with the same letter superscripts are not significantly different at 5% level of significance using Dunnett's Test (Knudson C w/ 6 BAP).

Leaf Characters and Chlorophyll Content

For leaf characteristics (Table 2), treatments supplemented with coconut water (7.5–10%), with or without 6-BAP, produced larger leaves than the control without fruit extract, which had the smallest leaves (0.61 mm length and 0.47 mm² area). Saba banana treatments also resulted in greater leaf size than the control. Although numerical differences were observed among the organic treatments, all treatments produced significantly larger leaves compared to the control.

Total chlorophyll content (Table 2) was higher in organic extract treatments than in the control without 6-BAP (9.05 mg/g). Coconut water at 10% without 6-BAP and Saba banana at 7.5% without 6-BAP showed higher chlorophyll values than the control. Some treatments with 6-BAP had lower chlorophyll levels; however, differences among treatments were not statistically significant except in comparison with the control.

Water Content Loss

Water loss (Table 2) varied across treatments, but differences among treatments were not statistically significant except when compared with the control (71.09% without 6-BAP; 69.60% with 6-BAP). Some treatments exhibited higher or lower water loss than the control, indicating that fruit extract supplementation influenced water retention, although the overall treatment effects were comparable to the control.

Stomatal Characteristics

Stomatal traits (length, width, density, and aperture) shown in Table 3 generally did not differ significantly from the control. However, stomatal density was significantly lower in the control without 6-BAP (117.97/mm²) compared with the organic extract treatments. Other stomatal measurements varied slightly among treatments but remained statistically comparable to the control. Overall, organic supplementation produced stomatal characteristics similar to or slightly improved relative to the control without 6-BAP.

Tabela 3. Stomatal characteristics of *in vitro* grown mature Calamansi Embryo in Knudson C with different fruit concentrations.

Table 3. Stomatne značilnosti *in vitro* gojenega zrelega zarodka kalamansija v Knudson C z različnimi koncentracijami sadja.

Treatments	Length (µm)	Width (µm)	Density (per mm ²)	Aperture (µm)
Saba Banana (2.5%) w/o 6-BAP	5.06±0.36 ^a	5.03±0.25 ^a	182.38±33.27 ^a	0.97±0.12 ^a
Saba Banana (5%) w/o 6-BAP	5.10±0.71 ^a	5.73±0.85 ^a	186.58±13.09 ^a	0.99±0.14 ^a
Saba Banana (7.5%) w/o 6-BAP	5.27±0.61 ^a	5.23±0.64 ^a	194.96±45.35 ^a	1.01±0.07 ^a
Saba Banana (10%) w/o 6-BAP	5.02±0.20 ^a	4.94±0.46 ^a	199.16±25.41 ^a	1.08±0.13 ^a
Saba Banana (2.5%) w/ 6-BAP	5.2±0.44 ^a	4.83±0.14 ^a	205.45±25.41 ^a	0.89±0.22 ^a
Saba Banana (5%) w/ 6-BAP	5.31±0.30 ^a	5.02±0.26 ^a	201.25±6.28 ^a	1.01±0.15 ^a
Saba Banana (7.5%) w/ 6-BAP	5.33±0.47 ^a	4.96±0.23 ^a	192.87±15.82 ^a	0.84±0.04 ^a

Saba Banana (10%) w/ 6-BAP	6.74±0.89 ^a	4.92±0.11 ^a	186.58±7.26 ^a	0.82±0.13 ^a
Coconut Water (2.5%) w/o 6-BAP	4.66±0.41 ^a	4.85±0.13 ^a	194.96±10.89 ^a	1.26±0.18 ^a
Coconut Water (5%) w/o 6-BAP	5.13±0.42 ^a	5.02±0.26 ^a	208.65±17.23 ^a	1.09±0.32 ^a
Coconut Water (7.5%) w/o 6-BAP	5.36±0.43 ^a	5.07±0.17 ^a	178.19±19.21 ^a	1.03±0.16 ^a
Coconut Water (10%) w/o 6-BAP	5.62±0.34 ^a	4.92±0.52 ^a	174.00±62.04 ^a	0.92±0.14 ^a
Coconut Water (2.5%) w/ 6-BAP	5.11±0.10 ^a	5.73±0.85 ^a	182.38±22.67 ^a	0.98±0.11 ^a
Coconut Water (5%) w/ 6-BAP	5.27±0.13 ^a	5.23±0.64 ^a	188.67±33.27 ^a	1.13±0.15 ^a
Coconut Water (7.5%) w/ 6-BAP	5.15±0.21 ^a	5.09±0.27 ^a	190.77±15.82 ^a	0.95±0.05 ^a
Coconut Water (10%) w/ 6-BAP	5.10±0.89 ^a	4.81±0.51 ^a	209.64±62.99 ^a	0.86±0.14 ^a
Knudson C w/o 6-BAP	4.46±0.52 ^a	3.62±0.90 ^b	117.97±15.97 ^b	0.87±0.09 ^a
Knudson C w/ 6-BAP	5.26±0.35 ^a	4.81±0.23 ^a	192.87±42.81 ^a	0.94±0.13 ^a

Values are expressed as mean ± SD. Means with the same letter superscripts are not significantly different at 5% level of significance using Dunnett's Test (Knudson C w/ 6-BAP).

Discussion

Plant tissue culture depends on nutrients, hormones, organic compounds, and environmental factors (Pasternak & Steinmacher, 2024). Various basal media have been developed, including Knudson C (Knudson et al., 1946), Vacin and Went (Vacin & Went, 1949), Hyponex (Kano, 1965), and Murashige and Skoog (Murashige & Skoog, 1962), with Murashige and Skoog being widely used for many plant species (Kumara et al., 2022). Despite their effectiveness, the high costs of basal media components necessitate exploring affordable alternatives. In this study, Knudson C medium was supplemented with fruit wastes, such as Saba banana and mature coconut water, to evaluate their effects on the *in vitro* growth of mature calamansi embryos.

On the other hand, shoot and root length are critical indicators of morphogenesis and plantlet vigour. Shoot elongation reflects proper shoot initiation, while root length ensures efficient nutrient uptake and acclimatisation (Rokosa & Kulpa, 2019). The results showed that 6-BAP enhanced shoot length in some cases, but lower to moderate concentrations of fruit extracts without 6-BAP often promoted better root elongation, particularly with Saba banana. Coconut water favoured shoot growth more than root elongation, likely due to its cytokinin content (Ge et al., 2005). Treatments without organic supplementation, especially Knudson C without 6-BAP, resulted in the poorest growth, emphasising the importance of fruit-derived additives in supplying vitamins, sugars, amino acids, and natural plant growth regulators (Mok & Mok, 2001; Ge et al., 2005; David et al., 2015; Lazim et al., 2015; Gansau et al., 2016;

Mardhikari et al., 2020). High cytokinin levels from 6-BAP sometimes inhibited root growth, consistent with previous reports (Auer, 1996; Laplaze et al., 2007; Thorpe, 2008).

Moreover, leaf development is another important indicator of physiological status and photosynthetic potential. Coconut water at moderate to high concentrations (7.5–10%) enhanced leaf size, likely due to synergistic effects of endogenous and exogenous cytokinins promoting cell proliferation (Werner et al., 2001; Yong et al., 2009). Saba banana showed positive effects at intermediate concentrations, reflecting its natural hormone content (Islam et al., 2015; Qiao et al., 2024). In contrast, the basal medium alone produced the smallest leaves, highlighting the necessity of organic supplementation for optimal growth (Bhojwani & Razdan, 1986).

Furthermore, chlorophyll content, indicative of photosynthetic capacity, varied with organic supplementation and 6-BAP application. Higher concentrations of Saba banana sometimes reduced chlorophyll, possibly due to osmotic stress or over-proliferation under high cytokinin influence (Hamdeni et al., 2022; Lee et al., 2022; Rassol et al., 2024; Wang & Yeh, 2024). Treatments with moderate supplementation maintained higher chlorophyll, suggesting better physiological performance and potential acclimatisation success (Preece & Suther, 1991; Yang et al., 2015; Gonzales-Alvarado & Cardoso, 2024).

Additionally, water content, critical for cell turgor and metabolic activity, was highest in 2.5–5% coconut water treatments with 6-BAP, likely reflecting enhanced cellular hydration due to cytokinins, sugars, and vitamins (Yong et al., 2009; Lazim et al., 2015). In contrast, 10% coconut water

or high Saba banana concentrations reduced water loss, possibly due to denser tissue or slower metabolic activity, which can favour acclimatisation (Hura et al., 2007; Preece & Suther, 1991; Deb & Imchen, 2010; Bag et al., 2019). Optimal tissue growth appears to result from moderate supplementation balancing growth promotion and water retention (Rout et al., 2000a).

Also, stomatal characteristics provide insights into plantlet physiological status. Treatments with coconut water or Saba banana, especially combined with 6-BAP, produced larger stomatal complexes and wider apertures, suggesting enhanced gas exchange potential (Hetherington & Woodward, 2003; Pillitteri & Torii, 2012; Farber et al., 2016). Knudson C alone had the smallest stomata, underscoring the importance of organic additives for microanatomical development and balanced auxin-cytokinin interactions (Bhojwani & Razdan, 1986; Sosnowski et al., 2023).

Overall, these results indicate that fruit-derived organic supplements can partially replace exogenous hormones, enhancing morphogenesis, physiological health, and tissue quality in calamansi embryo culture. The effects are concentration-dependent, highlighting the importance of optimising supplementation levels to maximise plantlet growth and acclimatisation potential.

Conclusions

The study demonstrated that the *in vitro* growth of mature calamansi embryos was enhanced by Saba banana and mature coconut water extracts, even in the absence of synthetic hormones 6-BAP, as shown by improvements in plant height, shoot and root length, leaf traits, stomatal features, chlorophyll content, and water retention. These findings suggest that commonly discarded fruit extracts can serve as effective organic supplements and/or hormone replacement for plant tissue culture, particularly for Calamansi micropropagation. Further chemical analysis

and hormone quantification are recommended to identify the active compounds responsible for the observed growth-promoting effects. This work supports the potential of agricultural by-products in advancing sustainable plant propagation practices.

Author Contributions

Conceptualization, J.C.D.; methodology, J.C.D. and M.J.G.V.; software, J.C.D.; validation, M.J.G.V., S.P.K. and R.M.R.D.; formal analysis, J.C.D.; investigation, J.C.D.; resources, J.C.D., M.J.G.V., R.M.R.D., S.P.K.; data curation, J.C.D.; writing—original draft preparation, J.C.D.; writing—review and editing, J.C.D., M.J.G.V., R.M.R.D., S.P.K.; visualization, J.C.D. and M.J.G.V.; supervision, M.J.G.V., R.M.R.D., S.P.K.; All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

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Data Availability

Research data is available at Zenodo (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19044104>).

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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Acta Biologica Slovenica 2026 Vol. 69 | Št. 2